

Servant leadership in SMEs: A study of Scotland

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This thesis is submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the West of Scotland for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

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I declare that this thesis has not been submitted for another comparable academic award.

Signed:

Personal details withheld.

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ABSTRACT

Servant leadership was developed as an alternative to the heroic leadership which was prevalent within the USA during the 1970s. It is considered an ethical form of leadership, which is concerned with putting the needs of the followers first. The servant leader aims to serve the follower, providing support and guidance wherever possible. Much literature currently exists concerning the traits and characteristics necessary for servant leadership. However, the research concerning the skills of a servant leader is still in its infancy.

The aim of this research therefore was to examine the potential skills necessary for servant leadership. Furthermore, it aimed to determine a possible and plausible definition of servant leadership whilst examining its impact upon organisations. The research began by conducting a systematic literature review in order to determine the gaps in the servant leadership literature. It confirmed that the skills necessary for servant leadership was lacking and therefore determined that this is an area of research which needed further exploration.

The research conducted qualitative research to determine the skills necessary for servant leadership. This research was guided by an inductive approach and underpinned by both a social constructivist and interpretivist philosophy. In order to collect the data, semi structured interviews were conducted. The participants involved in the research were purposively selected leaders and employees within Small to Medium Enterprises in Scotland. The research consisted of 30 participants: 15 leaders and 15 employees.

The skills that this research found to be necessary for servant leadership; were people management and development, technical skills, interpersonal skills, servanthood and conceptual skills. Within the research it was noted that servant leadership impacts upon employee work climates, organisational citizenship behaviour, public service motivation and organisational growth within SMEs. The research presents an empirical framework which indicates the relationship between the skills necessary for servant leadership within SMEs and its impact upon

organisations. This research further provided a possible definition for servant leadership, which was lacking in the field.

By addressing its aims and objectives, this research contributed to knowledge by producing new findings in the skills field, which previously remained relatively undeveloped. Through these findings the research addressed both theoretical and methodological gaps in the existing field. The research was conducted in a unique geographical context and resulted in robust empirical findings. Its definition and the framework presented help to broaden the knowledge in the field of servant leadership.

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CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION:

The concept of servant leadership has ancient roots, being identified within ancient monarchs and historical religious figures (Nair, 1994; Sendjaya and Sarros 2002). However, servant leadership was not formally developed until the 1970s by Robert Greenleaf. Yet, it remains the case, that due to the populous and saturated area of leadership studies, research into servant leadership has often been overlooked in preference of the more 'popular' leadership approaches (Boyum, 2006). Despite its relative obscurity, it remains a topic which has continued to generate interest throughout the 21st century (Russell, 2016; Sendjaya and Sarros, 2002). Academics, leaders and researchers continue to be fascinated by servant leadership and its paradoxes and promises (Stone et al., 2004). It continues to be an important area of study due to its contribution to success within organisations (Harrison, 2018).

Since its initial inception there has been continuous advancement and development in the field. Despite this, there remains no universal definition of servant leadership (Lussier and Achua, 2016). This research therefore aims to provide a clear and concise definition of servant leadership. Additionally, upon an extensive and systematic analysis of the existing research, it has become apparent that a skills perspective of servant leadership is still lacking, both empirically and with regards to a conceptual framework. In order to address this gap within the field, this research will conduct an analysis of servant leaders within Scottish small and medium enterprises (SMEs), to explore the skills that could be considered necessary for them to lead effectively. This research will be empirical and consist of multi-level analysis to allow for a consensus and thus a framework to be developed regarding the skills shown to found within for servant leaders in SMEs.

This chapter will therefore examine the aims and objectives of the research. It will then proceed to provide an overview of servant leadership. Then the originality of this research will be explored and discussed in depth. This chapter will conclude with giving a general overview as to the contents of this research.

1.2 RESEARCH AIMS, OBJECTIVES AND QUESTIONS

This chapter will now proceed to address the research aims and objectives.

1.2.1 RESEARCH AIM:

The aim of a body of research is concerned with the main overarching purpose of what the research wants to achieve (Thomas and Hodges, 2010). The research aim specifies what needs to be studied by the research and achieving the aim will answer the research questions, which will be discussed in the literature review chapter (Dudovsky, 2018).

Therefore, the aim of this research is to examine servant leadership within SMEs and to determine the necessary skills for success.

1.2.2 OBJECTIVES:

Research objectives are used to guide the research and to determine the information they wish to obtain (Neelankavil, 2007). In turn, the research should be able to meet the objectives which it has set out. Research objectives define the specific aims of the study (Hanson, 2006). They are used as a statement of purpose in a study which does not have a hypothesis. Research objectives divide the researcher's aim into several parts and address them separately (Dudovsky, 2018). The objectives for this research are as follows:

- *To identify the skills necessary for servant leadership within SMEs*
- *To determine the organisational impact of servant leadership on SMEs*
- *To develop an empirical based framework of the servant leadership skills necessary within SMEs which contributes to the existing theory*
- *To provide a definition of servant leadership*

Research questions on the other hand, are informed by a familiarity with the topic (Haynes, 2006). Questions will then arise from a determined knowledge deficit within

the field (Hulley et al. 2007). This research will therefore determine research questions as a result of the literature review, which will be conducted in Chapter 2.

1.3 WHAT IS SERVANT LEADERSHIP?

As previously mentioned, servant leadership is often described as paradoxical as it is concerned with the leader being viewed as a servant (Harrison, 2018). The duality of the nature of servant leadership means it is an often-misunderstood concept. The concept of servant leadership is overall probably best described by Greenleaf when he states that:

“The servant is leader first, it begins with the natural feeling that one wants to serve, to serve first. Then conscious choice brings one to aspire to lead”

(Greenleaf, 1998:4).

Although it is often compared to transformational leadership, it has been stated that transformational leaders may be unethical and behave in ways which are self-serving, thus differing them from servant leaders (Hoch et al., 2018). Servant leaders aim to behave ethically to serve and contribute to the development and empowerment of their followers.

1.4 RESEARCH RATIONALE

Interest in servant leadership has continued to grow. It is continuously being viewed as a viable alternative to the previous heroic approaches found in organisational leadership. In addition to an alternative to previously used approaches to leadership, servant leadership has been advised as a relief to the societal pressures placed on people within business (Greenleaf, 1998). It is often a more inclusive approach to leadership where leaders are viewed as the supporters of teams rather than the chiefs (Irving and Longbotham, 2007). This research is relevant because whilst the study of leadership is vast, servant leadership is still an area of research lacking in any real qualitative data that can be studied and learned from (Page and Wong, 2000). This means it is a topic that people are interested in and would be willing to partake and learn from. Furthermore, whilst its importance as a practice is

acknowledged, it has been highlighted that it is an area which could benefit from further study, which will be provided by this research. (Parris and Peachey, 2013).

The implications for theory from this research are substantial. It has the potential to develop a new area of servant leadership which has not yet been explored, that may in turn inspire further research and development of theory. Furthermore, the theory can be used as a learning tool by practitioners of servant leadership, potential future leaders, and as a training aid for employees within the workplace.

In addition, there is no concise definition of servant leadership. Greenleaf himself does not provide an explicit definition of servant leadership (Andersen, 2009; Laub, 1999). At present, researchers use a plethora of different definitions and constructs to measure servant leadership (Harrison, 2018). Therefore, this research aims to provide a comprehensive and encompassing definition of servant leadership, which at present is lacking within the field.

According to Phillips (1993), research should contribute to knowledge in a way that has not already been done. This research's contribution to knowledge is largely concerned with generating knowledge surrounding the skills of servant leadership, which is, at present, very limited. It is the case that Bottum and Lenz stated that the following skills are necessary for servant leadership:

"Communication skills and empathetic listening, conflict- resolution, problem solving, consensus decision making, and community building"

(Bottum and Lenz, 1998, p. 164).

Surprisingly, whilst Bottum and Lenz (1998) state that skills are necessary for servant leadership, their research is not supported empirically. Additionally, the skill set required for servant leaders as a whole is not identified within this research. It has previously been highlighted that the servant leadership literature is particularly lacking in skills research in general (Mcquade et al., 2020). This research, when completed, will be relevant, up to date and validated by empirical evidence. It will highlight the skills found in servant leaders within SMEs and it will additionally develop an empirical based framework from those findings.

This research is also concerned with examining SMEs within a European nation, rather than the American studies that currently exists. Therefore, this research will contribute to the existing knowledge within the field of servant leadership, by providing a comprehensive definition of servant leadership. Additionally, it will develop a framework to be used by those who practise servant leadership and those who wish to implement this leadership approach in their organisation. This research can therefore be used both within academia, and by practicing and aspiring servant leaders in industry.

1.5 ORIGINALITY OF RESEARCH:

Research can be justified by the contribution and development it provides to its relevant discipline and based upon its originality within the field. (Pugh and Phillips, 2005). There are many different definitions of originality in research. However, this research is original according to the definitions discussed by Phillips (cited in Pugh and Phillips, 2005) which will now be explored in greater detail. According to Phillips (cited in Pugh and Phillips, 2005) research can be original in the following ways:

- Carrying out empirical work that hasn't been done before.
- Making a synthesis that hasn't been made before.
- Using already known material but with new interpretation.
- Trying out something in Britain that has previously only been done abroad.
- Taking a particular technique and applying it in a new area.
- Bringing new evidence to bear on an old issue.
- Being cross-disciplinary and using different methodologies.
- Looking at areas that people in the discipline haven't looked at before.
- Adding to knowledge in a way that hasn't previously been done before

(Phillips, cited in Pugh and Phillips, 2005)

Additionally, according to Pugh and Phillips, originality can be outlined in the following ways:

- Setting down a major piece of new information in writing for the first time.
- Continuing a previously original piece of work.
- Carrying out original work designed by the supervisor.
- Providing a single original technique, observation or result in an otherwise unoriginal but competent piece of research.
- Having many original ideas, methods and interpretations all performed by others under the direction of the postgraduate.
- Showing originality in testing someone else's idea

(Pugh and Phillips, 2005, p. 62)

Therefore, in accordance with the two frameworks outlined, this research is original in the following ways:

1.5.1 TRYING OUT SOMETHING IN BRITAIN THAT HAS PREVIOUSLY ONLY BEEN DONE ABROAD

This research will be conducted within Scotland, whereas it has previously only been conducted abroad (Phillips, 1993). Whilst research has been conducted regarding servant leadership in SMEs (Claxton, 2014; McNeff and Irving, 2017), these studies were conducted within the North American context; this research will focus on SMEs within Scotland. Furthermore, whilst Pinnington (2011) looks at servant leadership in Scotland, this research conducts a comparison between five different styles of leadership, rather than focusing solely on servant leadership. It is also concerned with leadership development rather than the skills perspective which this research aims to examine.

1.5.2 LOOKING AT AREAS WITHIN THE DISCIPLINE THAT PEOPLE HAVEN'T LOOKED AT BEFORE

Within other approaches, much research has examined the necessary skills for leadership (Harrison, 2018). However, there remains limited research concerning skills within servant leadership, and the existing research is concerned only with one

or two skills in servant leadership, rather than providing a broad overview (Mcquade et al., 2020). For example, both O'Sherman (2019) and Barbuto et al. (2014) look at the skill of emotional intelligence as displayed by servant leaders. Additionally, Gigliotti and Dwyer (2016) focus upon communication skills and Hu and Liden (2011) touches briefly upon conceptual skills. This therefore highlights that whilst studies exist, they are limited to focusing only on one specific skill concerning servant leadership, whereas this research aims to identify all the necessary skills of a servant leader. Additionally, the aforementioned studies were conducted in the American and Chinese context, whereas this research will be looked at within a European context.

1.5.3 SETTING DOWN A MAJOR PIECE OF NEW INFORMATION IN WRITING FOR THE FIRST TIME

This research will develop a framework concerning the skills necessary for servant leadership, and its impact upon organisations therefore setting down a major piece of new information in writing for the first time.

Overall, originality can be said to be concerned with adding to knowledge in a way that has not been done before (Phillips, 1993). This research's contribution is largely concerned with generating knowledge surrounding the skills of servant leadership, which is currently limited. It contributes to knowledge within the discipline by looking at SMEs within a European nation, rather than the American studies which currently exists. Furthermore, the framework which will be developed within this research is unique, thereby creating knowledge in a way that hasn't been done before.

1.5.4 CARRYING OUT ORIGINAL WORK DESIGNED BY THE SUPERVISOR

This work was originally designed by the PhD supervisor, although it has been adapted, since its original inception. Therefore, it can be said to be adhering to the criterion of carrying out original work which was designed by the supervisor.

1.5.5 CARRYING OUT EMPIRICAL WORK THAT HASN'T BEEN DONE BEFORE

This research will be carrying out empirical work in order to determine the skills necessary for servant leadership within SMEs. As of yet, there has not been empirical research into this specific area regarding leadership skills as a whole, rather research tends to focus on one or two specific skills. Therefore, this research will be original in that respect. Additionally, Yigit and Bokzurt (2017) highlight that most research on servant leadership is quantitative. This research will therefore carry out original empirical work that will adopt qualitative research methods.

1.5.6 LOOKING AT AREAS THAT PEOPLE IN THE DISCIPLINE HAVEN'T LOOKED AT BEFORE

As previously mentioned, the servant leadership skills necessary for SMEs have not yet been explored within the discipline as a whole. This research will fill that gap in knowledge, therefore highlighting its originality.

Overall, this section has highlighted the numerous ways in which this research proves to be original. Out of the 15 different ways in which research can be original as aforementioned, this research has shown to be original in six different ways. The next section of this research will therefore proceed to highlight the ways in which this research will provide a contribution to knowledge.

1.6 CONTRIBUTION TO KNOWLEDGE:

It is the case that a doctoral thesis is supposed to provide an original contribution to knowledge within the field, in a global context (Tesch et al., 2015). According to Petre and Rugg (2010), originality is concerned with contributing to the existing discourse within the field. It is concerned with providing evidence of a conclusion that is worthwhile (Petre and Rugg, 2010). In order to prove the contribution to knowledge of this research, it will aim to answer the following questions, which have

been suggested in order to measure the contribution of one's research. They are as follows:

- The importance of the question. (Why is it worth asking?)
- The significance of the findings (Why should anyone care? Why do they matter?)
- The implications for theory
- The limitations of the research

(Petre and Rugg, 2004, p15).

1.6.1. THE IMPORTANCE OF THE QUESTION. (WHY IS IT WORTH ASKING?)

In reference to the research objective 'What is servant leadership?' It is worth answering as it has long been the case that there is no clear definition of servant leadership and therefore it is necessary for one to be developed. It is also necessary to ask the question 'What are the skills necessary for servant leaders within SMEs?' because the answers to this question can be used to help leaders within SMEs lead effectively. It is equally important to ask, 'What is servant leadership?' because for those in leadership in SMEs, it will help them to determine whether or not servant leadership is the correct form of leadership to adopt. Finally, it is important to query 'Does servant leadership impact upon performance for SMEs?' This allows us to evaluate the effectiveness of servant leadership through assessing its impact upon performance

1.6.2 THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE FINDINGS (WHY SHOULD ANYONE CARE? WHY DO THEY MATTER?)

It has been stated that within scholarly literature that there is a theoretical disunity with regards to the effectiveness of servant leadership within organisations (Brown

and Bryant, 2015). This research will address whether or not they are effective within organisations which are classified as SMEs and help to put an end to the disunity within the literature. It is also important to look at SMEs within Scotland as they make up 99.4% of private sector businesses (Scottish Government, 2015). It is therefore crucial that effective leadership styles are identified for SMEs to promote their success. This involves examining servant leadership as it has been stated that it has profound implications for both the individuals and organisations who choose to adopt this approach (Guillaume et al., 2012). Furthermore, a comprehensive literature on skills in servant leadership does not yet exist, and with the wealth of knowledge existent on the topic, it is important to highlight the new areas of research which have not yet been focused on. In addition, the framework which is developed can be used by servant leaders to grow and develop their leadership. As an area of research gaining more prominence, it is still the case that as of yet, no universal definition of servant leadership has been provided (Lussier and Achua, 2016). This research aims to rectify this and examine if one can be provided.

Overall, the positive effects of practising servant leadership have been found to be creativity and innovation, trust in leaders, organisational citizenship behaviour, job satisfaction and employee work engagement (Newman et al., 2017). Therefore, it is important to develop a framework in order to allow leaders to adopt an approach which both their employees and organisations will benefit from.

1.7 THE IMPLICATIONS FOR THEORY

The implications for theory from this research are substantial. It has the potential to develop a new area of servant leadership which has not yet been explored. This may in turn inspire further research and development of theory. Furthermore, the theory can be used as a learning tool by practitioners of servant leadership, potential future leaders, and as a training aid for employees within the workplace.

1.8 THE LIMITATIONS OF THE RESEARCH

The limitations of this research could be said to be geographical, as it is only being conducted within one country. However, it could also be stated that this is not

entirely a limitation. Yigit and Boskurt (2017) highlighted that between 2015 and 2016, the majority of research examining servant leadership was done within the USA and China. Therefore, it is a unique context which has not yet been explored and considering the wealth of literature which exists concerning servant leadership in Asia and North America it adds a new perspective to the research.

1.9 RESEARCH OVERVIEW

The research is divided into chapters. This chapter will now provide a brief overview of these chapters and the research in general.

1.9.1 CHAPTER 1:

The first chapter is the introduction, which provides a general overview of the research. It outlines the research aims and objectives, as well as the methodology that the research intends to use. Furthermore, it identifies the unique nature of this research and its contribution to knowledge. It provides an overview of the concept of servant leadership and the structure of the research in general.

1.9.2 CHAPTER 2:

The second chapter provides a literature review of the relevant leadership literature. It begins by exploring what exactly leadership consists of, exploring a variety of different leadership definitions. It then provides a chronological overview of leadership, in accordance with the most prominent eras of leadership in the field.

It then proceeds to present a systematic literature review which was conducted by this research. This begins with an explanation of the research protocol and procedures that the review adhered to. It also determines how an SLR is relevant within a qualitative body of research. The chapter then proceeds to report and disseminate the findings of the review, in both a descriptive and thematic manner. It then concludes by discussing how its findings relate to the research questions.

1.9.3 CHAPTER 3:

Chapter Three provides the methodology which is used in the research process. This will discuss the approaches, paradigms and philosophy adopted by the research. It

will then explore the research methods which were used in gathering the data. Additionally, it will outline the participants selected for the research, and how the sampling process was determined. There will also be a discussion of the interview process and the theory underpinning it. Finally, it will explain how this research was able to adhere to the relevant ethical guidelines.

1.9.4 CHAPTER 4:

The fourth chapter will discuss the findings of the research, presenting them in accordance with the relevant theme. This will outline the results of the research as determined by the data which was gathered. This chapter will aim to address a select number of the research aims and objectives, the remaining to follow in chapter seven.

1.9.5 CHAPTER 5:

Chapter five proceeds to explore the findings which were presented in chapter four with reference to the relevant literature. This includes answering all the research questions and objectives. It also presents the empirical skills framework, accompanied by an extensive explanatory discussion.

1.9.6 CHAPTER 6:

The research concludes in chapter six. The conclusion provides an overview of what the research has discussed. It then explores the potential limitations of the current research and scope for future areas for research. It reaches an overall balanced and logical conclusion to the research in general. The references and appendices then follow.

1.10 CONCLUSION:

This chapter has provided an overview of the research to follow. It has discussed the research aims and objectives, as well as the questions it aims to address. It has also highlighted the originality of this research and how it aims to contribute to knowledge. Furthermore, it provides an insight into the structure in terms of its chapter layout.

The research will now proceed to chapter two, which will conduct a literature review within the field of both leadership and servant leadership, specifically.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter provides an overview of leadership, as outlined within the introduction before conducting a systematic literature review which is focused upon servant leadership.

Leadership has been identified as a prominent area of academic focus and research, over the course of the last century. Yet, it is important to note that its existence can be traced back throughout the course of history, found within even the most ancient of societies (Bass et al., 2003). Leadership can be found within academia, business, politics, anthropology and theology, to name but a few disciplines. In addition to its academic presence, leadership is found within all forms of organised societal groups.

The actions and decisions of the leaders we find within our lives affect us in a plethora of ways, be it minimal or substantial. The inescapable nature of leadership can be said to have attributed to it becoming one of the most commonly researched, discussed and debated topics within the organisational sciences (Yammarino, 2013). As a result of its importance and increasing popularity, it can be described as both an intuitively appealing and necessary area of study. In essence, it would be fair to describe leadership research as essential, due to the way in which it permeates our society. Overall, it can be said that leadership has previously been, and will continue to be, one of the most important areas of research within the social sciences.

Research has shown that leadership remains one of the least understood phenomena on earth (Harrison, 2018). The concept of leadership has been dated back to the days of the ancient Egyptians, and examples of it can be found throughout history (Bass, 2008). Leadership has long been an area of interest to historians, philosophers and social scientists (Daft, 2015). Systematic scholarly research concerning leadership begun emerging over the past 100 years, and this period has seen the emergence of hundreds of different definitions of leadership (Yammarino, 2013). It has been stated that there are “almost as many different definitions of leadership as there are people who have attempted to define the concept” (Stogdill, 1974, p.5). Leaders are those

who are able to inspire and direct others towards achieving a common goal (Kotter, 1990). They should have the ability to create direction and vision, in order to generate common goals (Amanchukwu et al. 2015; Kotter, 1990).

This chapter will thus summarize leadership as follows:

“Leaders are individuals who establish direction for a working group of individuals who gain commitment from this group of members to this direction and who then motivate these members to achieve the direction’s outcomes.”

(Conger, 1992, p. 18)

This chapter will therefore provide an overview of what leadership actually is, and the definitions of leadership according to those which are most prominent within the field. This chapter will then proceed to highlight the evolutions in leadership theory which will allow for a greater understanding of the concept of servant leadership and how its development has been impacted.

2.2 WHAT IS LEADERSHIP?

Firstly, it is important to differentiate management from leadership. Management deals with complexity and brings consistency (Kotter, 1990). Leadership, on the other hand, is concerned with managing changes in a volatile world (Kotter, 1990). An effective leader motivates, inspires and directs activities in order to achieve common or organisational goals (Amanchukwu et al., 2015). Kotter (1990) explains that leadership is largely concerned with direction setting. The leader should then motivate and inspire the followers in that direction (Kotter, 1990). De Pree (1990) confirms this, stating that the leaders most important responsibility is to define reality.

Leadership is an important area of research, as it affects nearly every aspect of what we do (Yammarino, 2013). Yet it remains the case that no one approach to leadership can be considered to be universally effective (Amanchukwu et al., 2015). Many scholars believe that different approaches to leadership can be effective within

different situations. However, positive leadership has been described as the process by which an individual can influence a group of people in order to achieve a common goal (Northouse and Rowe, 2007).

2.3 LEADERSHIP DEFINITION

Leadership remains an area plagued by conflicting definitions. It has been estimated that by the end of the century there were at least 650 definitions of leadership (Bennis and Townsend, 1995). It is widely accepted that since then this number has only continued to grow (Silva, 2016). The table below illustrates a selection of the more prominent definitions of leadership, which have been put forward by scholars throughout the last century:

TABLE 2.1: LEADERSHIP DEFINITIONS

Author	Definition
Bass and Bass (2008)	Leadership is a universal phenomenon in both humans and in species of animals. For example, leadership can be found in patriarchal gorillas and matriarchal elephants.
Bennis and Nanus (1985) p. 19	“Leadership is like the abominable snowman; whose footprints are everywhere but who is nowhere to be seen.”
Bryman (1987) p.6	“Leadership is the creation of a vision about a desired future state which seeks to enmesh all members of an organisation within its net.”
Cohen (1990) p. 9	“Leadership is the art of influencing others to their maximum performance to accomplish any task, objective or project.”

Donnelly et al. (1985) p. 2	“Leadership is the process of influencing the activities of followers through the communication process and towards the attainment of some goal.”
Harrison (2018)	Leadership deals with variables such as influence, motivation and change and not just meeting organisational objectives.
Hemphill and Coons (1957)	Leadership is concerned with the behaviour individuals exhibit when they are directing an organised group towards a goal.
Hosking (1988)	Leadership is concerned with those who are both seen to and are expected to contribute to social order.
Jacques and Clement (1994)	Leadership is the act of an individual setting a goal and inspiring others to work with them and each other to achieve the goal.
Rauch and Behling (1984)	Leadership is concerned with exerting influence over a group in order for the achievement of goals.
Stogdill (1974)	Leadership is concerned with both initiating and maintaining structure in interaction and expectation.
Yukl (2006) p.8	Leadership is the process of influencing others to understand what needs to be done and how to do it.

This is merely a sample of some of the many leadership definitions which exist. Whilst the definitions differ, Ciulla (2002) argues that they are united in the respect that they are overall concerned with getting a group of people to do something. Ciulla

(2002) affirms that the only way in which the theories differ is with regards to how leaders get their followers to achieve the organisation's or the individuals' goals. Defining leadership remains an elusive problem due to the complexity of the concept itself (Daft, 1990). There are those who contest the idea that leadership even needs a definition. Bass (2008) has argued that the search for a single definition of leadership is impossible as it is entirely subjective to the researcher and the situation which they are observing. It has even been posited that a universal definition should not be possible as this would hinder creative thinking within the field (Alvesson and Sveningsson, 2006). Some have gone further and suggested that the concept of leadership is a myth and that it involves nothing more than hoping someone will solve our problems through sheer force of will (Martin, 2011). However, it can be said that leadership is an important area of study as literally nothing exists without it (Yammarino, 2013). Leadership is essential to the moral, political, economic and social fabrics of society (Sarros and Cooper, 2006). Leadership is 'intuitively appealing,' which is why it is a concept which has been studied at such length (Harrison, 2018 p.10).

Throughout history, myths, biographies, hero studies and case studies have all explored and discussed the concept of leadership (Yammarino, 2013). However, it is important to note that whilst it may appear that by definition bad people cannot be good leaders, it should be noted that this is not the case with scores of CEOs finding themselves in financial and legal difficulties (Kellerman, 2004). Leadership has evolved as a concept, shifting from being viewed as an ability or behaviour to an influential process (Harrison, 2018). Extensive leadership studies have resulted in the emergence of theories concerning traits, skills, characteristics and behaviours. It can be said therefore, that leadership has been examined from every possible angle (Chin, 2015). In order to fully understand the topic of this research, it is important to explore the prominent theories prior to the development of servant leadership. By providing an overview of the prominent leadership theories prior to servant leadership, a clearer picture of the approach emerges, highlighting its development and the approaches by which it was influenced.

2.4 APPROACHES TO LEADERSHIP

According to Harrison (2018), the main approaches to leadership throughout the 21st century are as follows; Great man theory, trait theory, skills, behavioural, leader member exchange theory (LMX), servant leadership, transactional, transformational, distributed, authentic and entrepreneurial leadership. This research has chosen to categorise these approaches using an adaptation of Kings (1990) and Clark and Harrison's (2018) leadership categorisation. King (1990) originally developed this leadership categorisation to provide an overview of leadership evolution. Clark and Harrison (2018) drew inspiration from King's classification in their 2018 evaluation of leadership evolution. King's (1990) work has been deemed highly influential within leadership research, particularly within leadership evolution (Boateng, 2012).

Clark and Harrison's (2018) use of the categorisation almost 20 years later solidifies its value as a tool of leadership categorisation, which is still relevant today. This chapter will build upon the work of previous scholars to develop a categorisation of leadership theories, in accordance with those deemed most influential by Clark and Harrison (2018). The categorisation which has been adapted within this research is as follows; personality era, influence era, behavioural era, transactional era, cultural era, skills era, and serving era. This is shown in table 2.2.

TABLE 2.2: LEADERSHIP ERAS

Personality Era	Influence Era	Behaviour Era	Transactional Era	Cultural Era	Skills Era	Serving Era
Great Man Trait	Transformational Entrepreneurial	Behavioural	Transactional LMX	Distributed Authentic Ethical	Skills	Servant Leadership

2.5 PERSONALITY ERA

According to Clark and Harrison (2018), the emergence of the personality era was the beginning of empirical leadership research. The personality era is generally considered to consist of both the Great Man theory and trait theory (Clark and Harrison, 2018; King, 1990). These will now be explored in greater detail.

2.5.1 THE GREAT MAN THEORY

Towards the late 19th century, and early 20th century, leadership focused upon Carlyle's (1841) 'Great Man Theory,' which remained prominent for a long period of time as it remained largely uncontested (Spector, 2016). Prior to the mid twentieth century there was a consensus that leaders were different from their followers, and it was the consensus that leaders were born not made (Cowthan, 1996). This was echoed within the research surrounding the "great man theory" which largely focused upon the innate traits of an individual (Freud, 1939; Carlyle, 1840).

The great man theory fundamentally believed that only great individuals possess the traits necessary for leadership (Harrison, 2018). Bass and Stogdill (1990) explain that for many, the course of history has been shaped by the leadership of great men. The great man theory suggests that a great leader shall arrive when the situation demands it (Marquis and Huston, 2009). Carlyle (1840) explains that leadership is not learned or inherited, but it is in fact a God-given gift. Carlyle believed that those who he described as heroes, such as Shakespeare, Rosseau, Napoleon etc. shaped history through their own personal God given attributes and divine inspiration (Bafou, 2012). This is echoed by Galton (1969) who stated that human ability was inherited and displayed within leadership. Additionally, Freud (1939) argues that leaders who are 'great men' are able to exert power over others as people tend to look for father-like figures to lead them, protect them and make decisions on their behalf.

One of Carlyle's main critics was Herbert Spencer who highlighted that it is the influence of society, rather than divinity which makes men great (Carneiro, 1981). Spencer goes as far as to state that Carlyle's notion that people are born great is 'unscientific' and 'childish' (Herbert, 1869). Furthermore, great man has been described as less of a theory, and more of a statement of faith which does not fit into scholarly theory (Spector, 2016). It can also be said that the great man theory is no longer relevant in today's society due to the fact that it has only taken into consideration men and not women (O'Connor, 2010). Spector (2016) highlights that the great man theory is indeed concerned only with great men. It fails to take into account historical female leaders and is therefore too exclusive a theory to be relevant within the 21st century. It is also important to note that the men mentioned within the Carlyle's Great Man Theory are all white and Anglican, rendering the great man theory exclusivity again inapplicable within today's society (Coppola, 2011). On the other hand, it should be noted that since Carlyle's research. Indira Ghandi and Martin Luther King have been studied with reference to the great man theory (Harrison, 2018).

Kellerman (1986) argues that the great man theory collapses completely when one asks where the great man comes from, as only two options are presented: natural or supernatural. Tucker (1989) states that the great man theory is not relevant, as leaders such as Stalin and Hitler, became powerful because of many external factors and influences, rather than on their own volition. It has also been argued that the great man theory is invalid as it practises elitism, due to its suggestion that only a chosen few have the ability to lead (Outcait et al., 2001). Additionally, Kotter (1990) has stated that great leaders do not simply emerge, as the theory suggests, but organisations actively seek and aim to employ them.

It has been stated that despite its lack of scientific validity, the great man theory remains relevant as people still want to search for a hero within business (Harrison, 2018). However, it can also be argued that the great man theory is irrelevant within 21st century society and is now an outdated concept. The theory has little empirical evidence, and it is difficult to apply within today's diverse society, whereby people from all walks of life have shown to be effective leaders. Furthermore, since the inception of the great man theory, studies have shown that women can be just as

effective as men within leadership roles (Kolb, 1999; Jenkins, 1991). This is echoed by Harrison (2018) who gives examples of Queen Elizabeth and Joan of Arc as great female leaders.

This chapter will now proceed to examine the trait approach within the next section which came into fruition as a result of a growing dissatisfaction with the great man theory. The trait approach to leadership has been described as an echo of the great man, focusing upon the attributes which differentiate effective from ineffective leaders (Northouse, 2013).

2.5.2 TRAIT THEORY

After the great man theory, a shift in perspective occurred which saw a need for leadership theory to expand to include people of different ethnicities and religions in comparison to those included within the great man theory (Bass and Bass, 2008). There was also a growing change in ideology with a growing consensus emerging that leadership should be examined from the lens of current organisational leaders rather than historical figures (Judge et al., 2002). Thus, the trait theory was developed, and remained prominent throughout the 20th century, with some going as far as to state that it is the only leadership theory which needs to be researched (Cowley, 1931). Trait theory examines the traits of a leader, rather than assuming their position was justified as the result of divinity (Bass, 1990). The basis of the trait theory suggests that an individual's personality traits and characteristics can influence their effectiveness as a leader (Colbert et al., 2012; Zaccaro et al., 2004). It was a more inclusive approach asserting that leadership traits exist, regardless of one's social status (Gordon and Curlee, 2011).

Many other studies have emerged throughout the past century concerning the trait approach to leadership (Colbert et al., 2012). Such traits as neuroticism, dominance and masculinity have been determined as the necessary traits for leaders (Novikova, 2013). However, such traits can be argued to be somewhat controversial as they are largely focused upon the male leader. This posits the same dilemma of exclusivity as presented within the great man theory; the exclusion of females. It is arguable that to

exclude females makes the assumptions that they lack the necessary traits for leadership, a mindset which is no longer deemed appropriate. In recent years, it is important to note that an increasing number of traits and values which were once typically considered feminine have been introduced within trait theory, thus increasing its status as a moral approach to leadership (Claes, 1999). Additionally, similar to the great man theory, trait theory asserts that leaders' traits are different to those of non-leaders. Overall, it can be said that trait theory faces the same dilemma of exclusivity as the great man theory.

2.6 INFLUENCE ERA

The influence era aims to explore the nature of leadership in accordance with power dynamics (Clarke and Harrison, 2018; King, 1990). Rather than focus on the individual, like the personality era, the influence era recognises that leadership is more than the study of a solitary individual. The influence era examines the relationship between the individual leader and their subordinates. According to Harrison (2018), the most influential leadership theories are transformational leadership and entrepreneurial leadership.

2.6.1 TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP

Transformational leadership was initially proposed by Burns (1978) and then expanded upon by Bass and Avolio (1990). Within this approach, the leader identifies the changes necessary within an organisation and recruits' followers to assist them in executing these changes (Burns, 2004). It is essentially concerned with creating an organisational vision and persuading those within an organisation to share in and implement that vision. There are five main personality traits which are often taken into consideration when implementing transformational leadership. They are as follows; extraversion, neuroticism, openness to experience, agreeableness and conscientiousness (Bass and Bass, 2008). In addition to this, transformational leadership proposes four main behaviours: idealised influence, inspirational motivation, individualised consideration and intellectual stimulation (Bass and Avolio, 1990).

The morality of transformational leadership has often been called into question, due to the methods which a leader may use to convince others to share in their organisational vision (Sendjaya, 2005). One must question the extent to which a leader will go to recruit others, and whether or not they are willing to use amoral methods to do so. It also raises an issue regarding how important the followers within an organisation are. It is worth considering that if the leader's sole focus is on implementing organisational change, then they may be willing to achieve this at the cost of their employees. It has also resulted in leaders elevated perceptions of personal power, which, in turn can lead to misuse and abuse of power (Barth-Farkas et al., 2014). It is important to note that from transformational leadership a facet of leadership has emerged known as pseudo-transformational leadership. This facet does not recognise ethics within transformational leadership and accepts that the approach is altruistic and concerned with self-serving purposes (Howell and Avolio, 1992). The potential for amorality within transformational leadership even resulted in the development of a new form of leadership; authentic leadership, which will be discussed at a later point in this chapter.

2.6.2 ENTREPRENEURIAL LEADERSHIP

Entrepreneurial leadership can be explained as the approach to leadership which emerged as a result of a combination of entrepreneurship and leadership. Entrepreneurial leaders combine the skills of entrepreneurs with their positions of leadership. They tend to focus upon creating value for society, stakeholders and businesses and pursue opportunities out-with the resources currently available to them or their organisation (Harrison et al., 2016). Entrepreneurial leaders are also concerned with implementing change and innovation for the benefit of an organisation (Van Zyl and Mathur-Helm, 2007) Overall, they are tasked with creating a vision which is shared with and implemented by their followers (Harrison et al., 2018).

Entrepreneurial leaders generally have a higher risk tolerance in comparison to most types of leaders. They are constantly concerned with risk when identifying or undertaking new opportunities. The result of the risks that they take can often be detrimental to their organisation or employees. For example, a risk could fail and cost the organisation resources or employees their employment. Additionally, it is important

to point out that entrepreneurial leaders are often accused of setting aside morality and ethics in order to focus on goals and achievements within their organisations (Surie and Ashley, 2008). Furthermore, entrepreneurial leaders generally ask their followers to abandon their safer and more secure jobs to join them in a venture into the unknown (Harrison et al., 2016).

It is important here to acknowledge the concept of social entrepreneurship. Social entrepreneurship is the use of start-up companies to proffer solutions to cultural, social and economic issues. It can be applied in accordance with an organisation's aims and beliefs. It is important to note that at present the ethical and moral benefits of social entrepreneurship remain largely unexplored and unvalidated within the field (Zahra et al., 2009). Overall, the entrepreneurial leader is arguably too focused on their own gain, often to the detriment of others.

2.7 BEHAVIOURAL ERA

Due to a lack of cohesive evidence regarding the trait theory, research began to look at what leaders do, rather than what they have (Harrison, 2018). The emergence of the behavioural theory marked an important shift within leadership studies from characteristics and traits, to the way in which individuals act (Harrison, 2018). Behavioural theory is focused upon the way leaders treat their followers within different contexts (Wright, 1996). Leadership behavioural theory seeks to identify the behaviours which positively influence both individual and organisational success (Yukl et al., 2002). Northouse (2018) explains that the behavioural approach to leadership provides a framework which allows for a broad analysis of leadership and the behaviours a leader may exhibit. Indeed, there are a variety of different behavioural taxonomies, some which focus on specific leadership theories, some which are broad, some are narrow, and some are overarching (Yukl, 2012). Due to the scope of the research which surrounds the behavioural approach, this chapter will now proceed to provide a general overview of behavioural theory, focusing on the four seminal works, which are credited with shaping this approach.

In the 1930s, one of the studies first credited with examining behavioural leadership theory was conducted at Iowa state by Kurt Lewin and colleagues (Harrison, 2018). The study has been described as a benchmark of its time and one of the most cited leadership works in history (Ledlow and Coppola, 2011). Lewin's study consisted of two groups of eleven-year-old children, and within the groups, researchers acted as a democratic leader in one group, and an authoritarian leader within the other (Billing, 2015). The study was later expanded to include laissez-faire leadership, and leaders swapped, so each group experienced each leadership style. The behaviour of each group was then studied under each circumstance (Lewin et al., 1939). The research found that when in autocratic circumstances, participants displayed aggressive behaviours, whereas positive behaviours were displayed with regards to the democratic and laissez-faire leaders (Lewin et al., 1939). This research highlights how the behaviour of leaders can influence the behaviour of followers.

However, despite the previously mentioned influence of this research, it has not been without its criticisms. It has been stated that the researchers used 'preference structured' questions to the groups, suggesting to them it would be far easier for them to agree with the leaders than disagree (Pomerantz, 1984). Additionally, the research has been criticised as it takes place in an 'experimental situation,' meaning that the results cannot translate into everyday situations (Billig, 2015). Furthermore, ethical concerns have been raised regarding the age of the participants and the validity of monitoring the behaviour of children in circumstances which they don't understand.

Following Lewin's study, the University of Ohio conducted research investigating leadership behaviours. The researchers aimed to 'describe individuals' behaviours' when in a position of leadership (Bass, 1990). The research consisted of 150 statements, which were designed to measure nine different dimensions of behaviour. The statements were then used to develop the Leaders Behaviour Description Questionnaire (LBDQ) (Stogdill, 1963). The research identified two categories of leadership behaviours: structure and consideration (Stogdill, 1974). Initiating structure is concerned with accomplishing a task and shaping behaviour to achieve it (Yukl, 2010). Consideration is more focused on a leader's orientation towards their employees and the concern they show them (Greenwood and McNamara, 1969).

The Ohio state researchers did however believe that a leader could be competent in both these categories (Harrison, 2018). However, this research has failed to stand up to serious psychometric examination (Schriesheim and Stogdill, 1975).

Furthermore, it has been improved in the form of adaptations and new interpretations of the LBDQ, as the original has proved nonviable across a multitude of situations (Littrel, 2015; Schriesheim, 1970).

The University of Michigan also conducted research into behavioural leadership (Harrison, 2018). The University of Michigan, however, believed that the two categories of leadership behaviours could not run parallel to each other, because if a leader was orientated towards production, then they would not care about their employees and vice versa (Harrison, 2018). The University of Michigan's research stated that the measure of leadership behaviour was a one-dimensional approach, rather than the two-dimensional approach put forward by the University of Ohio (Lussier and Achua, 2001). This is in contrast with the aforementioned University of Ohio studies which believed that the two could overlap. The Michigan studies also expanded to include three characteristics of effective leadership; task orientated behaviour, relationship orientated behaviour and participative leadership (Boje, 2000).

The Ohio and Michigan studies have been credited for paving the way for one of the most influential leadership models; Blake and Moutons Managerial Grid (Leadership Grid) (Harrison 2018). Please see Figure 2.1:

Figure 2.1: Blake and Moutons Managerial Grid

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Blake, R., & Mouton, J. (1964). The Managerial Grid: The Key to Leadership Excellence. Houston, TX: Gulf Publishing Company

(Blake and Mouton, 1964)

The managerial grid allows for a 1-9 scale which measures to what degree a leader's focus is on, either in regard to people or production (Kane, 2014). According to Blake and Mouton (1964), there are five main types of leadership which can be found within the grid. They are as follows:

- The Country Club Manager (1,9)

This leader is people orientated but cares little about production. Whilst this leader is good for moral and the working environment, productivity may suffer under them.

- The Impoverished Manager (1,1)

This leader is not focused upon either employees or production. This type of leadership will result in minimal results for both employee and organisational productivity.

- Middle of the Road Management (5,5)

This leader cares somewhat about people and results. There are average results in both categories under this approach, but they will not be optimal.

- Team Management (9,9)

This leader has a high concern for both people and production. Under this approach, optimum results will be achieved for both employees and the organisation

- Authority Management (9,1)

This leader has a high concern for production and a low concern for employees. Results in production may also suffer because of this style, due to its impact on the employees.

Whilst, as previously mentioned, the grid has been widely used within the literature, it does have its limitations. It has been criticised for its lack of empirical validation (Yukl, 1999). Furthermore, the grid fails to take into account situational contexts and the external influences which may impact upon a leader's priorities at any one given time.

The behavioural approach to leadership is undoubtedly important as it allows for the study of the actions taken by leaders in order to make them effective. Furthermore, the behavioural approach can also be considered important to leaders themselves. It allows them to learn about themselves and evaluate how they would improve or change themselves (Northouse, 2018). However, contemporary leadership behavioural research has been criticised for having a weak theoretical foundation (Van Knippenberg and Sitkin, 2013). Additionally, it has also been highlighted that the number of different behavioural studies conducted have made it difficult for the comparison and integration of the findings (Bass, 2008). Therefore, whilst the behavioural field is one of the largest areas of studies within leadership it is not without its shortcomings. It also fails to take into account how the behaviour demonstrated by the leader may differ, according to the follower. This will now be

explored within the next section, which aims to look at the Leader Member Exchange Theory.

2.8 TRANSACTIONAL ERA

The transactional era is a further expansion upon the influence era. Unlike the influence era, the transactional era recognises the reciprocal nature of the leader-follower relationship (Clark and Harrison, 2018). According to Harrison (2018), the most influential transactional approaches to leadership are Leader member exchange and transactional leadership, which will now be discussed.

2.8.1 LEADER MEMBER EXCHANGE

The introduction of Leader-member exchange theory (LMX) saw a move away from the earlier leadership theories which tended to focus largely upon behaviours and traits (Harrison, 2018). LMX theory is concerned with the examining the dyadic relationship between the leader and their followers (Uhl-Bien, 1995). Leader member exchange suggests that a follower's responsibility, performance and decisions are influenced by the strength of their relationship with their leader (Deluga, 1998). It has been described by some as a process approach to leadership, due to the stress it places on the interaction between the leader and the follower (Van Breukelen et al., 2000). It can also be considered a transactional approach, as both the leader and the followers are participants active in the process (Hollander, 1990). LMX originally emerged under the name Vertical Dyad Theory of leadership (Dansereau et al., 1975). It was developed to counter the theory that leaders have only one consistent style of leadership towards all followers, or members of their team (Graen and Cashman, 1975).

Prior to LMX, it was the common view that different perceptions of a leader were a result of inconsistencies in the follower's opinions and views rather than the fault of the leader (Van Breukelen et al. 2006). LMX theory is therefore largely credited with putting forward the idea that leaders may treat subordinates differently, which could

impact upon their effectiveness within the organisation (Gran et al., 1973). It has been suggested that LMX promotes employment experiences which in turn facilitates effective organisational performance (Liden et al., 1997).

It has been argued that LMX is difficult to measure as it is influenced by a number of different factors such as demographics, characteristics of group size, contributions etc. (Kozlowsky and Doherty, 1989; Tsui et al., 1995). It has also been highlighted that LMX varies according to the interaction a leader has with their followers, which in turn can affect their relationship with them (Dulebohn et al., 2012). The issue has been raised concerning how LMX should be measured, whether on the dyadic level, group level or at an organisational level (Van Breukelen et al., 2006). Furthermore, there has been a debate as to whether the dyadic units should be measured as independent variables or interdependent units (Klein et al., 1994). It has been stated that there remains to be determined a valid scale which can be used to measure the relationship between a leader and a follower (Harrison, 2018).

LMX divides followers into two categories; in groups and out groups, depending on how the leader perceives the behaviours of each follower. Within the in-group followers' complete extra tasks and help out the leaders, and the leaders do the same for them (Northouse, 2015). They tend to have a respectful and trusting relationship with the leader, which is mutually beneficial. On the other hand, those in the outgroup generally do only what is required of them at work, not offering extra input unless it is in some way beneficial to them (Northouse, 2015). Those in outgroups tend to have poor relationships with leaders (Craighead and Nemeroff, 2001). They are only bound to their leader via employment contracts and demonstrate low respect for their employer, and generally do not demonstrate much trust towards their leader (Graen and Uhl Bien, 1995).

This approach has been criticised, as organising followers into different groups according to behaviours could be considered favouritism and could result in detrimental effects on the organisation's efficiency (Scandura, 1999; Sias and Jablin, 1995). It could also pave the way for discriminatory practices within business, where some followers may be treated better than others, according to their group status. It has also been found that members of the in group will be more trusting of their

leader and favour them over their colleagues within the outgroup (Podaskoff, 1990). This is clearly problematic and could prove divisive within the workplace. It could also be stated that LMX theory is essentially the same as transactional leadership as follower relationships are formed with the leader, based on a reward and punishment basis. Essentially, employees are aware that the better their relationship with the leader, the more 'perks' they are likely to receive.

LMX has also been clearly shown to influence work climates (Dunegan et al., 1992; Kozolowski and Doherty, 1989). Positive dyadic relationships have been found to positively influence work climates (Baron and Kenny, 1986). It has also been stated that low quality relationships within LMX have been found to increase perceptions of abusive supervision (Lian et al., 2012; Martinko et al., 2011; Klausner, 2014). However, it has also been counter-argued that positive and high-quality relationships within LMX can mediate abusive supervision and influence positive organisational outcomes (Tepper, 2000; Xu et al., 2011). Therefore, there are some discrepancies in the field as to LMX's influence on abusive supervision. However, it could be argued that LMX in itself could result in abusive supervision, as those in the ingroup are more likely to be treated better than those in the outgroup.

It has been stated that the relationship between leaders and employees does indeed matter (Ansari et al., 2007). Liden and Grant (1986) found that only one in 10 leaders formed the same type of relationship with all their direct superiors. It is therefore clear that LMX does exist within organisations, and it is important to monitor it due to its influence on organisational performance outcomes. However, it is important to note that LMX has been criticised as discriminatory and lacking an empirical framework or measuring instrument (Harrison, 2018). Therefore, whilst it is important to recognise that relationships can be different between leaders and different followers, it should also be noted the negative effects this can have on both employee well-being and organisational performance.

2.8.2 TRANSACTIONAL LEADERSHIP

Transactional leadership theory was first developed by Burns in 1978 and is based upon the use of contingent rewards to motivate followers. The transactional leader generally adopts some form of 'reward' to incentivise or motivate subordinates (Harrison, 2018). Coercive steps can also be taken to ensure that followers do not make 'mistakes' and instead behave in a manner which is beneficial to the leader (Yukl, 2013).

Transactional leadership has been described as a poor attempt at leadership in terms of moral reasoning (Felix et al., 2015). This is due to the potential scope for bribery when adopting such an approach. It further promotes a fear-based work environment with employees only maintaining their leader's status quo through fear of punishment, rather than of their own volition. Additionally, it leaves room for corruption from leaders, who can use rewards to get employees to do as they wish. Today's society is one which is morally averse to corruption and bribery.

2.9 CULTURAL ERA

The cultural era considers the nature of organisational culture and its relationship with leadership (Clark and Harrison, 2018). Both organisational culture and leadership research are vast areas of study with a plethora of research streams, theories and ideas surrounding both concepts (Yukl, 2013). In accordance with the leadership theories highlighted by Harrison (2018) both distributed and authentic leadership are categorised under the cultural era of leadership.

2.9.1 DISTRIBUTED LEADERSHIP

Distributed leadership is concerned with the interaction between people and the situations in which they find themselves. Rather than focusing on a single individual, distributed leadership focuses on the collective effort of a group. Distributed leadership proposes that it is not possible for a leader to possess all the skills and traits necessary

for leadership across all situations, rather how leaders interact with their followers should be taken into consideration (Harris, 2010). It is also concerned with roles and responsibilities being distributed across a team.

Distributed leadership has been criticised as it allows the potential for a hegemonic nature emerging within a team-based ideology (Sinclair, 1992). This could lead to the silencing or ignoring of colleagues whose contributions may go unheard above their more vocal, or prominent counterparts (Sugure, 2009). Additionally, it has the potential for gendered interpretations of work within the team, which may leave some team-members work and ideas rendered invisible (Rippin, 2007). Overall, whilst on the surface, distributed leadership may seem to promote a democratic approach to leadership, it leaves the potential for a dismissal of less visible members of a team.

2.9.2 AUTHENTIC LEADERSHIP

Authentic leadership can be considered a relatively new concept, which is still largely in the throes of developing a generally accepted comprehensive definition (Northouse, 2015). As mentioned earlier, authentic leadership was developed in an attempt to address the shortcomings of transformational leadership. It should be noted that authentic leadership theoretically insists upon integrity and morality, whereas transformational leaders does not. Authentic leaders are self-aware and act in a way which acknowledges their abilities. They also have an internalised moral perspective, balanced processing, and relational transparency (Walumbwa et al., 2008)

It is important to note that this could be deemed superficial as there is no moral dimension or framework included within authentic leadership. This calls into question to what extent it is of greater moral standing than transformational leadership (Gardiner, 2017).

2.9.3. ETHICAL LEADERSHIP

Although not discussed within Harrison's (2018) approaches to leadership, it is important to consider ethical leadership. Ethical leadership entails a leader factoring in the potential implications of any decision or action they may need to take, with regards to the employees of their organisation (Mihelic et al., 2010). Whilst it is often criticised for being a vague concept, it is generally considered to be the act of enabling people to do the right thing. Ethical leaders' question what is right or wrong and as a result are able to develop a code of conduct for their followers.

Leadership is judged on outcomes, whereas ethics is judged on intentions. Therefore, though the leader may have ethical intentions, the outcomes produced may be amoral (Trevino and Brown, 2000). Leaders often lack guidance on how to be ethical. In fact, research has found that a large majority of adults are not fully informed with regards to ethics and lack the ability to act morally autonomously, the same can be said for leaders (Rest, 1986).

It can also be argued that a leader cannot be entirely ethical due to their loyalties to numerous stakeholders, which present them with conflicting ethical ideologies. Furthermore, it is difficult to determine what makes an ethical leader, as what is considered ethical in one culture, may not be seen to be so in another. The difference in these ethical values can lead to ethical conflicts within the leader, and indeed within the employees. Also, whilst leaders may strive to be ethical, they can be influenced and corrupted by the unethical behaviours of those around them. Furthermore, ethical leadership uses a reward and punishment system, leaving it open to the same potential amoral elements as transformational leadership (Yasir and Mohamad, 2016). Whilst on the surface, ethical leadership may appear moral, it can be argued that just because a leader is perceived as ethical does not necessarily mean that they are (Ciulla, 2003). Additionally, due to the ambiguity of the concept it is difficult, in fact, to even define what constitutes ethical leadership.

Katz (1955) was one of the leading proponents of the notion that leadership can be learned and therefore there should be a shift in focus, from a leader's traits to a leader's skills (Northouse, 2010). A focus on skills is important, as skills suggest what a leader can achieve, rather than the characteristics with which they were born (Katz, 1955). Leatherman (2008) similarly stated that the benefit of examining leadership skills lies in the fact that it can be learned and therefore taught to potential leaders. Skills have been described as a function of experience (Mumford et al., 2000). Skills within leadership are concerned with the knowledge and abilities which are necessary for effective leadership (Northouse, 2010). It has been explained that by continually developing their skills, leaders are able to increase their own competency (Caldwell, 2004). Harrison (2018) goes as far as to state that anyone who aspires to be a leader should be familiar with the skills necessary for leadership and how they can be developed. It is therefore clear that skills are considered an important aspect of leadership research. This section will now proceed to explore the concept of skills within leadership.

Several different leadership skill theories have emerged within academia, however the research presented by Katz (1955) into the essential skills for effective leadership is considered one of the most influential works on the subject. Katz (1955) stated that the skills necessary for effective administration (leadership) were technical, human and conceptual. Technical skills have been described as being concerned with ones' knowledge and understanding of a certain activity (Katz, 1974). A leader who has human skills, is one who has the knowledge and ability required to work alongside and with people (Harrison, 2018). Conceptual skills have been described as; good judgement, foresight, intuition, creativity and familiarity with the uncertain (Yukl, 2010). Katz's (1955) work can still be considered acceptable today with scholars such as Harrison (2018) agreeing that the main skills required for leadership are indeed technical, human and conceptual skills. Katz's (1955) skills framework sets the foundation for much of the later work which emerged, regarding leadership skills, and is still recognised as the core leadership skills of leaders at all levels (Northouse, 2015).

Another influential body of research on leadership skills was carried out by Mumford et al. (2000) who focused on leadership skills within the military. They found that three sets of skills were necessary for effective leadership: problem-solving skills, social judgement skills and knowledge. See figure 2.2. below for an overview of the three components which make up the skills model:

FIGURE 2.2 THREE COMPONENTS OF THE SKILLS MODEL

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Mumford, M. D., Zaccaro, S. J., Harding, F. D., Jacobs, T. O. and Fleishman, E. A. (2000). Leadership skills for a changing world solving complex social problems. *The Leadership Quarterly*

(Source : Mumford et al. 2000)

Mumford et al. (2000) believed that an individual's traits could influence the skills they possess, which could, in turn, promote effective leadership outcomes. However, it has been argued that the skills put forward by Mumford et al. (2000) are still trait like, and therefore their research is still trait-driven (Harrison, 2018).

Leadership skills have also been described as a strata plex, in accordance with their organisational level. This essentially means that leadership skills have a complex number of layers according to the leadership requirements and their relationship with the level within their organisation (Mumford et al., 2007). Within this research,

Mumford et al. (2007) also highlights that the following skills are necessary for leadership; cognitive skills, interpersonal skills, business skills and strategic skills. Additionally, whilst not mentioned by Mumford et al. (2007), business skills have been identified as particularly important within the literature surrounding entrepreneurial leadership (Harrison, 2018; Day and Haiping, 2001).

Whilst the main skillsets within leadership have been described as human, technical and conceptual, other skills have emerged within the leadership literature such as; analytical skills (Mumford et al., 2007), affective skills (Parker and Begnaud, 2004), entrepreneurial skills (Harrison, 2018), power sharing skills (Caldwell, 2004), problem solving skills (Puccio et al., 2014), political skills (Ferris et al., 2004; Hargrove and Owens, 2003), emotional intelligence (Goleman, 2014) and interpersonal skills (Uhl-Bien et al., 1986).

Additional leadership skill frameworks have been developed for the leadership required within certain fields. For example, education (Hall et al., 2016), social care (Walumbwa et al., 2005), and healthcare (Mathena, 2002) etc. In addition, training programmes have been developed in order to develop leadership skills such as: ASPIRE, The EMSP programme and numerous MBA and DBA programmes. It has been explained that such leadership programmes can promote the development of leadership skills and result in more effective leadership (Bass, 1990). However, it has also been counter-argued that skill development programs are a waste of resources as they focus on the wrong part of the brain (Goleman, 2000). Goleman (2000) argues that to develop leadership skills, it is important to focus on developing the emotional skills of the leader.

Mumford et al. (2007) believes that focusing on the skills necessary for leadership is important, as it shifts the focus from the person holding the job, onto the job itself. It has been highlighted that leadership skills are important as by developing skills, leaders can lead more effectively, leading others towards achieving goals and objectives (Sierwiorek et al., 2012). Furthermore, the skills perspective asserts that anyone can be a leader, if they are willing to adopt the necessary skillset (Harrison, 2018). Leadership skills has been a focus of academia for several years, either directly, or indirectly (Wright and Taylor, 1994). However, it is still argued that

leadership skills have received inadequate attention within research (Gordon and Yukl, 2004; Wright and Taylor, 1994). There is a growing consensus that research needs to focus on what leaders do rather than what they possess (Harrison, 2018).

2.11 SERVING ERA

As previously mentioned, this research will also include a serving era, which is not discussed within Clark and Harrison's (2018) original leadership outline. This will consist of servant leadership.

2.11.1 SERVANT LEADERSHIP

In a post heroic era of leadership, there was a growing interest in a leadership approach which was ethical and did not promote self-serving. Business organisations began increasingly seeking leadership that emphasised ethics and a concern for society as a reaction to the numerous high-profile scandals in major corporations and organisations (Peterson et al., 2012). Despite the fact that servant leadership as a philosophy is an ancient concept, which some argue can be found dating back as far as 490 BC, it became prominent in academia within the late 1970s (Mcquade et al., 2020). Servant leadership has continued to evolve and develop throughout the 21st century. However, the phrase servant leadership and a standardised theory of it only first emerged in 1970 and was set out by Robert Greenleaf. Harrison (2018) explains that the concept of servant leadership is paradoxical by nature, as it is concerned with both the servant and the leader. It is therefore perhaps best explained by Greenleaf who states that:

“the servant is leader first... it begins with the natural feeling that one wants to serve, to serve first. Then conscious choice brings one to aspire to lead”

(Greenleaf, 1970 p.4)

Greenleaf (1970) further expands that not only can individuals be servant leaders, but additionally so can organisations. It can therefore be said that servant leadership has introduced an entirely new concept of leadership. Within this concept the leader

is no longer the all-knowing individual they were once considered to be, but rather the leader is now the servant (Harrison, 2018).

There are many recognisable examples of servant leaders throughout history. For example, Martin Luther King, Mother Theresa, Mahatma Ghandi, Nelson Mandela, Dr Elam and Ping – Fu (Keets and Albado, 2017; Barnabas et al., 2010; Humphreys et al., 2014; Karanxha et al., 2011; Nwagbara, 2013). It can also be found rooted within popular culture for example within the 'King Arthur' television series (Oliver and Reynolds, 2010), in the 'Remember the Titans' movie (Reimers and Parsons, 2004) and within the novel 'Journey to the East' (Hesse, 1956). Servant leadership is also embraced by prominent organisations such as Herman Miller, SouthWest Airlines and 7-eleven (Ingram, 2016). Furthermore, different frameworks and models of servant leadership are prominent throughout the literature (Barbuto and Wheeler, 2006; Bass and Steidmeister, 1999; Greenleaf; 1970; Laub, 1999; Spears, 1995; Van Dierendonck and Patterson 2010 etc.) It can be used to provide a comprehensive overview of the concept as a whole and the trends which have emerged.

As a relatively newer approach, servant leadership is often compared to arguably similar and more established forms of leadership (Graham, 1991; Hannay, 2009; Hoch et al., 2016; Peterlin et al., 2015; Reddy and Kamesh, 2016; Ruwhill and Elkin, 2016; Smith et al., 2004).

Peterlin et al. (2015) examines servant and sustainable leadership parallel to each other in order to explore the implications for decision making. Peterlin et al. (2015) suggests that the two styles of leadership should be merged together to promote organisational sustainability. This idea of combining servant leadership and other styles of leadership is not unique to Peterlin et al. (2015). The combination of Maori and servant leadership is suggested by Ruwhill and Elkin (2016). The concept of combining authentic and servant leadership is echoed throughout the literature (Ling et al., 2016; Kiersch and Peters, 2017). Vevele and Liniņa (2016) also compared authentic and servant leadership in order to evaluate the most effective style of leadership within the Latvian retail sector. The research found servant leadership was the more effective style. However, due to the limited number of respondents, by

the researchers own admission, this research can be said not to be entirely generalisable (Vevele and Liniņa, 2016). Whilst the two styles of leadership are often compared and combined, they are arguably, fundamentally different. Authentic leadership is concerned with knowing and being true to oneself whereas servant leadership is concerned with the development of others and helping them reach their goals (Graham, 1991).

Servant leadership has been compared and used interchangeably with spiritual leadership (Sendjaya and Sarros, 2002). Freeman and Auster (2011) suggests that for servant leaders to be successful they must practise spirituality. Contreas (2016) also contrasts servant and spiritual leadership. Contreas (2016) finds that both models include strengths, attitudes and performance. However, the two differ in organisational variables. Additionally, Fry et al. (2007) states that in general the conceptual and empirical research on servant leadership supports their proposition that the servant leader must adopt spiritual leader values. However, the research does not state or provide examples as to what this literature is.

Comparisons have also been drawn between transformational and servant leadership (Hannay, 2009; Smith et al., 2004). Hannay (2009) drew matching characteristics between the two approaches such as trust, influence, vision and modelling between the two concepts. This research concluded that the overall differences lie in the fact that transformational leadership focuses on the organisation whereas servant leadership focuses on people. Furthermore, Smith et al. (2004) compared servant leadership and transformational leadership and found that servant leadership was a more stable style of leadership within organisations. Therefore, although it is often compared to transformational leadership, it has been stated that transformational leaders may be unethical and behave in ways which are self-serving, thus differing them from servant leaders (Hoch et al., 2018). Choudray and Zaheers' (2013) research found that transformational and servant leadership have positive impacts on organisational learning, but transformational leadership shows more positive impact than servant leadership on organisational performance. However, this research could benefit from expanding out-with the cultural context of Pakistan, and indeed including more respondents. Ronquillo (2011) argues that servant leadership and transactional leadership both value human resources and

employee development. However, it is highlighted that the two leadership styles differ as transactional leadership is more concerned with risk, intellectualism and innovation (Ronquillo, 2011). However, one could argue that servant leadership also promotes these values.

Harrison (2018) explains that the effectiveness of servant leadership within all situations has been a source of contention within the research. Hannay (2009) also confirms that the effectiveness of each leadership style is dependent upon the context. What is effective in Sri Lanka, may not be as equally effective within the context of North America. Hannay (2009) further elaborates on this point by comparing servant leadership to Hofstede's (1983) five cultural dimensions and highlighting that servant leadership is most appropriate in countries with a lower power distance.

The research of Hoch et al. (2018) conducted a systematic computer-based search of the literature connected with the leadership terms associated with ethical, authentic and servant leadership in order to explore their variance. The research found a high correlation between transformational and ethical leadership, but it was substantially lower for servant leadership. It also found that ethical and authentic leadership are similar. The research could be conducted incorporating more styles of leadership. Additionally, further databases could have been used in the research.

The importance of ethics is discussed within the literature surrounding servant leadership (Greenleaf, 1977). Therefore, the two are often used together or interchangeably (Reddy and Kamash, 2016). Servant leadership aims to develop and empower followers (Graham, 1991). However, ethical leadership is focused upon making decisions ethically and punishing unethical actions. Moreover, servant leadership aims to help followers to meet their goals whereas ethical leadership is largely concerned with meeting the ethical goals of an organisation (De Hoogh and Den Hartog, 2008).

Servant leadership is often used interchangeably with stewardship. However, stewardship is largely concerned with the empowerment of employers and employees (Harrison, 2018). Servant leadership is concerned with leading selflessly

(Lussier and Achua, 2001). Stewardship is often listed as one of the characteristics of a servant leader, rather than an approach to leadership itself (Barbuto and Gifford, 2010; Barbuto and Wheeler, 2006; Van Dierendonck, 2011).

Whilst the aforementioned leadership styles are those most commonly compared to servant leadership, there are other comparisons which have been made. For example, charismatic leadership (Serrano, 2014; Veiss, 2016), pastoral leadership (Seeland, 2017), paternalistic leadership (Oner, 2012) and entrepreneurial leadership (Petrovskaya, and Mirakyan, 2017). However, whilst servant leadership is often compared or used interchangeably with other styles of leadership, it is clear that it is an approach to leadership within its own right, with its own fundamentals, which makes it different to those already in existence. It is the case that whilst servant leadership may encompass other theories, other theories do not necessarily encompass all the characteristics of servant leadership (Allen et al., 2016). It has been stated that the most important difference between servant leadership and other leadership constructs is its holistic nature, made up of morality, spirituality and authenticity (Sendjaya and Cooper, 2011).

There are, it should be noted, detractors of servant leadership. It has both spiritual and biblical connotations and is often associated with religious leadership. There are those who believe it is entirely too spiritual to be adopted within a business environment. (Tourish and Pinnington 2002). There are also those who state that the very paradox of servant and leadership means that it cannot possibly exist out with theory (Kim et al., 2014). Additionally, Anderson (2009) argues that servant leaders pursue common goals which are not beneficial to many organisations. Bradley (1999) states that within a hierarchy, followers are servants and that the right to leadership is granted to them by their followers. Yet, it could be counter-argued that within dictator and authoritarian leadership this can be said not to be the case. In order to fairly examine servant leadership, research must also examine its criticisms. This era will be further expanded upon in this chapter via a systematic literature review.

2.12 SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW:

This chapter will now proceed to explore the systematic literature review on servant leadership undertaken by this research. By determining the existing knowledge in the field at present the research will further be able to identify research questions, to be addressed by this research. It is important to note that systematic literature reviews differ from traditional literature reviews. Traditional literature reviews are generally descriptive, with literature selected in accordance with the availability or preference of the author (Uman, 2011). On the other hand, systematic literature reviews use prescribed methodological approaches and processes in order to identify the relevant literature (Uman, 2011). Systematic literature reviews conduct searches in accordance with a predetermined review protocol. A review protocol is necessary when conducting a systematic literature review in order to record all the steps taken in the process. This in turn provides transparency and can be used to justify all omissions and errors (Denyer and Tranfield, 2009). A systematic literature review should therefore be explanatory, transparent and heuristic (Tranfield et al., 2003).

A systematic literature review should include a wide range to allow it to explore the entirety of the phenomenon in question (Dawson et al., 2013). Tranfield et al. (2003) also state that a systematic review must be replicable, exclusive, aggregative and algorithmic. The study should be easily replicated by those who follow the reviews protocols, with the same results repeated every time. A protocol outlines the way studies were found and identified, how their usefulness was decided upon and how the studies were combined. To develop a review protocol, it is necessary to formulate literature review questions to be addressed (Harrison et al., 2016). This will allow for the development of a clear link between the evidence found and the recommendations and conclusions reached within a body of research (Slavin, 1986). To guide a systematic literature review, clearly framed and concise questions should be asked, in accordance with what the research aims to achieve (Cooper and Hedges, 1994). This will enable the review to establish a focus and filter out information which is not relevant (Light and Pillemar, 1984). By doing this, the criterion for the study becomes clearer (Denyer and Tranfield, 2009).

It is important to determine how the systematic literature review aligns with the methodology undertaken by the research. Previously, qualitative research was often

criticised for being unsystematic, thus the need for systematic elements to be implemented within qualitative projects (Glaser and Strauss, 1967). Qualitative methodologies, as will be undertaken by this research, are largely concerned with human beings who do not act in a predictable manner (Taylor et al. 2016). This means that its subjects are not orderly or systematic. This often means that a systematic aspect is necessary within qualitative research (Taylor et al. 2016). In essence, qualitative researchers are storytellers. Therefore, whilst the SLR is systematic, it contributes to the storyline which will be developed within the findings and discussion chapters (Taylor et al. 2016). Inductive reasoning, which will be undertaken by this research, links the existing data gathered to generate knowledge (Thomas, 2006). Thus, an SLR is necessary to explore the existing data and to ensure that the researcher is not entirely removed from the phenomenon that they are studying (Smith, 1983). It is not possible for social constructionist interpretivist researchers to conduct research without familiarising themselves with the subject (1983). Thus, for the philosophical approaches underpinning this research it is necessary to provide validity (Aguinaldo, 2004). Furthermore, the interpretivist interprets the data and therefore must have an extensive knowledge of it (Crowther and Lancaster, 2008). Additionally, an SLR will also allow for the development of an interview protocol, which is determined by the gaps in the knowledge this chapter will identify.

This research followed a three-stage review process as developed by Tranfield et al. ,(2003) and implemented by Harrison et al. (2016). The review process is as follows:

- Stage one: Planning the review
- Stage two: Conducting the review
- Stage three: Reporting and dissemination

This chapter will now proceed to explain the review process undertaken and examine the findings which were determined as a result of the systematic literature review. The research will then provide recommendations for further areas of research and determine research questions before reaching its conclusion. It begins by examining stage one of the review process: planning the review.

2.13 STAGE 1: PLANNING THE REVIEW:

A panel of experts in servant leadership were consulted to advise on the development of a comprehensive review protocol. A scoping study was initially conducted to understand and identify the emerging trends within the servant leadership literature (Harrison et al., 2016). This was then used to develop the questions for this review. The following questions were therefore used to guide this systematic literature review:

- What are the themes in the servant leadership literature?
- What are the gaps in the servant leadership literature?

2.13.1 EVALUATION CRITERIA

To evaluate which research should be included within the systematic literature review, a selection criterion is necessary in order to filter relevant results (Denyer and Tranfield, 2009). The systematic checklist allows the relevant information to be filtered into the systematic literature review (Tranfield et al., 2003).

The inclusion criteria used within this research is as follows:

- Peer reviewed journal articles originally published in the English language
- Is relevant to the questions outlined within the protocol
- The articles focus is servant leadership
- Is relevant to the research's overall aims and objectives
- Servant leadership mentioned in abstract

The exclusion criteria are as follows:

- Articles without references
- Articles focused on other approaches to leadership
- Unpublished works

- Work published before 1970
- Grey literature (e.g., book reviews, interviews, newspaper articles etc.)

These criteria will ensure that only data which is relevant to the research will be examined within the systematic literature review.

2.14 STAGE 2: CONDUCTING THE REVIEW

This research was protocol driven, which is concerned with the hand or electronic searching of a database (Grewal et al., 2016). It was conducted using widespread and generic web-based searches. This then allowed for the identification of the databases which offered the most relevant information on servant leadership. The research largely used Google Scholar to identify databases. Google Scholar was used as an all-encompassing method of searching for data. From Google scholar searches it became clear which databases prominently featured servant leadership, thus narrowing the overall search. Harrison et al. (2016) suggests that databases such as Springerlink, Taylor and Francis, Emerald Insight, Wiley Online, Science Direct, Web of Knowledge and Ingentaconnect are suitable databases for use within a systematic literature review. This highlights the importance of using recognised academic journals when conducting a review.

This systematic literature review used the following databases to search for information:

- Emerald Insight: Emerald Insight is a British based organisation which offers journals from management and business. It provides access to nearly 300 journals, 100 of which are concerned with business, therefore making it a useful database for this research (Emerald Insight, 2020).
- SAGE Publications: SAGE Publications publishes more than 1000 journals and 800 books a year (SAGE, 2016). It is therefore an invaluable source of information regarding servant leadership.

- Springerlink: Springerlink contains 2700 journals (Springer, 2018). It is also useful as it allows for a preview of journals, making it much easier to assess their relevance.
- Wiley Online: Wiley Online was chosen due to its multi-search functionality which enables for an expanded search. It also features 1500 multidisciplinary journals (Wiley, 2018).
- Taylor and Francis: Taylor and Francis is an international database which features all peer reviewed work. It publishes around 2700 journals a year (Informa, 2017).
- Web of Science: Web of Science allows for comprehensive searching and specialises in subfields in academia (Science Direct, 2018). It contains over 90 million records which include over 1 billion cited references (Science Direct, 2018).

As previously mentioned, this research used a scoping study. A scoping study consists of mapping the literature to determine the gaps in the literature (Ehrich et al., 2002). Tranfield et al. (2003) proposes that prior to a systematic literature review, a scoping study should be conducted to present a clear basis for the existing work. They may also be used to examine the extent of the research activity. Arksey and Omalley (2005) outline the following methodology used to conduct a scoping study:

- Identifying the research questions
- Identifying relevant studies
- Study selection
- Charting the data
- Collating, summarising and reporting results

This research conducted a scoping study according to the objectives identified within the introduction. It examined a broad range of servant leadership literature through conducting online searches across a wide variety of databases and online tools. It determined which were the most relevant to the research's questions and aims, which it was able to narrow and focus through a systematic literature review. Additionally, the research was able to use the data from the literature review to inform the search strings used within the database, as seen in table 2.3.

Within the databases, relevant search strings were used in order to identify data relevant to the research. The search strings which were used are as follows:

TABLE 2.3: TABLE OF SEARCH STRINGS

Search String	Key Word(s)
Search string 01	Servant leadership (in title)
Search string 01a	Servant Leadership (anywhere)
Search String 02	Serv*** AND Lead***** (in title)
Search String 02a	Servant leadership (anywhere)
Search String 03	Serve AND Lead***** (in title)
Search String 3a	Skills (anywhere)
Search String 4	Serv*** AND lead*****
Search String 4a	Behav**** OR traits OR characteristics OR personality anywhere

The root and search strings culminated in a total of 3194 articles. These were subject to the inclusion and exclusion criteria and 189 duplicate articles were

removed. The articles were then subjected to the study quality assessment developed by Harrison et al. (2016). This consists of ensuring that the papers reported unambiguous findings based upon arguments and evidence; examining the papers referenced, and their appropriateness and conducting an abstract screening. The end result consisted of a total of 89 journal articles. These articles were then manually cross referenced via their reference lists and citations. The relevant articles from this search were then again filtered using the inclusion and exclusion criteria. This resulted in the additional inclusion of 14 articles (see Figure 2.3)

FIGURE 2.3: ARTICLE SELECTION PROCESS

Therefore, the total number of articles identified as relevant within the SLR was 103. Detailed information about the selection process is found in Figure 2.4:

FIGURE 2.4 DATABASE SEARCH RESULTS

Please see appendix 7 for a more detailed description of the search string process.

A summary of the relevant articles selected is found below

TABLE 2.4: ARTICLE SUMMARIES

Name of Article	Author(s)	Year	Summary
<p>1. Perceptions of school principals' servant leadership and theory teachers job satisfaction in Oman</p>	<p>Al-Mahdy et al.</p>	<p>2016</p>	<p>This article aims to look at perceptions of servant leadership and job satisfaction using the servant leadership survey and job satisfaction survey. It finds that in Oman, teachers indicate moderate levels of job satisfaction and servant leadership in principals. However, this research is limited to primary schools within Oman and therefore is not generalisable.</p>
<p>2. Determining the antecedents and outcomes of servant leadership</p>	<p>Amah, O.</p>	<p>2018</p>	<p>This article looks at the antecedents of servant leadership. It finds that self-efficacy and motivation to serve are particularly important antecedents of servant leadership. However, this literature is limited to the Nigerian context.</p>

<p>3. The effective leadership style in NGO's: impact of servant leadership style on employee's work performance and mediation effect of work motivation</p>	<p>Awan et al.</p>	<p>2012</p>	<p>In this research, servant leadership is found to increase employee work performance by mediating employee motivation. However, this research exists within Pakistan and therefore may not be applicable in a wider context.</p>
<p>4. Examining gender differences of servant leadership: an analysis of the agentic and communal properties of servant leadership questionnaire</p>	<p>Barbuto and Gifford</p>	<p>2010</p>	<p>This research looks at the following five dimensions in both male and female servant leaders; altruistic calling, emotional healing, wisdom, persuasive mapping, and organisational stewardship. It finds that both male and female servant leaders utilised communal and agentic servant leadership dimensions equally. The research would benefit from further testing out within governmental organisations and across a wider geographical area.</p>

<p>5. Scale development and construct clarification of servant leadership</p>	<p>Barbuto and Wheeler</p>	<p>2006</p>	<p>This article reviews literature to present a construct and scale of servant leadership, however at the time of the literature the scale was yet to be empirically tested.</p>
<p>6. An examination of emotional intelligence as an antecedent of servant leadership</p>	<p>Barbuto et al.</p>	<p>2014</p>	<p>This article aims to examine emotional intelligence in regard to servant leadership. Whilst it finds that emotional intelligence can be a good predictor of a servant leaders' ideology it finds it may not be a good predictor of servant leader behaviours when rated by the followers.</p>
<p>7. Spirituality and servant leader behaviour</p>	<p>Beazley and Gemmill</p>	<p>2006</p>	<p>This article aims to measure personal spirituality beliefs of servant leaders. It finds that those with stronger spiritual beliefs are more likely to be perceived as servant leaders. However, this research is limited to one organisation in Texas and is therefore not generalisable.</p>

<p>8. Antecedents of servant leadership</p>	<p>Beck, C.</p>	<p>2014</p>	<p>This is a mixed methods article which aims to examine the antecedents of servant leadership within organisations. It presents six findings which relate to the success of servant leaders. However, it could benefit from further study out with North America in order to develop findings which can be generalised.</p>
<p>9. Correlational analysis of servant leadership and school climate</p>	<p>Black, G.</p>	<p>2010</p>	<p>This article finds a positive correlation between school climate and servant leadership. However, the research was only conducted in catholic schools and therefore it cannot be said that it is applicable to secular or schools of other religions.</p>
<p>10. Servant leadership in Italy and its relation to organizational variables</p>	<p>Bobbio et al.</p>	<p>2012</p>	<p>This article aimed to determine whether the servant leadership survey was valid in Italy. It finds that it positively applies to servant leadership within Italy. This research could be further expanded</p>

			across more geographical locations.
11. Teacher as servant leader	Bowman, R	2010	This research recommends that teachers should practise servant leadership. It does not provide any empirical evidence to validate its findings.
12. Servant leadership: a critique of Robert Greenleaf's concept of leadership	Bradley, Y.	1999	This research reviews Greenleaf's original writings on servant leadership. However, it could benefit from reviewing more of the seminal and relevant works on servant leadership.
13. Servant leadership: a model for future faculty and future institutions	Buchen	1998	This article examines the work of Robert Greenleaf and uses it to propose a model of servant leadership for use within educational institutions. The model would benefit from empirical testing.
14. The call for servant leadership in intercollegiate athletics	Burton and Peachey	2013	This article puts forward proposals for sports leaders and directors on how they could best utilise and

			practice servant leadership. It would benefit from empirical research to validate its findings.
15. The influence of servant leadership on restaurant employee engagement	Carter and Baghurst	2014	This article conducted research on employees of servant leadership and found that servant leadership positively influences employee engagement and loyalty, However the research was confined to one restaurant with only 11 employees and therefore could benefit from further validation.
16. Servant leadership and goal attainment through meaningful life and vitality: a diary study	Rodríguez-Carvajal et al.	2018	This article conducted a diary study which found that servant leadership promotes employees' goals. The research developed a model. However, the model could benefit from empirical testing.
17. The effects of servant leadership on teachers' organizational commitment in primary schools in Turkey	Cerit, Y.	2010	This article finds that servant leadership has a positive influence on teachers' organisational commitment within primary schools in Turkey. However, it is limited to primary

			schools and the Turkish context.
18. The effects of servant leadership behaviours of school principals on teachers' job satisfaction	Cerit, Y.	2009	This article looks at the relationship between servant leadership of principals on teacher's job satisfaction. It finds a positive correlation between the two. It also finds servant leadership is a strong indicator of teacher job satisfaction. However, this research is limited to primary schools and the context of Turkey.
19. The servant leader: a higher calling for dental professionals	Certosimo, F.	2009	This research highlights how servant leadership is compatible with leaders within the dental profession. However, it does not provide any empirical evidence to validate the findings.
20. The impact of servant leadership on subordinates' organizational tenure on trust in leader and attitudes	Chan and Mak	2014	This article aims to examine the relationship between servant leadership, trust in a leader and satisfaction. It finds that trust in a leader mediates the relationship between

			servant leadership and subordinates job satisfaction. However, this research is limited to the Chinese context.
21. Effects of servant leadership on satisfaction with leaders: inclusion of situational variables	Charles, D.	2015	This article finds that within hotel workers in Haiti, servant leadership is positively linked to followers' satisfactions with their leaders. However, this research is restricted to the hotel industry within Haiti.
22. An identification perspective of servant leadership's effects	Chen et al.	2016	This article aims to examine the effects of servant leadership on organisational citizenship behaviours and employee turnover intentions. Conducted within the hospitality region in China, the research shows that servant leadership reduces the employees fear of being close to the supervisor whilst also reaffirming their identification within an organisation. This research could benefit from further expansion out with the hospitality sector to make it more generalisable.

<p>23. In search of clarity on servant leadership: domain specification and reconceptualization</p>	<p>VanMeter et al.</p>	<p>2016</p>	<p>This article examines the literature surrounding servant leadership to highlight the direction it believes servant leadership literature should be taking. Yet it is unclear why the literature that was chosen was indeed chosen and it lacks any empirical validation.</p>
<p>24. Examining the effects of servant leadership on life satisfaction</p>	<p>Chughta</p>	<p>2017</p>	<p>This research finds that servant leadership is positively related to both work engagement and organisational based self-esteem and additionally to life satisfaction. However, the research is limited to the context of Pakistan.</p>
<p>25. Servant leadership and procedural justice in the U.S. National Park Service: the antecedents of job satisfaction</p>	<p>Chung et al.</p>	<p>2010</p>	<p>This article aims to examine servant leadership perceptions within National Park Service employees. It finds that servant leadership positively influences employee job satisfaction. The research could be expanded across a greater number of national parks to</p>

			further validate its findings.
26. A case study of servant leadership in the NHL	Crippen, C.	2017	This article looks at leadership in the NHL. It finds there is a leadership culture which aligns with servant leadership within the NHL. However, it is one niche area of sport and it is not shown if this is applicable to wider sporting organisations.
27. Pioneer women in Manitoba: evidence of servant-leadership	Crippen, C.	2004	This research reviews the evidence and literature surrounding three pioneer women in Manitoba and finds evidence of the ten characteristics as put forward by Spears within each woman's history. It would benefit from studying a wider array of historical figures to further validate its findings.
28. Structural equivalence of the Barbuto and Wheeler (2006) servant	Dannhauser and Boshoff	2007	This research aims to examine the configuration equivalence, of the servant leadership questionnaire. It finds that it cannot be

<p>leadership questionnaire on North American and South African samples</p>			<p>replicated within the South African context.</p>
<p>29. Development of the servant leadership assessment instrument</p>	<p>Dennis and Bocarnea</p>	<p>2005</p>	<p>This article builds upon Patterson's servant leadership theory and develops an instrument to measure servant leadership which consists of empowerment, love, humility, trust and vision. The instrument developed would benefit from empirical testing.</p>
<p>30. A factor analysis of Page and Wong servant leadership instrument</p>	<p>Dennis and Winston</p>	<p>2003</p>	<p>This article analyses Page and Wong's servant leadership instrument and only confirms three of the original factors. It concludes the model would benefit from further development.</p>
<p>31. How might servant leadership work?</p>	<p>Ebener and O'Connell</p>	<p>2010</p>	<p>This article examines three Catholic parishes and finds servant leadership positively promotes a service orientated environment. However, as</p>

			mentioned the research is limited to three Catholic churches making it difficult to generalise on a wider scale.
32. Servant leadership: a systematic review and call for future research	Eva et al.	2018	A systematic literature review of servant leadership is conducted. However, this research fails to include search strings or inclusion/exclusion criteria.
33. Servant leadership: setting the stage for empirical research	Farling et al.	1999	This research presents a model of servant leadership based on influence, trust, vision credibility and service. However, the model would benefit from empirical testing.
34. Servant leadership and job satisfaction within private healthcare practices	Farrington and Lillah	2018	This research aims to examine the influence of servant leadership on job satisfaction. It finds that some elements of servant leadership such as developing others influence servant leadership. However, servanthood and humility did not. This research is however restricted both to private healthcare

			organisations and the South African context.
35. Attitudes towards collaboration and servant leadership among nurses, physicians and residents	Garber et al.	2009	This article aims to examine the self-perceived servant leadership characteristics of nurses, physicians and residents. However, it is limited to health care within the North American context.
36. Is servant leadership useful for sustainable Nordic health care?	Gunnarsdottir, S.	2014	This article tests a Dutch version of the servant leadership survey in hospitals and finds it is a suitable model for Nordic health care and finds that job satisfaction is positively linked to servant leadership. However, it uses a new instrument for measurement which lacks validation and is limited to the Icelandic context.
37. Exploring servant leadership across cultures: a study of followers in	Hale and Fields	2007	This article aims to examine the differences in perceptions of servant leadership between Ghana and North America. It finds that Ghanaians

<p>Ghana and the USA</p>			<p>experienced significantly less servant leadership than North Americans. The research would benefit from empirical research to further validate its findings.</p>
<p>38. Servant leadership in the people's republic of China: a case study of the public sector</p>	<p>Han et al.</p>	<p>2010</p>	<p>This article aims to examine if the Western perspective of servant leadership is the same as in China. It finds that within China, it is public servant leadership within the public sector and servant leadership within the private sector. However, the research uses 'Chinese' servant leadership and western servant leadership within the surveys suggesting it is comparing two different types of servant leadership. This makes its findings unclear. It may benefit from making the comparison of one type of servant leadership.</p>

<p>39. Teacher as servant applications of Greenleaf's servant leadership in higher education</p>	<p>Hays, J.</p>	<p>2008</p>	<p>This research aims to examine servant leadership and teaching and then make recommendations as to how lecturers can incorporate servant leadership into their teaching, however it lacks empirical research to validate its recommendations.</p>
<p>40. Servant leaders inspire servant followers: antecedents and outcomes for employees and the organization</p>	<p>Hunter et al.</p>	<p>2013</p>	<p>This research aimed to examine the relationships between servant leadership, personality and critical follower and organisational outcome. It found that leader agreeableness was positively associated with servant leadership however extraversion was negatively related. It was also found that servant leadership resulted in decreased follower turnover intentions and disengagement.</p>
<p>41. Team effectiveness and six essential servant</p>	<p>Irving and Longbotham</p>	<p>2007</p>	<p>This article uses the organisational leadership assessment and the team effectiveness</p>

<p>leadership themes: a regression model based on items in the organizational leadership assessment</p>			<p>questionnaire to present a multiple regression model that explains a significant percentage of the variance in the effectiveness of teams. However, the research is limited as it was only conducted in one non-profit organisation.</p>
<p>42. Examining the impact of servant leadership on sales force performance</p>	<p>Jaramillo et al.</p>	<p>2009</p>	<p>This article finds that salespersons perceptions of servant leadership relate to salesperson/customer orientation and drive adaptive selling behaviours and sales performance outcomes. It would benefit from further expansion out with North America.</p>
<p>43. Healing a broken spirit: role of servant leadership</p>	<p>Jit et al.</p>	<p>2017</p>	<p>This article looks at servant leaders' approach to suffering. It finds that their compassionate approach to leadership allows them to alleviate the suffering of their followers. However, this research was limited to only 15 participants.</p>

<p>44. A correlation of servant leadership, leader trust and organizational trust</p>	<p>Joseph and Winston</p>	<p>2005</p>	<p>This article uses existing constructs and measuring instruments to develop a model of servant leadership attributes. It finds servant leadership correlates positively with both leader trust and organisational trust. The research would benefit from empirical validation.</p>
<p>45. Servant leadership, employer brand perception, trust in leaders and turnover intentions: examining the impact of servant leadership on salespersons turnover intention</p>	<p>Kashyap and Rangnekar</p>	<p>2009</p>	<p>This article examines servant leadership and its impact on salespersons turnover intention. It finds that along with other factors servant leadership can positively influence salesperson turnover, particularly when the salesperson views the organisation as unethical. The research could be further expanded geographically.</p>
<p>46. Servant leadership and perceptions of service quality provided by front-line</p>	<p>Koyuncu et al.</p>	<p>2014</p>	<p>This research aims to examine servant leadership impact on hotel workers. It finds that service employees with high levels of servant leadership indicate</p>

<p>service workers in hotels in Turkey: achieving competitive advantage</p>			<p>higher levels of service quality. However, the research is only applicable to Turkey and within the hotel industry.</p>
<p>47. Character and leadership: situating servant leadership in a proposed virtues framework</p>	<p>Lanctot and Irving</p>	<p>2010</p>	<p>This research reviews the literature surrounding servant leadership so as to propose a framework of the virtues necessary for servant leadership, however the framework is not empirically validated.</p>
<p>48. How and when servant leadership enhances life satisfaction</p>	<p>Li et al.</p>	<p>2018</p>	<p>This research finds positive links between servant leadership and employee life satisfaction and a positive workplace affect. However, by the authors own admission, the time lagged design of the research may limit the ability to draw conclusions.</p>
<p>49. Servant leadership and serving culture: influence on individual</p>	<p>Liden et al.</p>	<p>2013</p>	<p>This research examines servant leadership in restaurants and finds that it positively affects creativity, restaurant performance, customer service</p>

and unit performance			behaviours and employee job performance. However, it is important to note that the research was conducted within a chain of restaurants and therefore may not be applicable to independent or family run restaurants.
50. Servant leadership: validation of a short form of the SL-28	Liden et al.	2015	This article examines servant leadership and knowledge sharing climate. It finds that servant leadership positively affects knowledge sharing and team sales performance. It would benefit from further testing out with the USA.
51. Servant leadership: development of a multidimensional measure and multilevel assessment	Liden et al.	2008	This article validates the servant leadership scale using confirmatory factor analysis. However, it is a new model and would therefore benefit from further empirical testing.
52. From the West to the East: validating servant	Liu et al.	2015	This article aimed to examine the generalisability of servant leadership in Western society and

<p>leadership in the Chinese public sector</p>			<p>China. It found that generalisation is limited but also finds that servant leadership is positively associated with public service motivation. However, the research needs to investigate more countries in the East in order to truly draw comparisons between the West and the East.</p>
<p>53. Just the servant: an intersectional critique of servant leadership</p>	<p>Liu</p>	<p>2017</p>	<p>This article conducting a study of one Asian manager whose servant leadership was informed by dynamics of race, gender, sexuality, age and class. However, it important to note that this research only involved one participant and could be further validated through the use of more participants.</p>
<p>54. Do servant-leaders help satisfy follower needs? An organizational justice perspective</p>	<p>Mayer et al.</p>	<p>2008</p>	<p>This article finds the need for a theoretical model linking servant-leadership to job satisfaction as the two are positively correlated. However, the model it suggests has not yet been tested or validated.</p>

<p>55. Servant leadership, employee satisfaction, and organizational performance in rural community hospitals</p>	<p>McCann et al.</p>	<p>2014</p>	<p>This research finds that within rural healthcare organisations, employee satisfaction and servant leadership are strongly correlated. However, this is conducted in a rural environment and may not be applicable to suburban or cosmopolitan areas.</p>
<p>56. Job satisfaction and the priority of valuing people</p>	<p>McNeff and Irving</p>	<p>2017</p>	<p>This research finds a positive correlation between job satisfaction and servant leadership. However, the researcher in this work is also a leader in the organisations in question which could result in interviewer bias.</p>
<p>57. Insights on practicing of servant leadership in the events sector</p>	<p>Mehjeirkouni, M.</p>	<p>2018</p>	<p>This research aims to see if events sector leaders are perceived as servant leaders. However, the results were unclear and could benefit from further validation.</p>
<p>58. What every leader ought to know about becoming a</p>	<p>Mertel and Brill</p>	<p>2015</p>	<p>The authors review case studies to develop a servant leadership competency and</p>

<p>servant leader</p>			<p>values assessment for use by leaders in healthcare organisations, however the recommendations are yet to be empirically validated.</p>
<p>59. Servant leadership across cultures</p>	<p>Mittal and Dorfman</p>	<p>2012</p>	<p>This article analyses the following five aspects of servant leadership namely, Egalitarianism, Moral Integrity, Empowering, Empathy and Humility. It finds that different elements of servant leadership are endorsed across different parts of the world according to GLOBEs culture clusters. The research would benefit from empirically testing its findings for further validation.</p>
<p>60. How does servant leadership affect employee attitudes, behaviours and psychological climates in a for-profit</p>	<p>Ozyilmaz and Cicek</p>	<p>2015</p>	<p>This article aims to measure servant leadership effect on behaviours, employee attitudes and psychological climate. It finds it positively impacts all three and that psychological climate can also mediate servant leadership and</p>

organizational contact?			employee behaviours. This research would benefit from further validation as at present it is only applicable within the Australian context.
61. Challenging servant leadership in the non-profit sector the side effects of servant leadership	Palumbo, R.	2016	This research is conducted via participant observation in charities in Tanzania. It finds that servant leadership can constrain rather than empower and discourage organisational commitment. The research could be further expanded out with Tanzania.
62. A systematic literature review of servant leadership theory in organizational contexts	Parris and Peachey	2013	A systematic literature review of servant leadership. However, this review fails to include search strings. Additionally, it states that the authors used databases available through their university libraries but does not seem to include any of their major business databases.
63. Exploring servant leadership across	Pekertie and Sendjaya	2010	Examines servant leadership across cultures using GLOBE study. Servant

<p>cultures: comparative study in Australia and Indonesia</p>			<p>leadership is culturally accepted in both Australia and Indonesia. However, different attributes of servant leadership were ranked in different orders of importance. Further comparisons could be made across additional cultures to further develop this research.</p>
<p>64. One University's response to the anti- leadership vaccine: developing servant leaders</p>	<p>Polleys, M.</p>	<p>2002</p>	<p>This research explains how a servant leadership program is being implemented within Columbus State University. However, the program is relatively new therefore making it difficult to conclude its success yet.</p>
<p>65. Catholic servant leadership in education: going beyond the secular paradigm</p>	<p>Punnachet</p>	<p>2009</p>	<p>This article argues that servant leadership has become too secular and therefore needs to be redeveloped into a Christian framework, however it provides no empirical evidence to validate its recommendations.</p>

<p>66. A relational perspective to knowledge creation: role of servant leadership</p>	<p>Rai and Prakash</p>	<p>2012</p>	<p>This article presents a model of servant leadership which is concerned with sharing leadership responsibilities. It highlights that this will lead to better knowledge creation within organisations. This model would benefit from empirical testing.</p>
<p>67. A new scale to measure executive servant leadership: development, analysis and implications for research</p>	<p>Reed et al.</p>	<p>2011</p>	<p>This article reviews the literature surrounding servant leadership and suggests a new scale for measuring executive servant leadership: Executive Servant Leadership Scale (ESLS). The scale would benefit from being empirically tested.</p>
<p>68. Service before self: towards a theory of servant-leadership</p>	<p>Reinke, S.J.</p>	<p>2004</p>	<p>This research finds that the one element of servant leadership: stewardship, determines trust within organisations. However, this research was only conducted in a suburb of one state meaning it may not be applicable to wider America or indeed other nations.</p>

<p>69. Servant leadership in sport a new paradigm for effective coach behaviour</p>	<p>Rieke et al.</p>	<p>2008</p>	<p>This article aims to examine the effects of coaches' servant leadership on athletes. It found that athletes who believed their coaches to be servant leaders displayed higher intrinsic motivation, were more task oriented and were more satisfied. However, this research is limited in the respect that it only looks at coaches within basketball.</p>
<p>70. Servant leadership in sport: a review, synthesis, and applications for sport management classrooms</p>	<p>Robinson et al.</p>	<p>2018</p>	<p>This research reviews servant leadership literature and presents recommendations for leaders in sports to practice servant leadership. This research would benefit from empirical evidence to support the recommendations it makes.</p>
<p>71. Leading people positively: cross-cultural validation of the servant leadership survey</p>	<p>Rodriguez-Carvajal et al.</p>	<p>2014</p>	<p>This article assesses servant leadership models and compares them. It finds similarities between SL-8 and SL-28 scales. It would benefit from the empirical testing of both models</p>

			to make further comparisons.
72. A review of servant leadership attributes: developing a practical model	Russell and Stone	2002	This article reviews servant leadership literature so as to develop a theoretical model of the concept. The model would benefit from empirical testing.
73. The role of values in servant leadership	Russell, R.	2001	This is a literature review which deduces that the three main aspects of servant leadership are trust, appreciation of others and empowerment. This research could benefit from further empirical testing.
74. Servant leadership: The primacy of service	Savel and Munro	2017	This research explores servant leadership and presents it as a leadership model suitable for intensive care units, however it lacks any empirical evidence.
75. Servant leadership behaviour scale: a hierarchical model and	Sendjaya and Cooper	2011	This article tests a six-dimensional scale of servant leadership - The servant leadership behaviour scale. It finds it can

test of construct validity			successfully be used to measure and identify servant leadership. The scale would benefit from empirical testing.
76. Servant leadership as antecedent of trust in organizations	Sendjaya and Pekerti	2010	This article aims to examine the impact of servant leadership on followers' trust. It finds that those who perceived high servant leadership behaviours have significantly higher trust levels than those who did not. The survey would benefit from further geographical testing as at present it is only valid within the Australian context.
77. Servant leadership: Its origin, development and application in organizations	Sendjaya and Sarros	2002	This article aims to examine the philosophical foundations of servant leadership and examine its history. However, it could benefit from further empirical evidence when discussing the application of servant leadership within organisations.
78. Defining and measuring servant	Sendjaya et al.	2008	This article aims to examine previous qualitative and

<p>leadership behaviour in organizations</p>			<p>quantitative studies so as to define servant leadership. It also aims to examine the most prominent behaviours for servant leaders. It then presents a framework of servant leadership.</p>
<p>79. Public servant leadership: myth or powerful reality</p>	<p>Shim et al.</p>	<p>2016</p>	<p>This article examines whether servant leadership influences government employees' attitudes and productivity. It finds servant leadership contributes to developing employees' trust in leadership, enhancing employees' perception of fair work procedures, and inducing benevolent work behaviours (OCB). However, it is limited to the North Korean context.</p>
<p>80. The effect of servant leadership on rewards, organizational culture and its implication for</p>	<p>Sihombing et al.</p>	<p>2018</p>	<p>This article aimed to examine factors that affect employee performance within Bank Tabungan Negara, Indonesia. The research found that servant leadership significantly affected rewards and organisational culture,</p>

<p>employee's performance</p>			<p>but it had no significant effect on employee performance. However, the research is limited to one bank in Indonesia.</p>
<p>81. Have you paid your rent? Servant leadership in correctional education</p>	<p>Simmons and Branch</p>	<p>2015</p>	<p>This article reviews the literature surrounding servant leadership and suggests it as a model for those who teach correctional education within a correctional institution. However, it provides no empirical evidence to validate its recommendations.</p>
<p>82. Servant leadership and team performance: the mediating role of knowledge-sharing climate</p>	<p>Song et al.</p>	<p>2015</p>	<p>This article examines servant leadership and knowledge sharing climate. It finds that servant leadership positively affects knowledge sharing and team sales performance. This research is however limited to the South Korean context.</p>
<p>83. Servant leadership and engagement in a merge process under high uncertainty</p>	<p>Sousa and van Dierendonck</p>	<p>2014</p>	<p>This article validated the servant leadership survey in Portugal and also found that servant leadership strongly affected work engagement in conditions of high</p>

			uncertainty. However, this research is limited to very specific conditions within an organisation.
84. Servant leaders as under estimators: theoretical and practical implications	Sousa and van Dierendonck	2017	This article finds that underestimation is the strongest predictor of servant leadership effectiveness and that this positively impacted psychological empowerment amongst followers. This research may benefit from further testing to validate servant leaderships effectiveness in generating psychological empowerment amongst followers.
85. Reflections on Robert K Greenleaf and servant leadership	Spears, L.	1996	This article discusses the original writings of Greenleaf on servant leadership. It would perhaps benefit from further analysis of additional texts.
86. Character and servant leadership: ten characteristics of effective,	Spears, L.	2010	This research reviews servant leadership literature and determines that there are ten main characteristics for servant leadership.

<p>caring leaders.</p>			<p>These are: listening, empathy, healing, awareness, persuasion, conceptualization, foresight, stewardship, commitment to the growth of people, and building community. However, this research lacks empirical validation.</p>
<p>87. Servant leadership in English sixth form colleges: what do teachers tell us?</p>	<p>Stoten, D.</p>	<p>2013</p>	<p>This article aims to examine whether servant leadership is useful for English sixth form colleges. It is found to be less applicable than transformational management. However, it is limited to the small context of sixth form teachers which is only an applicable demographic within England and therefore not generalisable.</p>
<p>88. Principles of servant-leadership in community health nursing</p>	<p>Sturm, B.</p>	<p>2008</p>	<p>This article reviews previous studies to assess servant leadership's suitability for community health nursing. It finds that servant leadership can increase nurse collaboration, satisfaction, and</p>

			retention, however it is not empirically validated.
89. Work–family effects of servant leadership: the roles of emotional exhaustion and personal learning	Tang et al.	2016	This research finds that employee perceptions of servant leadership related negatively to work family conflict and positively to work-to-family positive spill over. However, this research is limited to the Chinese context.
90. Examination of leadership practices of principals identified as servant leaders	Taylor et al.	2007	This article aimed to examine the practices of principals who were identified as servant leaders. It found that principals who identified as servant leaders were rated significantly higher by their teachers in the five leadership areas highlighted by the leadership practices inventory. However, it fails to consider the principal's own perceptions of their leadership, simply focusing on the teachers' perceptions which could result in participant bias.

<p>91. The servant leadership survey: development and validation of a multidimensional measure</p>	<p>van Dierendonck and Nuijten</p>	<p>2011</p>	<p>This article conducted a literature review alongside quantitative research to develop an eight-dimensional model of servant leadership. The eight dimensions are standing back, forgiveness, courage, empowerment, accountability, authenticity, humility, and stewardship. The model is however new and could benefit from further empirical validation.</p>
<p>92. Compassionate love as a cornerstone of servant leadership: an integration of previous theorizing and research</p>	<p>van Dierendonck and Patterson</p>	<p>2014</p>	<p>This article examines the research surrounding servant leadership and proposes that compassionate love is necessary for servant leaders to serve others. However, the article itself admits that love is a mysterious concept and difficult to measure. Therefore, with no empirical evidence and a concept which is difficult to define and measure, the validity of the proposals made within this article remains debatable.</p>

<p>93. The cross-cultural invariance of the servant leadership survey: a comparative study across eight countries</p>	<p>van Dierendonck et al.</p>	<p>2017</p>	<p>This article tests the servant leadership survey across eight countries and highlights the extent to which servant leadership is experienced across different cultures. However, it is important to note that the research was conducted in western countries and therefore the findings of this research cannot be said to be applicable to the developing world.</p>
<p>94. Servant leadership: a review and synthesis</p>	<p>van Dierendonck, D.</p>	<p>2010</p>	<p>A literature review of servant leadership. This research would benefit from a systematic approach to highlight why the literature chosen for the study was included, and justification for the literature excluded.</p>
<p>95. Individual differences in servant leadership: the roles of values and personality</p>	<p>Washington et al.</p>	<p>2006</p>	<p>The research aims to examine servant leadership and four individual differences, values of empathy, integrity, and competence and the five-factor model's</p>

			personality factor of agreeableness. It found servant leadership was positively related to all aspects. The research could be expanded to include more organisations for further validation.
96. Servant leadership	Wilson, R.	1999	This article aims to highlight how servant leadership can benefit employees and an organisations strategic plans, however it does not provide any empirical evidence to confirm its recommendations.
97. Seeking and measuring the essential behaviours of servant leadership	Winston and Fields	2015	This article aims to examine the effect of servant leadership on subordinates' trust in leadership and job satisfaction. It finds that the ten main behaviours of servant leadership are; practices what he/she preaches; serves people without regard for their gender, nationality or race; sees serving as mission of responsibility to others; genuinely interested in

			employees as people; understands that serving others is most important; willing to make sacrifices to serve others; seeks to instill trust rather than fear and insecurity; is always honest; is driven by a higher calling and promotes values that transcend self-interest and material success. The research could be further expanded out with the American context.
98. Servant leadership as a humane orientation: using the GLOBE study construct of humane orientation to show that servant leadership is more global than Western	Winston and Ryan	2008	This article uses GLOBE's study to present a non-western concept of servant leadership, however it is not empirically validated.
99. Servant leadership at Heritage Bible College: a	Winston, B.	2004	This article verifies Patterson and Winston's model of servant leadership via a case study of employee attitudes

single case study			towards leaders at Heritage Bible college. However, it is limited to only one college.
100. Measurement invariance of the servant leadership questionnaire across K-12 principal gender	Xu et al.	2015	This article aims to test the servant leadership questionnaire on males and females. It finds that females were more likely to demonstrate emotional healing, wisdom, persuasive mapping and organisational stewardship than males and there was no difference on altruistic calling. However, this research is limited as its participants were solely high school principals in America.
101. Servant leadership and voice behaviour: a cross-level investigation in China	Yan and Xiao	2016	This article tests the influence of servant leadership on voice behaviour. It finds that servant leadership significantly influences voice behaviour, and that psychological safety mediates between servant leadership and voice behaviour.

<p>102. A multilevel study of servant leadership on creativity: the roles of self- efficacy and power distance</p>	<p>Yang et al.</p>	<p>2017</p>	<p>This article conducts empirical research in banks in China to develop a model of beliefs that mediate the relationship between servant leadership, employee creativity and team creativity.</p>
<p>103. A content analysis of servant leadership studies</p>	<p>Yigirt and Bozkurt</p>	<p>2017</p>	<p>This article reviews servant leadership literature written between 2000 and 2016, therefore it is limited only to a span of 16 years.</p>

2.15 REPORTING AND DISSEMINATION

Thus far, this chapter has advised how the results of the literature were derived, by exploring the planning and conducting stages. This chapter will now proceed to examine the literature through reporting and dissemination. To do this, the following five key areas were examined; geographical distribution; types of articles; number of publications; citations and journal publications. Then a thematic analysis was conducted regarding the literature.

Having discussed how the review was carried out, this chapter will now report the findings of the systematic literature review and answer the review questions.

2.15.1. DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

The chapter will now provide a descriptive analysis of the research. This includes a geographical distribution of the articles, types of study, methodological approaches, methods of data collection, number of publications, citations and journal publications.

2.15.2 GEOGRAPHICAL DISTRIBUTION

Most of the research concerning servant leadership was found to be within North America with 50 articles (See Figure 2.5). The second largest concentration of research was found within China with nine articles. Despite the existence of research within China, servant leadership clearly is a topic largely confined to the West with eight research articles in Australia and two articles in both Spain and Portugal. To summarise a total of 77% of the research concerning servant leadership exists within the developed countries. This shows that servant leadership is still a concept which is lacking in research within developing countries. Additionally, only one paper conducted research in United Kingdom. However, it is important to highlight that this research was only conducted in England and is therefore not applicable to the United Kingdom as a whole. This clearly indicates that within the rest of the United Kingdom, for example, Scotland, there is a gap in the knowledge concerning servant leadership.

FIGURE 2.5 NUMBER OF ARTICLES ACCORDING TO GEOGRAPHICAL DISTRIBUTION

2.15.3 TYPES OF STUDY

Findings from the review show that there are three different types of research employed within servant leadership. These types of research were conceptual, reviews and empirical. Most of the research were conducted empirically at 60%. A further 23% of the research was conceptual and 17% of the research consisted of literature reviews (see Figure 2.6)

FIGURE 2.6 TYPES OF STUDY

2.15.4 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES

Most of the research conducted within the literature was quantitative in nature, contributing about 78% of the empirical research. 17% of the research conducted was qualitative and 5% used a mixed method approach. This clearly indicates that most of the research conducted regarding servant leadership is quantitative, and thus suggests there is room for further qualitative research to be conducted (see Figure 2.7).

FIGURE 2.7 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES

2.15.5 MODES OF DATA COLLECTION

As shown above, majority of the research concerning servant leadership is conducted quantitatively, therefore it is unsurprising that the most common method of data collection were surveys at 77%. Qualitative methods were far less common, with only 14% of the research consisting of interviews. Even less common were participant observation; polynomial and 3D surface analysis, focus groups, with 2% and diary studies at 1%. This highlights that there is much more scope for qualitative research methods to be employed when researching servant leadership. Please see below chart for further detail (See Figure 2.8).

FIGURE 2.8 MODES OF DATA COLLECTION

2.15.6 NUMBER OF PUBLICATIONS BY YEAR

This section will now present a chronological overview of publications published by year. The research within this review emerged in 1996 and has continued to be an area of study up until today. There have been peaks in the research, particularly in 2010, and interest in servant leadership has peaked again in 2018. This shows that despite the conceptualisation of servant leadership in the 1970s it remains a relatively new concept within academia. Additionally, due to its recent peak, it is a relevant and current area of research.

FIGURE 2.9 NUMBER OF PUBLICATIONS BY YEAR

2.15.7 ARTICLE CITATIONS

The articles varied dramatically in terms of the number of times they were cited, from 0 to 1249 (see Figure 2.10). The most widely cited article was 'A review of servant leadership attributes: developing a practical model' (Russell and Stone, 2002). This article had 1249 citations in total. This article is often considered one of the seminal works of servant leadership and it developed an eight-dimensional model of servant leadership. It is used frequently throughout the literature when determining servant leadership and is highly influential in the field, as well as being one of the original frameworks put forward concerning servant leadership.

FIGURE 2.10 ARTICLES

2.15.8 JOURNAL PUBLICATIONS

In total, articles included in the review were published across 74 journals. The highest number of publications was found in the Leadership and Organization Development Journal. The journals which had the most articles are found in Figure 2.11, all other journals featured one article.

FIGURE 2.11 JOURNALS WITH THE HIGHEST NUMBER OF PUBLICATIONS

2.16 ANSWERING THE REVIEW QUESTIONS

This section of the research provides the answers to the two review questions of the SLR.

2.16.1 WHAT ARE THE THEMES PRESENT WITHIN THE SERVANT LEADERSHIP LITERATURE?

In order to address review question one, a thematic analysis was conducted, which will now be discussed. Braun and Clarke (2006) suggest that a thematic analysis is concerned with the identification and recording of patterns which are found within the data. They outline six stages necessary to conduct a thematic analysis (see Figure 2.12).

FIGURE 2.12: STAGES OF THEMATIC ANALYSIS

(Braun and Clarke, 2006)

After completion of the first five stages of thematic analysis it became apparent there were recurring themes present within the literature. This chapter will provide an analysis of the literature in accordance with themes, concluding Braun and Clarke's (2006) sixth stage.

2.16.2 VALUES

Research concerning the values of servant leadership emerged as a theme throughout the thematic analysis (Hays, 2008; Mertel and Brill, 2015; Russell, 2001; Washington et al., 2006). The following table highlights the research concerned with values which were present:

TABLE 2.5 VALUES

Author(s)	Name of Article
Hays (2008)	Teacher as servant applications of Greenleaf's servant leadership in higher education.
Mertel and Brill (2015)	What every leader ought to know about becoming a servant leader.
Russell (2001)	The role of values in servant leadership.
Washington et al. (2006)	Individual differences in servant leadership: the roles of values and personality.

Values are typically concerned with the life goals which guide people's judgement and their perceptions. In terms of servant leadership, Russell (2001) believes that it is the values of the servant leader that distinguish them from other approaches to leadership. Russell (2001) expands that to practise servant leadership a value system is important, as it allows one to serve. However, it is important to highlight that the conclusions reached by Russell have not been validated empirically. Washington et al. (2006) also believes that the values of the servant leader impact upon the way in which they lead. Washington et al. (2006) expands that the

necessary values for servant leadership are empathy, integrity and competence. However, as is the case with Russell (2001), Washington et al. (2006) lacks empirical validation for this research.

The research of Hays (2008) is concerned with applying how the values of servant leadership can impact on learning experiences of both leaders and teachers (Hays, 2008). This research presents a servant teaching model. However, it is important to note that this model has not been empirically tested, nor is it based on any empirical evidence generated by the research. Furthermore, Mertell and Brill (2015) believe that the values of servant leadership would be beneficial for leaders in healthcare, but again fail to provide empirical evidence to confirm their recommendations. It can therefore be said that with regards to the values within servant leadership, although it is an important area of the research, it is one which is thus far lacking in empirical research.

2.16.3 LITERATURE REVIEWS

A large amount of the research generated by the systematic literature review is concerned with reviewing the literature surrounding servant leadership (Bowman, 2010; Bradley, 1999; VanMeter et al., 2016; Crippen, 2014; Eva et al., 1996; Mittal and Dorfman, 2012; Parris and Peachey, 2013; Polleys, 2002; Sendjaya and Sarros, 2002; Simmons and Branch, 2015; Spears, 1996; Yigirt and Bozkurt, 2017). Please see below table for further details:

TABLE 2.6 LITERATURE REVIEWS

Author(s)	Article Title
Bowman (2011)	Teacher as servant leader.
Bradley (1999)	Servant leadership: a critique of Robert Greenleaf's concept of leadership.
Crippen (2004)	Pioneer women in Manitoba: Evidence of servant-leadership.
Eva et al. (1996)	Servant leadership: a systematic review and call for future research.
Mittal and Dorfman (2012)	Servant leadership across cultures.
Parris and Peachey (2013)	A systematic literature review of servant leadership theory in organizational contexts.
Sendjaya and Sarros (2002)	Servant leadership: Its origin, development and application in organizations.
Spears (1996)	Reflections on Robert K Greenleaf and servant leadership.
VanMeter et al. (2016)	In search of clarity on servant leadership: domain specification and reconceptualization.

Winston and Ryan (2008)	Servant leadership as a humane orientation: using the GLOBE study construct of humane orientation to show that servant leadership is more global than Western.
Yigirt and Bozkurt (2017)	A content analysis of servant leadership studies.

The majority of the literature reviews included in the review were concerned with examining how servant leadership has been continuously developed and advanced (VanMeter et al., 2016; Sendjaya and Sarros, 2002; Yigirt and Bozkurt, 2017).

VanMeter et al. (2016) uses literature to identify where servant leadership should be proceeding, in terms of future research. The research of Yigirt and Bozkurt (2017) includes research conducted within a period of 16 years. This could have resulted in the exclusion of large volumes of research conducted out with this selected period. The research of Crippen (2004) discusses the use of servant leadership within an educational setting, but it is limited to the area of Manitoba.

A further two literature review articles aimed to examine Greenleaf's seminal works concluding with both critiques and recommendations (Bradley, 1999; Spears, 1996). Yet, both these articles could benefit from the inclusion of further seminal works to make robust conclusions and comparisons.

Furthermore, Winston and Ryan's (2008) study was concerned with the application of the findings of the GLOBE studies culture literature to highlight the similarities of servant leadership globally. However, it should be noted that this study was not validated empirically. It is not clear why this research chose to include or exclude the literature that it does. Sendjaya and Sarros (2002) use the literature to highlight how servant leadership is beneficial to organisational performance yet fails to validate these claims with empirical evidence.

Two of the literature reviews were conducted systematically (Eva et al., 1996; Parris and Peachey, 2013). However, both reviews fail to include the search strings used in

their research protocols. Additionally, Eva et al. (1996) research failed to include inclusion/exclusion criteria. Furthermore, in the research of Parris and Peachey (2013), the authors used databases available through their university libraries, but they do not seem to include any of their major business databases widely trusted within academia. Overall, both systematic literature reviews could benefit from more rigorous review protocols.

2.16.4 BEHAVIOUR

An additional theme which emerged from the literature was the behaviour of servant leaders (Beazley and Gemmill, 2006; Cerit, 2009; Sendjaya et al., 2008; Sturm, 2008; Taylor et al., 2007; Van Dierendonck and Patterson, 2014; Winston and Fields, 2015). (See Table 4.5.)

TABLE 2.6 BEHAVIOUR

Author(s)	Title of Article
Beazley and Gemmill (2006)	Spirituality and servant leader behaviour.
Cerit (2009)	The effects of servant leadership behaviours of school principals on teachers' job satisfaction.
Sendjaya et al. (2008)	Defining and measuring servant leadership behaviour in organizations.
Sturm (2008)	Principles of servant-leadership in community health nursing.
Taylor et al. (2007)	Examination of leadership practices of principals identified as servant leaders.

Van Dierendonck and Patterson (2014)	Compassionate love as a cornerstone of servant leadership: an integration of previous theorizing and research.
Winston and Fields (2015)	Seeking and measuring the essential behaviours of servant leadership.

Four main behaviours of servant leaders became apparent across these seven articles. The first of these was stewardship (Beazley and Gemmill, 2006; Sturm, 2008). Despite the empirical validation of the research of Beazley and Gemmill (2006) it should be noted that the research was only conducted in one Texan organisation, making the results limited. Furthermore, Sturm (2008) research was not empirically validated at all.

The second behaviour of a servant leader identified was the enabling of followers (Cerit, 2009; Taylor et al., 2007; Sendjaya et al. 2008; Winston and Fields; 2015). However, research in this area is again, limited. Cerit (2009) research is focused primarily on Turkish primary schools, meaning the results are not generalisable. Taylor et al. (2007) research examines the practices of principals who were identified as servant leaders. However, it fails to consider the principals' own perceptions of their leadership, simply focusing on the teacher's perceptions which could result in participant bias. Additionally, Sendjaya et al. (2008) research was conducted solely in Australia and could therefore benefit from wider geographical validation. It is also important to note that Winston and Fields (2015) yielded results solely from one university, therefore calling in to question the wider applicability of their results.

Thirdly, influencing followers was identified as a behaviour of servant leaders (Taylor et al, 2007; Sendjaya et al., 2008). However, it has been previously mentioned that there is a lack of geographical validation in Sendjaya et al. (2008) and the possibility of participant bias in the research of Taylor et al. (2007).

The final prominent behaviour identified was spiritual support (Beazley and Gemmil, 2015; Sendjaya et al., 2008; Sturm, 2008). Yet it should be pointed out that spirituality is a difficult concept to measure and conceptualise.

2.16.5 PERFORMANCE

The most saturated area of the research was the impact of servant leadership on performance (Al-Mahdy et al., 2016; Amah, 2018; Barbuto et al., 2014; Barbuto and Gifford, 2010; Rodríguez-Carvajal et al., 2018; Crippen, 2017; Dennis and Bocarnea, 2005; Hale and Fields, 2007; Han et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2017; Mehjeirkouni, 2018; Rieke et al., 2008; Rodriguez-Carvajal et al., 2014; Stoten, 1987; Sousa and van Dierendonck, 2014; Xu et al., 2015). Please see Table 4.6 for further details of the research concerned with performance.

TABLE 2.7 PERFORMANCE

<p>Al-Mahdy et al. (2016)</p>	<p>Perceptions of school principals' servant leadership and theory teachers job satisfaction in Oman.</p>
<p>Amah (2018)</p>	<p>Determining the antecedents and outcomes of servant leadership.</p>

Author(s)	Title of Article
Awan et al. (2012)	The effective leadership style in NGO's: impact of servant leadership style on employee's work performance and mediation effect of work motivation.
Barbuto and Gifford (2010)	Examining gender differences of servant leadership: an analysis of the agentic and communal properties of servant leadership questionnaire.
Barbuto et al. (2014)	An examination of emotional intelligence as an antecedent of servant leadership.
Beck (2014)	Antecedents of servant leadership.
Black (2010)	Correlational analysis of servant leadership and school climate.
Bobbio et al. (2012)	Servant leadership in Italy and its relation to organizational variables.
Carter and Baghurst (2014)	The influence of servant leadership on restaurant employee engagement.
Cerit (2010)	The effects of servant leadership on teachers' organizational commitment in primary schools in Turkey.
Chan and Mak (2014)	The impact of servant leadership on subordinates' organizational tenure on trust in leader and attitudes.

Charles (2015)	Effects of servant leadership on satisfaction with leaders: inclusion of situational variables.
Chen et al. (2016)	An identification perspective of servant leadership's effects.
Chughta (2017)	Examining the effects of servant leadership on life satisfaction.
Chung et al. (2010)	Servant leadership and procedural justice in the U.S. National Park Service: the antecedents of job satisfaction.
Crippen (2017)	A case study of servant leadership in the NHL.
Dennis and Bocarnea (2005)	A factor analysis of Page and Wong servant leadership instrument.
Ebener and O'Connell (2010)	How might servant leadership work?
Farrington and Lillah (2018)	Servant leadership and job satisfaction within private healthcare practices.
Gunnarsdottir (2014)	Is servant leadership useful for sustainable Nordic health care?
Hale and Fields (2007)	Exploring servant leadership across cultures: a study of followers in Ghana and the USA.
Han et al. (2010)	Servant leadership in the people's republic of China: a case study of the public sector.

Hunter et al. (2013)	Servant leaders inspire servant followers: antecedents and outcomes for employees and the organization.
Jaramillo et al. (2009)	Examining the impact of servant leadership on sales force performance.
Jit et al. (2017)	Healing a broken spirit: role of servant leadership.
Joseph and Winston (2005)	A correlation of servant leadership, leader trust and organizational trust.
Kashyap and Rangnekar (2009)	Servant leadership, employer brand perception, trust in leaders and turnover intentions: examining the impact of servant leadership on salespersons turnover intention.
Koyuncu et al. (2014)	Servant leadership and perceptions of service quality provided by front-line service workers in hotels in Turkey: achieving competitive advantage.
Li et al. (2018)	How and when servant leadership enhances life satisfaction.
Liden et al. (2013)	Servant leadership and serving culture: influence on individual and unit performance.
Liu (2017)	Just the servant: an intersectional critique of servant leadership.

Mayer et al. (2008)	Do servant-leaders help satisfy follower needs? An organizational justice perspective.
McCann et al. (2014)	Servant leadership, employee satisfaction, and organizational performance in rural community hospitals.
McNeff and Irving (2017)	Job satisfaction and the priority of valuing people.
Mehjeirkouni (2018)	Insights on practicing of servant leadership in the events sector.
Ozyilmaz and Cicek (2015)	How does servant leadership affect employee attitudes, behaviours and psychological climates in a for-profit organizational contact?
Palumbo (2016)	Challenging servant leadership in the non-profit sector the side effects of servant leadership.
Reinke(2004)	Service before self: towards a theory of servant-leadership.
Rieke et al. (2008)	Servant leadership in sport a new paradigm for effective coach behaviour.
Rodriguez-Carvajal et al. (2014)	Leading people positively: cross-cultural validation of the servant leadership survey.

Rodríguez-Carvajal et al. (2018)	Servant leadership and goal attainment through meaningful life and vitality: a diary study.
Sendjaya and Pekertie (2010)	Servant leadership as antecedent of trust in organizations.
Shim et al. (2016)	Public servant leadership: myth or powerful reality.
Sihombing et al. (2018)	The effect of servant leadership on rewards, organizational culture and its implication for employee's performance.
Song et al. (2015)	Servant leadership and team performance: the mediating role of knowledge-sharing climate.
Sousa and van Dierendonck (2014)	Servant leaders as under estimators: theoretical and practical implications.
Sousa and van Dierendonck (2017)	Servant leadership and engagement in a merge process under high uncertainty.
Stoten (2013)	Servant leadership in English sixth form colleges: what do teachers tell us?
Tang et al. (2016)	Work–family effects of servant leadership: the roles of emotional exhaustion and personal learning.

Winston (2004)	Servant leadership at Heritage Bible College: a single case study.
Wong et al. (2016)	Servant leadership for team conflict management, coordination and customer relationships.
Xu et al. (2015)	Measurement invariance of the servant leadership questionnaire across K-12 principal gender.
Yan and Xiao (2016)	Servant leadership and voice behaviour: a cross-level investigation in China.
Yang et al. (2017)	A multilevel study of servant leadership on creativity: the roles of self- efficacy and power distance.

The research shows that servant leadership has an overall positive influence on employee performance. It has been found to positively influence trust in leaders from followers (Beck, 2014; Bobbio et al., 2012; Chan and Mak, 2014; Joseph and Winston, 2005; Kashyap and Rangnekar, 2009; Reinke, 2004; Sendjaya and Pekertie, 2010; Shim et al., 2016).

Additionally, servant leadership been studied with regard to employee job performance at length. Sihombing et al. (2018) found that servant leadership had no impact on employee job performance. However, it is important to note that this research was only conducted in one bank in Indonesia, it has not been validated across organisations nor globally. Furthermore, many other scholars have verified that servant leadership does indeed impact positively on employee job performance (Awan et al., 2012; Jaramillo et al., 2009; Liden et al., 2015; Song et al., 2015).

Servant leadership has been found to positively impact employee job satisfaction. This has been found within numerous different organisational environments, for example; within healthcare, family run organisations, national parks and education (Al-Mahdy et al., 2016; Charles, 2015; Chung et al., 2010; Farrington and Lilan, 2018; Gunnarsdottir, 2014; Mayer et al., 2008; McCann, 2014; McNeff and Irving, 2017).

Servant leadership has also been found to impact positively on the climate within the workplace, overwhelmingly being found to provide a positive working climate within organisations (Black, 2010; Jit et al., 2017; Liden, 2015; Ozyilmaz and Cicek, 2015).

Whilst the aforementioned elements of performance are the most prominently discussed with regards to servant leadership, there are many other aspects of work performance discussed within the literature. For example; work family commitment (Tang et al., 2016); team conflict management (Wong et al., 2016); voice behaviour (Yan and Xiao, 2016); life satisfaction (Chen et al., 2016; Ebener and O'Connell, 2010); organisational commitment (Cerit, 2016; Palumbo, 2016), employee creativity (Yang et al., 2016), customer service (Hunter et al., 2013; Wong et al., 2016) and employee engagement (Carter and Baghurst, 2014).

Overall, the literature indicates that servant leadership impacts positively on numerous facets of organisational and employee performance and across different organisations.

2.16.6 THEORETICAL

A number of articles emerged within the systematic literature review which aimed to present theoretical work concerning servant leadership; for example, in the way of frameworks and measurement instruments (Dennis and Winston, 2003; Irving and

Longbotham, 2007, Liden et al., 2015; Liu et al., 2015; Pekertie and Sendjaya, 2010; Polleys, 2002, Punnachet,2009; Rai and Prakesh, 2012; Savel and Munro, 2017). Please see below Table 4.6 for further information:

TABLE 2.8 THEORETICAL

Author(s)	Title of Article
Barbuto and Wheeler (2006)	Scale development and construct clarification of servant leadership.
Buchen (1998)	Servant leadership: a model for future faculty and future institutions.
Burton and Peachey (2013)	The call for servant leadership in intercollegiate athletics.
Certosimo (2009)	The servant leader: a higher calling for dental professionals.
Dannhauser and Boshoff (2007)	Structural equivalence of the Barbuto and Wheeler (2006) servant leadership questionnaire on North American and South African samples.
Dennis and Winston (2003)	A factor analysis of Page and Wong servant leadership instrument.
Farling et al. (1999)	Servant leadership: setting the stage for empirical research.
Garber et al. (2009)	Attitudes towards collaboration and servant leadership among nurses, physicians and residents.

Irving and Longbotham (2007)	Team effectiveness and six essential servant leadership themes: a regression model based on items in the organizational leadership assessment.
Lanctot and Irving (2010)	Character and leadership: situating servant leadership in a proposed virtues framework.
Liden et al. (2015)	Servant leadership: validation of a short form of the SL-28.
Liu et al. (2015)	From the West to the East: validating servant leadership in the Chinese public sector.
Pekertie and Sendjaya (2010)	Exploring servant leadership across cultures: comparative study in Australia and Indonesia.
Polleys (2002)	One University's response to the anti-leadership vaccine: developing servant leaders.
Punnachet (2009)	Catholic servant leadership in education: going beyond the secular paradigm.
Rai and Prakash (2012)	A relational perspective to knowledge creation: role of servant leadership.
Reed et al. (2011)	A new scale to measure executive servant leadership: development, analysis and implications for research.

Robinson et al. (2018)	Servant leadership in sport: a review, synthesis, and applications for sport management classrooms.
Russell and Stone (2002)	A review of servant leadership attributes: developing a practical model.
Savel and Munro (2017)	Servant leadership: the primacy of service.
Sendjaya and Cooper (2011)	Servant leadership behaviour scale: a hierarchical model and test of construct validity.
Simmons and Branch (2015)	Have you paid your rent? Servant leadership in correctional education.
van Dierendonck and Nuijten (2011)	The servant leadership survey: development and validation of a multidimensional measure.
Van Dierendonck et al. (2017)	The cross-cultural invariance of the servant leadership survey: a comparative study across eight countries.

Numerous scales and measuring instruments were found to exist within the research in the review, which were concerned with measuring servant leadership (Barbuto and Wheeler, 2006; Dannhauser and Boshoff, 2007; Reed et al., 2011; Sendjaya and Cooper, 2011; van Dierendonck and Nuijten, 2011). van Dierendonck and Nuijten (2011) developed a scale which measured eight dimensions of servant leadership and originally conducted empirical evidence within the United Kingdom and the Netherlands. The scale was then further tested by van Dierendonck et al. (2017) across eight different countries. However, it should be highlighted that these eight countries were all western and developed, with the majority European. It could

therefore be debatable as to the scale's applicability on a wider scale, out with western countries.

Barbuto and Wheeler (2006) also developed a scale to measure the characteristics of servant leadership. Whilst this scale was further tested by Dannhauser and Boshoff (2007) in the North America and South Africa context, it could still benefit from further global testing. Reed et al. (2011) developed a scale to measure the characteristics of servant leaders, however this research was only carried out in a single college in Florida, and not in fact on any executive servant leader.

Additionally, Sendjaya and Cooper (2011) developed the servant leader behaviour scale. Yet this has only been tested in two not for profit organisations within Australia, and it cannot be adjudged to be universally applicable.

As previously mentioned, much of the research included within this review has presented frameworks, aiming to outline the concept of servant leadership (Buchen, 1998; Garber et al., 2009; Farling et al., 1999; Lanctot and Irving, 2010; Rai and Prakesh, 2012; Russell and Stone, 2002). Russell and Stone (2002), Lanctot and Irving, (2010) and Buchen (1998) developed frameworks of servant leadership based on characteristics. However, it is important to note that none of these frameworks were proposed based on empirical findings. Additionally, Garber et al. (2009) presented a framework of servant leadership to be used by hospital and healthcare leaders. Whilst this research was empirically tested, it was conducted in a south-eastern American healthcare system, which means it may not be applicable in every type of health care organisation. Farling et al. (1999) presents a model of servant leadership based on behaviour, but again, this framework is not empirically tested.

Further frameworks of servant leadership have been developed for its use within correctional facilities (Simmons and Branch, 2015); dentistry (Certosimo, 2009); sport (Burton and Peachey, 2013; Robinson, 2018) and teaching (Pekertie and Sendjaya, 2010). However, it is important to note that none of the aforementioned frameworks were based upon empirical research.

2.16.7 CHARACTERISTICS

A further theme which emerged within the literature was that of characteristics (Spears, 2010; van Dierendonck, 2010; Wilson, 1999). (See Table 4.7)

TABLE 2.7 CHARACTERISTICS

Author(s)	Title of Article
Spears (2010)	Character and servant leadership: ten characteristics of effective, caring leaders.
van Dierendonck (2010)	Servant leadership: a review and synthesis
Wilson (1999)	Servant leadership

A commitment to the development of people was agreed throughout the literature as one of the most important characteristics of servant leadership (Spears, 2010; van Dierendonck, 2010; Wilson, 1999).

It was also unanimously agreed that servant leaders should all demonstrate stewardship, promote empathy/acceptance and direction (Spears, 2010; Van Dierendonck, 2010; Wilson, 1999). However, it is important to note that there is a lack of empirical evidence in any of the research which is concerned with characteristics.

Therefore, to answer review question one, the themes in the servant leadership literature are values, literature reviews, behaviour, theoretical, performance and characteristics.

2.17 GAPS IN THE RESEARCH

2.17.1 GAPS IN THE LITERATURE

As demonstrated within the systematic literature review, significant gaps exist within the research surrounding servant leadership. Particularly prominent gaps can be found in the literature surrounding skills and SMEs, which have been given the least academic focus. Gaps also emerge surrounding both the evidence and theoretical literature. They will now be explored within this section.

2.17.2 THEORY BASED GAPS

The theory surrounding servant leadership is sparse, with few frameworks in existence. Whilst frameworks are presented, they are largely concerned with the implementation of servant leadership within specific sectors e.g. healthcare, nursing, education etc. (Baldimir and Hood, 2016; Davis, 2017; Farling, Stone and Winston, 1999; Greenleaf, 1998; Greenleaf, 1970; Harris and Hockaday, 2017; Jackson, 2008; Mittal and Dorfman, 2017; Page and Wong, 2000; Reed et al., 2011).

However, the following gaps are present within the servant leadership literature:

- There is no framework concerning the implementation of servant leadership within SMEs.

Whilst some research has looked at servant leadership and SMEs, it remains largely lacking in a theoretical construct. This research aims to address this gap in knowledge by presenting a framework, which unlike many of those in existence will be verified by empirical data. This will ensure its validity and robustness for implementing servant leadership within SMEs.

- There is no framework concerning servant leadership skills within SMEs

There have been many theoretical studies that have explored the relationship of servant leadership with regards to behaviour, traits and characteristics (Anderson, 2009; Austell, 2009; Greenleaf, 1970; Lanctot and Irving, 2010; Lehrke and Sowden, 2017; Russell, 2001; Russell and Stone, 2002; Spears, 2010). However, little theoretical research examines servant leadership and skills. O'Sherman (2019) looks at emotional intelligence and only one theoretical study exists which looks at the skills necessary for servant leadership (Bottum and Lenz, 1998), however this study lacks empirical evidence.

- There is no framework concerning the relationship between servant leadership skills and organisational impact.

Whilst numerous studies have explored servant leadership's impact on organisations, as of yet no framework has been developed which shows the relationship between organisational impact and skills (Al-Mahdy et al., 2016; Amah, 2018; Barbuto et al., 2014; Barbuto and Gifford, 2010; Rodríguez-Carvajal et al., 2018; Crippen, 2017; Dennis and Bocarnea, 2005; Hale and Fields, 2007; Han et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2017; Mehjeirkouni, 2018; Rieke et al., 2008; Rodriguez-Carvajal et al., 2014; Stoten, 1987; Sousa and van Dierendonck, 2014; Xu et al., 2015). This will therefore be presented within this research.

Overall, this research will provide an empirical study of skills within servant leadership, in order to develop an empirical based framework, which as of yet remains non-existent.

- There is no comprehensive definition of servant leadership

Parris and Peachey (2013) highlighted the theoretical disunity within servant leadership when they examined the different measurement instruments which exist within the field. This research highlighted the issue of multiple definitions and construct confusion within servant leadership (Parris and Peachey, 2013). This

research therefore aims to rectify the lack of understanding of servant leadership by providing a clear and concise definition of the concept. This will allow both practitioners and researchers to develop a better understanding and awareness of the concept of servant leadership.

2.17.3 EMPIRICAL BASED

As discussed within the literature review, there are some empirical studies which exist in relation to servant leadership. Empirical studies have explored the concepts of behaviours, characteristics, traits and values within servant leadership, and have examined the concepts in their entirety (Beck, 2014; Noland and Richards, 2015; Van Dierendonck and Nujiten, 2011; Washington, 2006). However, the following gaps are present within the servant leadership literature:

- A lack of empirical exploration of all skills necessary for servant leadership

Within the literature surrounding skills in servant leadership the empirical research focuses only on one skill, rather than a plethora. For example, the three main skills which are focused on within the literature are; trust, building trust and emotional intelligence, with the majority of the research focusing on emotional intelligence (Barbuto et al., 2014; Mukanoweshuro, 2016; Pressis et al., 2015; Shamshad, 2016). However, this research aims to look at skills as a whole, rather than focusing on one skill in particular. This will present a broad overview of the skills necessary within servant leadership.

- Lack of exploration of employee perceptions of servant leadership skills

No empirical research yet exists which explores employees' perspectives of the skills necessary within servant leadership.

- The geographical location of SME studies

Whilst empirical studies have been conducted within SMEs, they have all been carried out within the North American context (Claxton, 2014; McNeff and Irving, 2017; Van Winkle et al., 2014). This research will therefore address the gap which exists concerning servant leadership within the European, and more specifically Scottish context. Additionally, no research exists which empirically examines servant leadership skills within SMEs in Scotland, which is where this research will contribute to the knowledge.

2.17.4 METHODOLOGY BASED GAPS

- Lack of substantial qualitative research on servant leadership and SMEs

Whilst McNeff and Irving (2017) conducted interviews within their research, they carried out what has been described as 'personal interviews' and it is not made clear as to what exactly these interviews consist of. Therefore, due to the vagueness of the methodology provided it is debatable as to how valid the interview process was. Furthermore, McNeff conducted the interviews within a company he owns, interviewing his own employees. This could easily result in both participant and interviewer bias, again raising questions as to the validity of the data gathered.

Claxton (2014) also interviewed participants within his research on servant leadership and SMEs. However, Claxton's research consisted of a very small number of participants, who were all situated within North America. Additionally, Claxton looked at what makes employees feel valued within SMEs rather than the skills necessary for servant leadership within SMEs. Therefore, this research will fill the methodological based gap of conducting qualitative research which focuses on the skills necessary for servant leadership within SMEs.

The basis of servant leadership is empowering others and ensuring that the long-term welfare of the followers comes first (Harrison, 2018). It is therefore important, that in a world which has faced many leadership crises, a new, more ethical

approach to leadership is considered, in the form of servant leadership. It has been stated that servant leadership has witnessed an “explosion of unparalleled interest” throughout the last decade (Spears and Lawrence, 2002, p.1). This is clearly shown through the vast literature which has emerged surrounding and covering the concept. Therefore, it is important to explore the concept of servant leadership further as a relevant and contemporary approach to leadership and as an alternative to the existent, often authoritarian, approaches. The framework which this research will therefore proceed to develop can be used to introduce servant leadership to SMEs, build upon the skills of existing servant leaders, and to inform those wishing to research the area.

This systematic literature review has examined the six categories which emerge most frequently within the literature: values, literature reviews, behaviour, theoretical, performance and characteristics. From this, both the empirical and theoretical research has been explored to create a clear and systematic overview of servant leadership. It has also become clear through the SLR that both skills and servant leadership are lacking in empirical research. Furthermore, the existing research is saturated with a quantitative approach. This research will proceed to address this by conducting qualitative research to determine the skills necessary for servant leadership within SMEs.

By answering the questions of this research and addressing its objectives and aims this research will contribute to the substantial gaps which exist within the literature surrounding servant leadership and skills, the impact of servant leadership on organisations and a comprehensive definition of servant leadership.

2.18 RESEARCH QUESTIONS:

The systematic literature review has determined that there is a gap with regards to skills in the servant leadership knowledge. The gaps found within a systematic literature review can then in turn be used to formulate research questions for the research to address (Arksey and Omalley, 2005). The research questions aim to address the research problem, which the SLR has determined to be skills knowledge

and a lack of a comprehensive definition of servant leadership (Booth et al., 1995). The research, which is conducted should then address the questions, and in turn, the research problem. As previously mentioned, the research questions emerge from a knowledge deficit within the field (Hulley et al. 2007). The SLR has therefore determined that the questions for this research should pertain to skills and a definition of servant leadership. It is necessary to examine these aspects because, as previously mentioned, there is no definition of servant leadership and skills are necessary for effective leadership (Harrison, 2018). The research questions for this study were therefore identified as the result of the literature reviews conducted and are as follows:

- *How can servant leadership be defined?*
- *What are the most prominent skills for servant leaders within SMEs?*
- *What is the organisational impact of servant leader's skills' on SMEs?*

2.19 CONCLUSION

This chapter has explored the various prominent eras to leadership as determined by Clark and Harrison (2018). It also discussed the relevant leadership approaches within each era. Furthermore, in addition to Clark and Harrison's (2018) determined leadership eras, this research also added a serving era, which consist of servant leadership.

This chapter also provided a systematic literature review which has shown the trends and development of the research concerning servant leadership. It has examined how the literature is made up, and indeed what the literature consists of. It has also highlighted the gaps in the research making recommendations as to how these gaps can be addressed. It has furthermore identified research questions through determining gaps in the existing knowledge.

The research will now proceed in the next chapter to provide a methodology, which will discuss the methods used to gather the primary data within this research.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

This chapter aims to explore the methodology which will be undertaken within this research process and how it is influenced by the philosophy of this research.

However, before one can comprehend the undertaking of a methodology, one must initially understand the concept of research. Research is the systematic work which is undertaken to contribute to knowledge (OECD, 2015). It is the human activity of embarking on an intellectual pursuit in order to discover something new, or to contribute to existing knowledge (Srivastava and Rego, 2013). The research in question in this instance is an original research, which is concerned with producing entirely new knowledge, rather than reaffirming or finding a new method of presenting existing knowledge (Rozakis, 2007). Essentially, the main purpose of research is the generation of knowledge.

A methodology consists of the theory and analysis which have influenced and informed how the research is carried out (Pathak, 2008). In essence, the methodology is a research design which is tailored to fit the phenomenon being investigated (Jonker and Pennick, 2010). It entails the theoretical underpinnings used within research, thus presenting a rationale as to why particular methods or practices have been applied to a specific phenomenon (Kallet, 2004).

A methodology is important, to establish the research's reliability; explain how the data was obtained, and in turn, how it was interpreted (Jonket and Pennick, 2010). By providing a rationale for the methodology one is able to provide justification as to why decisions were made. Overall, the methodology maps out the path that the research will take and determines its systematic direction. Applying the correct methodology to research is essential to ensure that the results produced are scientific and reliable, and to protect the validity of the study as a whole.

This methodology has been influenced by the research's overall aim which is to examine servant leadership within SMEs and to determine the necessary skills for success.

This research aims to answer the three following questions:

- *How can servant leadership be defined?*
- *What are the most prominent skills for servant leaders within SMEs?*
- *What is the organisational impact of servant leader's skills' on SMEs?*

As previously stated, this chapter will proceed to outline the methodology used within the research. To do this, it will begin by examining the approach to research which was undertaken. Exploration of the research approach is essential, as it influences the entirety of the methodology. The chapter will then discuss the paradigm undertaken before proceeding to explore the research philosophy used. Then a detailed account of the research process and strategy will be given. It will look at the methods used within the research, and how the data was then analysed. It will

further examine the quality criteria used by this research, and the ethical implications which were considered. This will then allow the chapter to reach a comprehensive and informed conclusion regarding the research undertaken.

3.1 RESEARCH APPROACH

There are generally considered to be three main approaches to research. These are inductive, deductive and abductive. (Bryman and Bell, 2007; Creswell, 2014). These will now be further discussed, with an explanation of each of these approaches provided. This will allow for a justification of the approach which was chosen.

3.1.1 DEDUCTIVE APPROACH

The deductive approach is commonly used when the researcher wishes to test an already informed theory or hypothesis (Thompson et al., 2014). Subsequently, it is generally the case that the research is designed around either the falsification or verification of the hypothesis (Strauss and Corbin, 1998). It has been highlighted that deductive reasoning is the only approach which allows one to arrive at a conclusion with the highest level of certainty (Strauss and Corbin, 1998). However, it is important to note that by focusing on a specific hypothesis one can limit the scope of the research. This can also lead to the exclusion of valuable information which is not directly related to the proposed hypothesis. As this research does not have a hypothesis it was determined that the deductive approach would not be suitable.

3.1.2 ABDUCTIVE APPROACH

Abductive reasoning begins with an observation then seeks to find the likeliest explanation for this. Unlike deductive reasoning, which aims for certainty, abductive reasoning seeks to find the best explanation for a particular experience or phenomenon (Sober, 2013). However, it can be plagued by the same limitations as deductive reasoning; in that it focuses solely on the experience which it is aiming to examine. Furthermore, unlike deductive reasoning, abductive reasoning does not

provide a verification of the research conclusions it draws, it simply provides the best possible explanation (Sober, 2013). Therefore, with abductive reasoning the conclusions drawn are not finite nor definite, making it inappropriate for this research.

3.1.3 INDUCTIVE APPROACH

Inductive reasoning uses detailed and pre-informed knowledge to inform theories and concepts (Neuman, 2014). It links the existing literature to the data gathered to generate knowledge (Thomas, 2006). As this research does not have an existing hypothesis, nor has any prior observation been conducted, it will be adopting an inductive approach. This research will also be free of any prior conceptions, due to the lack of literature and research which exists concerning the skills necessary for servant leadership. This will allow it to develop the framework of the skills necessary for servant leadership, without the influence or bias of previous works.

It will be informed by the systematic literature review conducted in chapter two, thus allowing it to generate a relevant interview protocol. Furthermore, it is working with human participants, where existing preconceptions or hypotheses are not always useful, due to the unpredictability of the nature of such social research. As a result of this, the adoption of inductive reasoning is beneficial to this research. A phenomenon with a social element is often difficult to measure and summarise, thus meaning the broad nature of inductive research is most applicable. Overall, the reasons for adopting an inductive approach to research are best summarised in the following statement:

“The human reason discovers new relations between things not by deduction, but by that unpredictable blend of speculation and insight... induction, which—like other forms of imagination—cannot be formalized”

(Bronowski, 1967 in Valladeres, 2005 p. 22)

For further detail on the three approaches to research please see Figure 3.1. below:

FIGURE 3.1 RESEARCH APPROACHES

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Original figure can be found in Nicholls, D. (2009). Qualitative Research: Part Three - Methods. *International Journal of Therapy and Rehabilitation*. 16 (12), pp. 638-647.

(Adapted from Nicholls, 2009)

3.2 RESEARCH PARADIGM

The paradigm is essentially the framework which influences the way in which knowledge is gathered and interpreted within the research process (Bogdan and Biklen, 1998; Mertens, 2005). It is essential for one to decide upon a research paradigm to justify the overall research design and the choices made within the methodology (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). The term paradigm can be defined as a “loose collection of logically related assumptions, concepts or propositions that orient thinking and research” (Bogdan and Biklen, 1998, p.22). This chapter will now proceed to explore the paradigm employed by this research, providing justifications.

There are numerous paradigms which can be used within research, for example: critical, transformative, pragmatism, interpretivist, emancipatory, constructivist, deconstructivist and positivist (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). However, the paradigms most commonly used in research are positivist, interpretivist, transformative and pragmatic (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). These will now be explored further to provide justification for the paradigm chosen by this research.

3.2.1 POSITIVIST PARADIGM

A positivist paradigm is concerned with the scientific method of gathering and analysing data (Matens, 2005). It aims to test theories or find explanations for experiences. It aims to do this via the method of observation and measurement to control and predict the forces we are surrounded by (O'Leary, 2004). Positivists, or post positivists as they became known after World War II, believe that research is influenced by a plethora of already developed theories, including and out with the one already being tested (Cook and Campbell, 1979). Positivism is the essential belief that reality is objective and can be observed without interference (Simon and Levin, 1998). In essence, it is concerned with the rules and precise nature of events (Howell, 2013). As this research is concerned with human participants, a positivist paradigm is not ideal due to its specific nature. It would be difficult if not unachievable to attempt to measure the skills of servant leaders scientifically and exactly.

Positivist research is most aligned with quantitative methods of analysing and collecting data (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). Therefore, this paradigm is not useful for this study as it is concerned with gathering data qualitatively. In addition, this research has no preconceived theories or experiences which it wishes to explore.

3.2.2 TRANSFORMATIVE PARADIGM

Transformative research emerged because of dissatisfaction with a lack of inclusive perspective behind the existing dominant paradigms (Matens, 2005). There was concern that the pre-existing and more popularised paradigms were largely male dominated and lacked racial diversity and inclusion (Matens, 2005). Therefore, transformative researchers believe that research should be intertwined with politics and indeed should be shaped by a political agenda (Creswell, 2014). It often aims to provide evidence to inform or promote reform for the groups involved (Creswell, 2014). A mixed methods approach is generally considered useful for those undertaking transformative research (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2009). This research is

not informed nor influenced by any political or societal issues, nor is it campaigning for any type of reform. Therefore, this research has chosen not to adopt a transformative paradigm.

3.2.3 PRAGMATIC PARADIGM

A pragmatic paradigm is concerned with the 'what and why' of research and is not fully committed to a singular philosophy or reality (Mackenzie and Knipe, 2006). The pragmatic paradigm places the research problem at the centre of the research and frames the research in order to address it, and develop an understanding of the problem (Creswell, 2014).

The pragmatic paradigm is most associated with mixed methods (Somekh and Lewin, 2005). It is therefore unsuitable for this research which wishes to gather data via qualitative means. Additionally, this research is not solely focusing on a research problem per se, thus, the pragmatic paradigm is not suitable for this study.

3.2.4 INTERPRETIVIST PARADIGM

The interpretivist paradigm evolved from the German philosophical study of hermeneutics, or the study of interpretive understanding (Mertens, 2005). Interpretivism believes that reality is the result of social constructionism and their research focuses on the point of view of the participants of the subject being studied (Creswell, 2014). It doesn't begin with a theory or pattern but generally develops a theory of pattern throughout the research process (Creswell, 2014). This pattern can be found through thematic analysis of the data, which this research will employ in order to analyse the data gathered (Braun and Clark, 2006).

Interpretivist research largely looks at the meanings within the practices of the human participants and their lived experiences (Creswell, 2014). Interpretivists must be able to identify and appreciate the differences in their human participants and find meaning in them (Creswell, 2014). Interpretivism generally focuses on the role of the

observer and how they choose to interpret their reality. In addition, interpretivist research generally operates using qualitative methods, which will be undertaken by this research in terms of semi-structured interviews (Burns, 1997; Silverman, 2000). A true picture of reality can only be formed through the interpretation of data, conducted subjectively and gathered from human participants (Crowther and Lancaster, 2008).

Due to its social constructionist nature, interpretivism is useful when dealing with cross cultural differences within organisations (Dudovskiy, 2015). This research aims to explore a variety of industries and both leaders and employees, thus cross-cultural differences may arise in the research. Furthermore, interpretivist paradigms are useful for the study of leadership, and factors which influence leadership, thus making them appropriate for this research (Dudovskiy, 2015). Furthermore, the interpretivist believes that knowledge is relative in accordance with culture and context (Pizam and Mansfield, 2009). As this research is focusing upon the specific culture of SMEs and the context of Scotland, interpretivism is therefore appropriate in this respect.

This research will therefore adopt an interpretivist paradigm. This is because it is wishing to interpret the data received from the participants to determine the skills necessary for servant leadership. In addition, it wishes to use qualitative research to gather data. Therefore, an interpretivist paradigm is ideal for this research as it aims to generate rather than test theory, and to use entirely qualitative methods in its research gathering process.

3.3 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHY

The research philosophy guides the methodology and is concerned with how new knowledge is generated. At every stage of the research, albeit often subconsciously, assumptions will be made by the researcher (Burrell and Morgan, 1979). Therefore, research philosophies are concerned with the preconceived beliefs and assumptions of those carrying out the research which can influence the generation of knowledge (Saunders et al., 2012). The two main assumptions are concerned with human

knowledge (epistemological assumptions) and the realities that one may encounter throughout the research's philosophy (ontological assumptions) (Saunders et al., 2012). Such assumptions are necessary as they shape how research questions are answered and how the methodological process is carried out (Crotty, 1998).

Ontology refers to the nature of reality and the preconceived assumptions researchers have regarding it (Saunders et al., 2012). It is concerned with the science of being (Marsh et al., 2002). Epistemology is concerned with the study and theory of knowledge (Porter, 2006). It aims to examine the justification and nature of knowledge (Hofer and Pintrich, 1997). (See Table 5.1.)

TABLE 3.1 RESEARCH PHILOSOPHIES

Assumption Type	Types of Questions	Continua with two sets of extremes
Ontology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the nature of reality? • What is the world like? • For example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are organizations like? - What is it like being in organizations? - What is it like being a manager or being managed? 	Objectivism vs. Subjectivism <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real \leftrightarrow Nominal/Decided by convention • External \leftrightarrow Socially Constructed • One true reality (universalism) \leftrightarrow Multiple relativism • Granular (things) \leftrightarrow Flowing (processes) • Order \leftrightarrow Chaos

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(Adapted from Saunders et al., 2009, p. 129)

According to Saunders et al. (2009) there are two ontological approaches: objectivism and subjectivism.

3.3.1 OBJECTIVISM

In its simplest form, objectivism is concerned with “what is” (Crotty, 1998, p.10). Objectivism posits that social entities are in a reality which is external to the influence of social actors (Saunders et al. 2012). Objectivists postulate that by observing overt behaviour, one is able to deduce replicable facts (Diesing, 1966). Objectivism believes in singular truths which exist regardless of the period of time, culture, or any other outside influence. Objectivism is often referred to as ‘common sense’ (Hiller, 2016). However, due to its ‘common sense nature’ objective researchers often do not reflect on their findings (Pascale, 2011). This can leave the findings remaining relatively unexplained (Hiller, 2016). Therefore, an objectivist ontology has been deemed unsuitable for this research.

3.3.2 SUBJECTIVISM

Subjectivism is concerned with the assumptions of the arts and humanities. It asserts that social reality is concerned with the actions and indeed perceptions of social actors (Saunders et al., 2012). In an ontological sense, subjectivism encourages nominalism (Saunders et al., 2012). Subjectivism can often be referred to as social constructionism, which is used for the purpose of this research (Saunders et al., 2012). It is concerned with knowledge which is constructed through interactions with others (McKinley, 2015). Within social constructionism, one can interpret the literature so as to address their research questions (McKinley, 2015). It emphasises the importance of context and culture. Within society, it is concerned with generating knowledge (McMahon, 1997). Social constructionism believes that meaningful

learning occurs most often when people are engaged in social activities (Kim, 2001). This research will therefore be adopting social constructionism as its ontology.

According to Saunders et al. (2012), there are main three epistemological approaches. They are positivism, realism and interpretivism.

3.3.3 POSITIVISM

Positivism is generally the approach taken by the natural scientist (Saunders et al., 2012). Essentially, positivism aims to establish law-like generalisabilities based upon what the researcher has observed (Gill and Johnson, 2010). This research is taken without any preconceived values or feelings of the researcher (Saunders et al., 2012). It is generally conducted based upon a preconceived hypothesis or observation and is concerned with the collection of quantitative data. Due to its rigidity, positivism is often accused of losing rich, valuable information which cannot be quantified scientifically (Saunders et al., 2012). As this research will not be based on any preconceived observations or hypothesis, it is not viable to adopt a positivist epistemology.

3.3.4 REALISM

Realism believes that there is a world out with the reality that we develop within our minds (Crotty, 1998). Similar to positivism, realism is an epistemology which adopts a scientific approach (Saunders et al., 2012). There are two different approaches to realism; direct realism and critical realism (Saunders et al., 2012). Direct realism believes that what we experience is the real world, whereas critical realism believes that what we experience is our interpretation of reality (Saunders et al., 2012). Realism is concerned with quantitative data and is influenced by the researcher's preconceived notions and values. As this research does not have any preconceived notion nor is it aiming to gather quantitative data, it will not be adopting a realism epistemology.

3.3.5 INTERPRETIVIST

The interpretivist epistemology is concerned with conducting research with people, rather than objects (Saunders et al., 2012). It is concerned with phenomenology, or how we interpret the world around us (Saunders et al., 2012). Interpretivists are of the belief that realities can be relative and multiple (Hudson and Ozanne, 1988). Interpretivism captures meaning within human interaction and perceived realities (Black, 2006; Hudson and Ozanne, 1988). It allows for and is open to new knowledge and generates it with the help of its participants. It is of the belief that one cannot have prior knowledge of social realities, and therefore enters research without preconceived notions (Hudson and Ozanne, 1988). An interpretivist epistemology is concerned with human experience (Fossey et al. 2002). As this research aims to examine the lived experiences of servant leaders, an interpretivist paradigm is appropriate. As this research is concerned with people and the phenomenology of servant leadership, it will be adopting an interpretivist philosophy.

In conclusion, the overall philosophy adopted based on the ontology and epistemology is a social constructionist and interpretivist stance.

3.4 RESEARCH PROCESS

This section will now discuss the research process employed. Research processes can be applied to many different types of study and guides the way in which the research will gather data (McNabb, 2008). The research process within social sciences is classified into three categories: explanatory, descriptive and exploratory (Robson, 1993). These three processes will now be explored further.

3.4.1 EXPLANATORY RESEARCH

Explanatory research is largely concerned with the cause and effect of relationships (Yin, 1994). Explanatory research observes and measures change within followers. It aims to provide meaning as well as description (McNabb, 2008). It aims to predict

events as well as building theory (White, 1999). It is generally concerned with quantitative data and aims to gather data through methods of fixed design, meaning it is not applicable to this research.

3.4.2 DESCRIPTIVE RESEARCH

Descriptive research is needed to explain the inner properties and relationships of a particular phenomenon (Huczynski and Buchana, 1991). It is useful for the portrayal of situations, events and people (Robson, 1993). It is descriptive and explains characteristics rather than looking for answers or potential explanations. In essence, a descriptive research design is concerned with examining the 'what' rather than the why and how, which makes it unsuitable for this research (Shields and Rangarajan, 2013).

3.4.3 EXPLORATORY RESEARCH

Exploratory research can be considered the study of a new phenomenon (Yin, 1994). It seeks to ask questions and examine new phenomenon or examine existing phenomenon in a new way. It is essentially useful for conducting research in an area which is underdeveloped (Shields and Rangarajan, 2013). In addition, it is useful for developing a working conceptual hypothesis (Shields and Rangarajan, 2013).

Therefore, this methodology will adopt an exploratory process. As highlighted in chapter two; skills are an underdeveloped area of research within servant leadership. In addition, this research does not have a predetermined hypothesis, thus meaning an exploratory design is the most logical approach for it to undertake.

3.5 RESEARCH METHODS

This section will now explain the research method used for the study. There are two types of research methods: qualitative and quantitative (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

Research which adopts either a quantitative or qualitative approach can be considered empirical. (Punch, 1998). However, qualitative research is not concerned with numbers, whereas quantitative research is (Punch, 1998). (See Table 5.2.)

TABLE 3.2 RESEARCH METHODS

	Qualitative	Quantitative
Conceptual	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concerned with understanding human behaviour from the informant's perspective • Assumes a dynamic and negotiated reality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concerned with discovering facts about social phenomena • Assumes a fixed and measurable reality
Methodological	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data are collected through participant observation and interviews • Data are collected through participant observation and interviews • Data are analysed by themes from descriptions by informants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data are analysed through numerical comparisons and statistical inferences • Data are reported through statistical analyses

(Adapted from Minichello et al. 1990, p.5)

3.5.1 QUANTITATIVE METHODS

Quantitative research generally consists of experiments, controlled observations and questionnaires. It aims to identify and analyse numerical or statistical data. To do this, it generally employs instruments which yield statistical data (Creswell, 2014). Quantitative research tends to be concerned with testing or proving an existing hypothesis through experimental means.

Due to the complexity of human variables, quantitative methods may struggle to control or interpret them, in a way which could be managed by qualitative methods. In addition, the quantitative researcher must be able to control their research so as to determine cause and effect (Burns, 2000). Due to the control, the quantitative researcher needs to exert over the research, it often needs to take place in settings or environments which are not natural (Carr, 1994). This can lead to results which are not valid or generalisable, out with the experimental situation. Additionally, the influence of the preconceived hypothesis may influence or impact on the true results which can be found within the data.

3.5.2 QUALITATIVE METHODS

Qualitative data adopts an interpretive approach to research (Denzin and Lincoln, 1994). Within this form of research, it is generally the case that themes are developed because of the open-ended research which is gathered (Creswell, 2014). It consists of scientific observation which results in data which is not numerical (Babbie, 2014). It is more concerned with definitions, meanings and concepts rather than measurements or the counting of things (Berg and Lune, 2010).

Qualitative research can be conducted in different ways such as interviews, participant observation, focus groups and ethnography. However, it should be noted that qualitative researchers should not be placed under a 'methodological straightjacket' and must be allowed to utilise the methods necessary to conduct their research (Aguinaldo, 2004). Qualitative data can be analysed via content analysis, grounded theory and thematic analysis. This research has chosen to adopt a thematic analysis approach to the data, which will be expanded upon at a later point within this chapter.

This research has chosen to adopt a qualitative method as it is the most applicable for explaining the how and why of human experiences (Given, 2008). It aims to examine the human element of data, rather than the numerical or statistical. As this research is concerned with human participants this is a far more logical approach to adopt than quantitative, which is more concerned with gathering data numerically. Furthermore, it could be argued quantitative research is more precise. It is also the case that qualitative research allows for ambiguities in the data which therefore allows it to present a true reflection of social reality (Burns, 2006).

Social constructionist research has long been associated with qualitative research (Andrews, 2012). As this research is grounded in social constructionist and interpretivist theory qualitative methods are the most appropriate for determining human experience (Fossey et al. 2002).

3.6 TRENDS IN THE RESEARCH

As mentioned within the systematic literature review, the majority of the research concerning servant leadership has been conducted quantitatively. In addition, the most used method of gathering data concerning servant leadership was found to be surveys. In leadership research in general, there tends to be a greater focus upon quantitative research as opposed to qualitative (Stentz et al., 2012). However, there have been concerns within academia that the research concerning servant leadership is lacking due to poor research design and measurement (Eva et al., 2018).

This research therefore aims to differentiate from the status quo and present qualitative research concerning leadership, which is conducted via interviews. However, it is important to note that the viability of using qualitative research within servant leadership has previously been verified See Table 5.3. below for examples:

TABLE 3.3 QUALITATIVE SERVANT LEADERSHIP STUDIES

Author(s)	Name of Article
Carter and Baghurst (2014)	The influence of servant leadership on restaurant employee engagement.
Crippen (2017)	A case study of servant leadership in the NHL.
Liu (2017)	Just the servant: an intersectional critique of servant leadership.
Rodriguez - Caravajal et al. (2018)	Servant leadership and goal attainment through meaningful life and vitality: a diary study.

It is hoped that this will strengthen the existing knowledge concerning servant leadership, and indeed leadership as a whole.

3.7 SAMPLING

Researchers lack both the time and the resources to conduct an analysis of an entire population (Taherdoost, 2016). Therefore, researchers need to select a sample for analysis (Taherdoost, 2016). Thus, in order to generate data, research must have a specific population to be examined (Sekaran and Bargie, 2010). There are two generally accepted approaches to sampling; probability and non-probability (Wisniowski et al., 2020).

3.7.1 PROBABILITY SAMPLING

In probability sampling, a random selection is used to choose participants (Christensen et al., 2020). It is arbitrary and every person in the population has a chance of being included in the sample (Taherdoost, 2016). It is considered costly and time consuming for its level of sampling error (Brown, 2017). It is also often not deemed to be possible or practical.

3.7.2 NON-PROBABILITY SAMPLING

In non-probability or purposive sampling, a selection criterion is used to choose participants (Christensen et al., 2020). Nonprobability can be said to achieve greater accuracy in comparison to probability, as responses in probability sampling can be low (Baker et al., 2013; Wisonowski et al., 2020). Non-probability sampling is employed for in-depth qualitative research which examines complex phenomena (Small, 2009). Nonprobability sampling is carried out until theoretical saturation is reached (Strauss and Corbin, 1990).

This research aims to conduct research with purposive participants due to its examination of a social phenomenon. Therefore, rather than a study of the public, it will include participants who can provide direct insight into the phenomenon being studied. This research conducted 30 interviews in total, 15 of which were with employees of SMEs and 15 with leaders of SMEs. The interview process was conducted until saturation was reached (Strauss and Corbin, 1990). The SMEs were identified in accordance with the Scottish SME directory, provided by the Scottish government. According to the Scottish government there were 345,915 private

sector SMEs operating in Scotland as of March 2018 (Scottish Government, 2018). In order to identify the organisations relevant to the research, organisational criteria were developed based on the purposive sampling strategy. It is as follows:

3.7.3 SME CRITERIA

- The organisation must be based in Scotland
- The organisation must have been established in Scotland
- The organisation must be recognised by the Scottish Government
- The organisation should have continuous growth and profit in order to indicate the potential success of servant leadership on SME performance
- The organisation should have been established for a period of at least five years
- The organisation must have fewer than 250 employees with a turnover not exceeding €50 million, in accordance with the European definition of SMEs (March 2003)

(Adapted from Scottish Government, 2018).

In order to identify participants who, adopt servant leadership, potential participants were contacted beforehand. As of yet there is no widely used instrument to measure servant leadership (Green et al., 2015). Therefore, this research has developed its own criteria based on a series of measurement frameworks used within the influential works in the field (Barbuto and Wheeler, 2006; Chung et al., 2010; Erhart, 2004; Farrington and Lillah, 2018; Linuesa-Langero et al., 2013; McCann et al., 2014; McNeff and Irving, 2017; Wu et al. 2013). It is as follows:

3.7.4 SERVANT LEADERSHIP CRITERIA

- High employee satisfaction, indicated by low turnover rate
- High customer service rating, indicated by reviews and testimonials
- Demonstration of ethical behaviours
- The creation of value for those out with the organisation

In order to present a representative picture of Scotland, the research will examine SMEs from each of the geographical locations in Scotland. The Scottish government defines urban and rural areas in accordance with population and accessibility (Scottish Government, 2018) (Table 5.4). This was chosen so as to provide a clear overview of the entirety of Scotland, rather than just a rural or suburban population. Further information on this can be found in appendix 8.

TABLE 3.4: CLASSIFICATION OF GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATIONS IN SCOTLAND

Type of Area	Number in Settlement
Large Urban Areas	A settlement of 125000 or more
Other Urban Areas	A settlement of 10,000 – 124999
Accessible Small Town	Settlements of 3,000 to 9,999 people and within 30 minutes' drive of a settlement of 10,000 or more.
Remote Small Towns	Settlements of 3,000 to 9,999 people and with a drive time of over 30 minutes to a settlement of 10,000 or more.
Accessible Rural Towns	Areas with a population of less than 3,000 people, and within a 30 minutes' drive time of a settlement of 10,000 or more.

Remote Rural Towns	Areas with a population of less than 3,000 people, and with a drive time of over 30 minutes to a settlement of 10,000 or more.
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(Adapted from Scottish Government, 2016)

Participants were contacted via email or letter to ask for their participation in the study. Some networks were already previously established with leaders and workers in SMEs. However, other participants were contacted in accordance with the aforementioned criteria. Interviews lasted approximately 45 minutes to one hour and were conducted face-to-face.

3.8 MODE OF DATA COLLECTION

There are different ways to gather data when conducting qualitative research. For example, one may use focus groups, ethnography, participant observations or interviews (Barret and Twycross, 2018). This research used interviews to gather the necessary data. Interviews are beneficial for uncovering social phenomenon which could not otherwise be understood via quantitative methods such as surveys (Silverman, 2000). Interviews are useful for this research as it is aimed at addressing the social phenomenon of the skills necessary for servant leadership. Interviews are also useful when there is little already known about the topic in question.

As has been mentioned throughout, there is little known about the skills of a servant leader, thus interviews are necessary to determine this information. The geographical locations of the participants involved in the research means that it is more logical to conduct interviews, rather than to attempt other methods of data collection. Therefore, interviews are the ideal approach to conducting this research.

3.8.1 TYPES OF INTERVIEWS

There are three fundamental types of interviews employed in qualitative research. These are structured, semi-structured and unstructured interviews (Gill et al., 2008). Creswell (2013) suggests that those adopting an interpretivist and social constructionist underpinning should carry out interviews in order to gather data. This is necessary as within an interpretivist paradigm meanings are formed through interactions with others (Creswell, 2013). They will now be further discussed to justify the approach decided upon by this research.

3.8.1.1: STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS

Structured interviews consist of a rigid set of questions from which there is no deviating. In essence, structured interviews can be described as verbally administered questionnaires (Gill et al., 2008). Structured interviews are useful for administering precise questions and for obtaining quick and easy answers. However, there is little scope for expansion upon the answers given by participants and can therefore lead to the omission of information which may be beneficial to the overall research. Thus, they will not be employed within this research.

3.8.1.2 UNSTRUCTURED INTERVIEWS

Unstructured interviews are not informed or influenced by any preconceived theories or information (Bailey, 2008). They have no real prearranged questions or directions (Bailey, 2008). Each question posed by the researcher leads on from the direction taken by the last question. However, such interviews can be time consuming, and due to the lack of structure, can last several hours. Additionally, they can be difficult to manage and veer off topic, thus leading to information, which is not relevant to the research, which the researcher then must discard (Gill et al., 2008). Therefore, unstructured interviews will not be conducted by this research.

3.8.1.3 SEMI STRUCTURED INTERVIEWS

Semi structured interviews consist of an interview protocol which has been influenced by the existing research surrounding the topic. The protocol consists of

key questions which will be covered within the interview (Britten, 1995). The questions used in semi-structured interviews consist of open ended and closed questions, leaving more room for information to be obtained than other types of information (Galletta, 2013). They allow for the interview to explore the more appropriate topics, but also allow the participant to divert and thus divulge more relevant information to the phenomenon (Silverman, 2000).

The research employed this method to gather the data from participants. Due to the social constructionist and interpretivist nature of this research, it is necessary to explore the human element of this research making semi structured interviews an ideal approach to adopt. Additionally, semi-structured interviews allow for the comparison of the answers given by participants. This is necessary within an interpretivist philosophy (Crichton and Kinash, 2008). Furthermore, the research used semi-structured interviews as it aims to triangulate the data gathered from both participants and leaders. Additionally, semi-structured interviews have proved to be an effective method in gathering data in servant leadership research (Parris and Peachey, 2013).

3.6 DEVELOPING AN INTERVIEW SCHEDULE

Within semi-structured interviews, the researcher aims to set up a guide or schedule of the areas they wish to be covered in the interview (Drever, 1995). They aim to prepare this before the research is undertaken, so they have a pre-existing idea of the way in which they would like the interview to progress. To form an interview schedule, one must look at the relevant existing theories in the literature to guide their work.

To develop an interview schedule, this research was influenced by the seminal works on servant leadership by Robert Greenleaf (1970). This work presents a comprehensive overview of the concept of servant leadership and was therefore used to incorporate servant leadership into the interview protocol. Additionally, within leadership, one of the most prominent works on skills was conducted by Katz who proposed that leadership is concerned with skills which can be learned (Katz, 1955). This was used in formulating questions on skills which was beneficial in determining

the framework outlined within this research's aims. Additionally, the work of Mumford et al. (2000) was used to inform the interview protocol, as it is concerned with skills as a function of experience.

According to Galletta (2013) an interview protocol should be divided into three sections. The first of these is "The Opening Segment: Creating Space for a Narrative Grounded in Participant Experience" (Galletta, 2013, p.46). The researcher should therefore begin by expressing their gratitude to the participant for partaking in the study. The principles of consent should be covered again, to ensure that the participant is aware of their ability to withdraw at any time. The questions in this section should be quite general, but still relevant to your area of research.

"The second section is the Middle Section: Questions of Greater Specificity" (Galletta, 2013, p.49). This section should be guided by the literature. The questions within this section should be more relevant to the topic and indeed be searching for more in-depth answers from your participants.

The final section is Concluding segment: Revisiting the Opening Narrative for Important Theoretical Connections and Moving Towards Closure (Galletta, 2013, p. 51). This should return to points that the researcher thinks were not previously explained by or could be expanded upon by the participant. They should again thank the participant and reiterate their ability to withdraw from the interview if they so wish. For a full outline of the interview protocol please see appendices 5 and 6.

3.7 DATA ANALYSIS

This section of the chapter will now provide an overview of how the analysis of the data gathered was conducted. It will explain the step-by-step process before the results of the data analysis are revealed within the findings chapter. There are numerous ways in which qualitative data can be analysed. For example, ethnography, phenomenology, grounded theory and thematic analysis.

3.7.1 ETHNOGRAPHY

Ethnography is concerned with the researchers directly observing participants within certain environments (Sutton and Austin, 2015). However, ethnographic research is time consuming and can be costly. Furthermore, it is concerned with the researchers own view and interpretation of what they witness during the observation, it can therefore consist of bias and opinion, on the researcher's part.

3.7.2 PHENOMONOLGY

Phenomenology is concerned with the study of consciousness and experience (Parnas and Zahavi, 2002). It aims to understand how human beings experience their world (Sutten and Austin, 2015). However, it is concerned with reflection, which similar to ethnography can be influenced by the researcher's own interpretations.

3.7.3 GROUNDED THEORY

Grounded theory is concerned with constructing theories through data analysis (Thomas and James, 2006). However, this form of analysis is often criticised as it is concerned with the participants preconceptions which can then influence the data interpretation (Thomas and James, 2006).

3.7.4 THEMATIC ANALYSIS

Thematic analysis aims to identify and record patterns within the data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). It provides a rich description, generated from the ideas identified within the data (Guest et al., 2012). As this research was conducted without a hypothesis to guide it, it undertakes a thematic analysis to analyse the findings of the data. Braun and Clarks (2006) thematic analysis can be adopted within social constructionist research. It has been found, that although not stereotypical, thematic analysis is compitable with a constructionist paradigm (Budds et al. 2013; Singer and

Hunter, 1999; Taylor and Ussher, 2001). A thematic analysis is the process of recording and identifying the themes which emerge throughout the data (Braun and Clarke, 2006). This research utilised Braun and Clarke (2006) six step process to conduct a thematic analysis. This can be seen in Table 5.5:

TABLE 3.5 THEMATIC ANALYSIS

Phase	Examples of Procedures for each step
Familiarising oneself with the data	Transcribing data; reading and re-reading, noting down initial codes
Generating initial codes	Coding interesting features of the data in a systematic fashion across the dataset, collating data relevant to each code
Searching for the themes	Collating codes into potential themes, gathering all data relevant to each potential theme
Involved reviewing the themes	Checking if the themes work in relation to the coded extracts and the entire dataset; generate a thematic 'map'
Defining and naming the themes	Ongoing analysis to refine the specifics of each theme; perceptions of clear names for each theme
Producing the report	Final opportunity for analysis, selecting appropriate extracts; discussion of the analysis; relate back to research question or literature; produce report

(Adapted from Braun and Clarke, 2006 pp. 87)

The first phase of the process is the initial transcribing and reading of the data, noting down initial codes which may occur to the researcher during this process.

The second phase is concerned with generating initial codes in accordance with the data which the researcher has transcribed.

The third phase is concerned with grouping similar codes together into relevant themes, in order to better organise them.

The fourth and fifth phases are concerned with defining and refining these themes, making sure they are accurate and concise, before naming them.

The sixth phase is concerned with the researcher setting out their findings in the appropriate manner.

3.8 CODING

After all the interviews were completed, they were then transcribed verbatim. It was then possible to begin coding the data, in accordance with the information which emerged and seemed relevant throughout the research process. Consistent with a social constructionist thematic analysis, this allows for the identification of themes within the data (Budds, 2013). The coding was initially conducted through pre-set codes which had already been predetermined. Though these codes were broad they allowed for the development of more specific storylines to emerge through the text. As a result of the storylines, narrower and more specific codes were able to emerge throughout the data. The data was coded repeatedly until specific and relevant codes were identified and determined.

3.9 PILOT STUDY

In order to test the validity of the research, a pilot study was conducted with relevant organisations. A pilot study aims to see whether something can be done (In, 2017). A pilot study is important in order to determine the quality and efficiency of the main study and to determine its feasibility (In, 2017). It is the first step of the research protocol. It is essentially a smaller scale study which influences the main study (Arnold et al., 2009). It is necessary for the pilot study to precede the main research in order to evaluate its validity (In, 2017). The pilot study incorporated the features of the main study, and the desired participants to ensure that this was the most efficient way for the main study to proceed (Benger et al., 2016).

Conducting a pilot study enables the researcher to test the questions they wish to ask within the main study (Saunders et al., 2012). Furthermore, the thematic analysis

of the pilot study can allow the researcher to determine if their questions are framed appropriately and capture the relevant data (Zikmund, 1997). It also allows the researcher to reflect upon their practice and develop an awareness of the potential ethical implications of their research (Kim, 2010).

Whilst some scholars suggest that pilot studies can be informal, others believe that they should be conducted in a formal manner and incorporated into the main study (Kim, 2010; Zikmund, 1997). This research elected to conduct the pilot study in a formal sense to ensure the rigour of the main study. Therefore, the ethical and methodological studies employed in the main study were also present within the pilot study.

The pilot study consisted of four interviews, two with leaders and two with participants in SMEs in Scotland. The pilot study consisted of participants who were eligible and met the criteria but were not counted within the results of the main study. As with the main study, the participants were informed of the ethical standards of the study and informed of their voluntary participation and guaranteed anonymity. Whilst the pilot study participants were not included in the findings, they met the participant criteria discussed previously.

The pilot study used the same interview schedule, analysis methods and theoretical underpinning as the main study. The data gathered from the pilot studies was then transcribed and thematically analysed using the 6-stage process previously outlined (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The pilot study found the interview protocol and analysis methods to be appropriate. Furthermore, it was able to inform of an appropriate timescale to conduct the interviews.

The pilot study offered an opportunity for reflection into the interview process. The researcher was able to determine that the previously imagined timescales for the interviews was too short, and this needed to be expanded to allow participants to fully express themselves within their answers. It was also noted that participants may need a further explanation of the concept of servant leadership before beginning the interview process, to avoid any confusion. The research was overall deemed to be appropriate and achieved its ethical objectives.

3.10 MAIN STUDY

In total the interview process consisted of 30 interviews. 15 leaders and 15 employees from the same SME. The SMEs were located in the six aforementioned geographical classifications of Scotland, thus totalling 15 SMEs which were examined. The participants were contacted via email or letter (Appendix 3 and 4). The semi-structured interviews were conducted in person and recorded on a handheld device. The participants were deemed to be suitable with regards to the aforementioned classification of geographical locations, the SME criteria and the servant leader criteria (Scottish Government, 2016).

Data saturation occurs when the relevant information has been determined from the research process and continuing would not further contribute to the theory (Lowe et al., 2018). After the 15th interview it was noted that the same themes were beginning to emerge within the data, thus it was determined that data saturation had been reached and the interview process was stopped (Lowe et al., 2018).

Qualitative research often utilises terms parallel to those used within quantitative research (Sparkes, 2011). By conducting research with both a leader and an employee within an SME the research was able to triangulate the data findings for accurate results. An overview of the participants involved in the research can be seen tables 5.6 and 5.7.

TABLE 3.6 OVERVIEW OF THE LEADER PARTICIPANTS

Leader	Gender	Industry	Geographical Location
Leader A	Male	Finance	Large Urban Area
Leader B	Male	Hospitality	Other Urban Area
Leader C	Female	Care	Accessible Small Town

Leader D	Male	Construction	Large Urban Area
Leader E	Male	Manufacturing	Large Urban Area
Leader F	Male	Fishing	Remote Small Town
Leader G	Male	Hospitality	Accessible Rural Town
Leader H	Female	Environmental	Accessible Small Town
Leader I	Male	Education	Remote Rural Town
Leader J	Male	Tourism	Remote Rural Town
Leader K	Male	Manufacturing	Other Urban Area
Leader L	Male	Catering	Accessible Rural Town
Leader M	Male	Manufacturing	Large Urban Area
Leader N	Male	Construction	Large Urban Area
Leader O	Male	Sales	Other Urban Area

TABLE 3.7 OVERVIEW OF THE EMPLOYEE PARTICIPANTS

Employee	Gender	Industry	Geographical Location
Employee A	Female	Finance	Large Urban Area
Employee B	Female	Hospitality	Other Urban Area
Employee C	Female	Care	Accessible Small Town
Employee D	Male	Construction	Large Urban Area
Employee E	Male	Manufacturing	Large Urban Area
Employee F	Male	Fishing	Remote Small Town
Employee G	Female	Hospitality	Accessible Rural Town

Employee H	Male	Environmental	Accessible Small Town
Employee I	Male	Education	Remote Rural Town
Employee J	Male	Tourism	Remote Rural Town
Employees K	Male	Manufacturing	Other Urban Area
Employee L	Male	Catering	Accessible Rural Town
Employee M	Male	Manufacturing	Large Urban Area
Employee N	Male	Construction	Large Urban Area
Employee O	Male	Sales	Other Urban Area

Overall, the majority of participants were male. Only 13% of leaders were female and only 20% of employees were female. There were 10 different industries which the SMEs operated in, the majority operating in the manufacturing industry. Furthermore, the research included SMEs within each of the geographical classification areas within Scotland (Scottish Government, 2016). The most common area was a large urban area, with 20% of SMEs operating in this area. Further discussion of the participants is included in chapter 4.

3.11 EVALUATION OF THE RESEARCH

Qualitative researchers must be aware that due to the social nature of their research, it is often the case that the conclusions they draw may not in fact be the absolute or indeed objective truth (Leininger, 1994). Therefore, in order to ensure and defend the integrity of their work, qualitative researchers must be able to justify its trustworthiness, credibility, applicability and consistency (Leininger, 1994; Lincoln and Guba, 1985).

3.11.1 TRUSTWORTHINESS

Trustworthiness is defined as a measure of the level of trust one has in a process (Chang et al., 2010). This research has proven to be trustworthy as it has passed the stringent ethical approval process as required by the University of the West of Scotland. It has additionally adhered to the ethical guidelines as set out by the University of the West of Scotland when carrying out the research. Furthermore, participants have been advised that they are able to view the transcripts of their interviews, which would allow for them to identify any potential untrustworthiness within the research. Participants were also provided with informed consent forms to ensure trustworthiness within the research.

3.11.2 CREDIBILITY

Credibility can be determined as a confidence in the truth of the research findings (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). The credibility of this research can be justified in that it has been verified by a panel of experts, coherent in methodological practices and servant leadership. Additionally, it has been informed by trusted and verified literature concerning methodological practices. Furthermore, by interviewing both employees and leaders within organisations, data triangulation has been achieved.

3.11.3 REFLEXIVITY

Reflexivity is concerned with self-reflection and reflection on the research process (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). This ensures that research is not influenced by either personal bias or bias influenced by the relationship to the research (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). The researcher was reflexive in order to examine the cause and effect found within the data. By being reflexive, the researcher ensured that the data gathered within the research is credible. Furthermore, the researcher conducted peer debriefing with the supervisor. This ensured that an additional party was aware of the research process and can validate its credibility.

3.11.4 APPLICABILITY

Applicability is concerned with the transferability of the research (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). It should be the case that the research is able to be transferred to other participants to other settings or with other respondents (Lincoln and Guba, 1985). Additionally, the exact methods adopted by this research have been clearly indicated and laid out by the researcher, thus highlighting that applicability was provided throughout the process of data gathering. Furthermore, evidence of how the data was gathered is provided through the discussion of the primary data.

3.11.5 CONSISTENCY

Consistency is concerned with showing relevant transitions within the research to provide transparency (Newman and Covrig, 2013). This research demonstrates consistency as a step-by-step comprehensive guide has been produced both within the research and the appendices. This research could therefore be replicated by anyone else wishing to conduct the same study. In addition, the research has provided an audit trail of the data gathering process which can be found within the appendix. This demonstrates the consistency of this research.

3.12 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

As this research was conducted within the University of the West of Scotland, their ethical principles have been taken into consideration. There are four principles outlined within the university's guidelines. They are as follows: honesty, rigour, transparency and respect and care (University of the West of Scotland, 2016).

3.12.1 HONESTY

To ensure honesty this research has acknowledged all work it has used. It has done this, by ensuring proper referencing has been conducted in order to give credit to all whose work has been of influence. Additionally, to be honest in research, one must ensure that data is not falsified or incorrectly reported. Through the transparent

nature of this research, where all is provided within the methodology and findings, the research has ensured that no false data or conclusions have been drawn.

3.12.2 RIGOUR

Rigour is an important ethical conclusion to take on board as it ensures that the accurate data is gathered in the correct way. To ensure rigour, this research carefully considered and researched all potential methods of data gathering. This allowed methods of the best fit to be applied, and thus the most accurate results to be provided by the data analysis.

3.12.3 TRANSPARENCY

Within research, transparency is an important ethical conclusion as it ensures that it is clear how all findings were determined by the data and its interpretations. This study ensured transparency by obtaining informed consent from all participants in the research. The consent form informed participants what the research entailed and what their participation in it meant. They were also informed that they were able to withdraw from the study at any time if they wish. Additionally, within the interview process the consent form was also discussed with participants to ensure that they understood everything that it entails.

Participants were given an information sheet which also gave them further detail as to what the study included. They were also made aware that they were able to contact the researcher at any time should they want clarification or further elaboration on any area of the study. Before participants even agreed to take part in the study, they were provided with a letter which outlined the contents of the research, to see if they wished to participate. For further information please see Appendices 1 and 2.

3.12.4 RESPECT AND CARE

Finally, respect and care must be given, for all participants, communities and other parties who may be involved in the data gathering process (University of the West of Scotland, 2016). This is concerned with respect for all human participants involved in the research (University of the West of Scotland, 2016). This research provided care and respect to the participants by ensuring that all research was carried out ethically, in accordance with the guidelines of University of the West of Scotland's ethics committee (See Appendix 9).

Additionally, great lengths were taken to protect participants privacy and anonymity. No names were recorded of any participant in the transcripts or the research itself. Instead, code names have been given to participants to protect their privacy. Additionally, paperwork filled out by participants e.g., consent forms were shredded after they had been uploaded onto the researcher's password protected computer which only the researcher had access to. After interviews were transcribed the voice recordings were deleted to protect the participants' privacy. Overall, the upmost care was taken to ensure that respect and care was shown to the participants in this research.

3.13 CONCLUSION

This chapter has provided an overview of the potential research approaches and philosophies that could potentially be employed by this research before justifying the approaches that the research decided upon in accordance with their appropriateness. It has also provided an overview of the qualitative research methods in terms of semi structured interviews, and the protocol which was used in the interview proves. It also discussed the participants and the SMES involved within the research, and the criteria which was met in order for them to be included. Furthermore, it has informed how it conducted the research to a high ethical standard.

In conclusion this chapter has presented the methodology employed by the research. The next chapter will proceed to discuss the findings which were determined by the research.

CHAPTER 4: FINDINGS

4.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter will present the findings collated by this research. These findings are the result of the semi-structured interviews of 30 participants. Details of the participants involved with the interview process can be found in appendix 8. The interviews of the participants were recorded and then transcribed in their entirety. This chapter will include excerpts from the interviews to further expand upon and justify the themes identified. Consistent with a social constructionist position, there was a focus on the language used by the participants throughout and its interpretation (Budds, 2013). Throughout the chapter there will be inclusions of example excerpts provided by participants so as to expand upon the relevant theme. As discussed within the methodology, to ensure ethical practice is adhered to, participants will be kept anonymous. Therefore, both leaders and employees will be referred to with a designated letter. For example, Leader A or Employee A. There are examples of how this will be demonstrated in table 6.1. This also provides an indication as to how the participants quotes will be presented within this chapter. This chapter aims to address, in part, the research objectives so as to determine the skills necessary for servant leadership.

As mentioned within the introduction, the research objectives are as follows:

- *To identify the skills necessary for servant leadership within SMEs*
- *To determine the organisational impact of servant leadership on SMEs*
- *To develop an empirical based framework of the servant leadership skills necessary within SMEs which contributes to the existing theory*
- *To provide a definition of servant leadership*

This chapter will begin by addressing research objective one:

To identify the skills necessary for servant leadership within SMEs

Before proceeding to address research objective two:

To determine the organisational impact of servant leadership on SMEs

Research objectives three and four, will be discussed in the following chapter.

Additionally, as previously mentioned in the introduction, the research questions for this research are as follows:

- *How can servant leadership be defined?*
- *What are the most prominent skills for servant leaders within SMEs?*
- *What is the organisational impact of servant leader's skills' on SMEs?*

This chapter will aim to answer research question two:

- *What are the most prominent skills for servant leaders within SMEs?*

Before proceeding to address research question three:

- *What is the organisational impact of servant leader's skills' on SMEs?*

This chapter will begin by providing a discussion of the skills theory to demonstrate how the skills were analysed and determined within this research. It will then proceed to provide an overview of the skills and subskills found within the interview process, as determined by the thematic analysis. Then the research will proceed to discuss a breakdown of the skills; interpersonal, conceptual, people management and development, technical and servanthood, with the relevant evidence determined within the interview process. The research will then proceed to outline the relationship between these servant leadership skills and their impact upon organisations.

The chapter will conclude by highlighting how the research questions and objectives have been addressed throughout the discussions. The skills discussion will consist of employees and leaders to allow for comparison and analysis.

4.2 SKILLS

As previously mentioned, the skills era focuses upon the skills and capabilities that a leader utilises to influence their followers (Mumford et al., 2000). Katz (1955) was one of the leading proponents of the notion that leadership can be learned and therefore there should be more focus on leader's skills rather than traits (Northouse, 2015). Skills within leadership are concerned with the knowledge and abilities which are necessary for effectiveness (Northouse, 2015). It has been suggested that by continually developing their skills, leaders are able to increase their own competence and thus become better leaders (Mumford et al., 2000). As previously mentioned, the research regarding skills and servant leadership is limited, therefore it was necessary for this research to rely upon general leadership skills literature when determining the skills to be used in the analysis.

4.3 TECHNICAL SKILLS

Technical skills were first determined as an area of study necessary for leadership by Katz (1955). It has since been determined as an important consideration when taking into account a leader's performance (Bass, 1990; Harrison, 2018; Katz, 1974). Technical skills generally consist of business, information or product knowledge. They are formed via formal education, work experience and the relevant training (Yukl, 2010). The concept of technical skills was introduced within the thematic analysis as they became apparent within the data generated. The three subthemes which emerged with regards to technical skills were education, professional experience and reflexivity.

FIGURE 4.1: TECHNICAL SKILLS

4.3.1 EDUCATION

Both leaders and employees who deemed education to be important for a servant leader. It should be noted that those who did not deem it so important, offered that experience was of greater importance than education, which will be discussed later within the chapter.

Education was deemed to be important in terms of further education or technical qualifications. 12 leaders and 8 employees deemed it to be important. 10 leaders had university degrees, 4 had postgraduate degrees of MBAs and 1 PhD and an additional 4 had military education. This is highlighted by Leader L who stated:

“I left school with no qualifications and when I joined the military, I realised that wasn’t such a good idea, so I had to start right at the beginning, so, I did my ONCH, I think, and this might sound strange, education is important, and I really believe that.”

This is further confirmed by Employee B who says of her leaders:

“Just feel like they all have a lot of education, a lot of like experience yeah because they’re like PhD graduates”

However, there were different aspects of education which both leaders and employees deemed to be important. For example, Employee N stated:

“I mean if you want to be an accountant, you need to go and do your degree in accountancy; if you want to be a surveyor, you’ll need to go and do some sort of course; a buyer, you could probably learn from someone teaching you; an estimator is generally the same” (Employee N).

This was echoed by Employee F who stated:

“They all have expertise in their own subject I think” (Employee F).

This demonstrates that these employees generally believe that your educational requirements are dependent on the role that you are undertaking. On the other hand, Leader B was more of the opinion that leaders should be educated in a general sense, explaining:

“So technical, because I’m a chartered accountant and I think that is important. I think you... if you are a leader you have to have professional qualifications” (Leader B).

This is echoed by Leader O who explained:

“Well, I’m a professional qualified person. I think it’s more me as a person, more than what I’ve done, yeah I’ve always had that open doors for me, I wouldn’t be here if I didn’t have these qualifications” (Leader O).

There was also a notion that continuous learning is important for leaders. This was not necessarily with regards to education in a formal sense. For example, Leader A, did not believe that a high school or further formal education were necessarily important. However, he did believe that it was important to educate yourself through learning from those around you such as entrepreneurs, other business owners and others in the industry. This was echoed by Leader M who, although believed more in formal education, thought it was just as important to learn from the people around you and other cultures. Leader F also learned from the charitable boards he sat upon. Leader C echoed Leader A in learning from other leaders, however they focused upon those in the media such as Steve Jobs, and the relevant leadership podcasts. Leader D believed it was important to learn from the people around them and their environment, which was echoed by Leader A, who summarises the sentiment stating:

“Learning, always Learning.” (Leader A).

This was also confirmed by Leader B, who stated:

“But, never to assume that I know it all, there’s always something more to learn.” (Leader B).

However, this sentiment was only echoed by Employee K, who believed it was important for leaders to learn from the organisations which they have been involved in before. On the other hand, employees found a general knowledge more important than continuous learning, with six employees deeming this important. Employee L believed that his leader should have a technical knowledge, which was echoed by Employee M. Employee L believed that it was important that his leader had the knowledge to fill the gaps within the organisation. Only one Leader, Leader M, believed that a knowledge of business and your general industry was important. This shows a difference in employees and leaders with regards to the importance of learning and knowledge. It was also highlighted by Leader G, Leader F and Employee M that a general level of intellect or intelligence is necessary for leaders, alongside a formal education.

Therefore, it can be stated that education was regarded as important for leaders; whether this was in a formal or informal sense was debateable amongst the employees and leaders. Generally, the majority of the leaders and employees believed that a formal education is necessary for the role of a servant leader, and to allow them to develop their technical skills.

4.3.2 PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

Professional experience was also considered necessary for developing the technical skills of the servant leader. 12 leaders and eight employees stated that it was necessary for a servant leader to have some form of relevant experience to succeed.

In total, 12 leaders deemed professional experience important, whereas three believed that it was not so necessary and instead were more concerned with life skills. Whilst the number of employees who agreed that professional experience was necessary is less than that of leaders, at only 8 employees, they did not directly say it was not important. Moreover, they focused on other aspects such as formal education or life experiences. Additionally, 2 employees stated that they were not sure with regards to professional experience.

Though some leaders believed that both education and experience were important, a few leaders believed that their jobs could only be learned through experience. There was also discussion of their previous roles being of importance with regards to experience. Three leaders mentioned that their military background had contributed to their experiences and seven other leaders mentioned that it was their experiences in other organisations. For example, Leader H summarised the need for experience by stating:

“You can’t really be trained to do the jobs that we do, in the office. The guys are all clever, educated, know what it takes to get a job done, whereas the guys on the site are maybe less educated, less motivated, that work in much worse conditions, that can only be brought through in your own experience. It really is just an experience thing” (Leader H).

Leader H further stated:

“There’s loads of other skills that are all experience to be honest with you, you know you go and do a course that gives you a piece of paper that tells you, you can go onto a site you know from health and safety. It’s all about communication and having the experience in what we do here, that’s the key to it all” (Leader H).

The notion of professional experience was also echoed by Employee C when he stated:

“I would say they bring their previous experience to the Trust, so you know it, it’s a mixture of you know depends on where they’ve been before and their network of supporters.” (Employee C).

Leader H is one of three leaders who believed that formal education was not necessarily important for her role but that her success was more of a result of experience. However, nine other leaders believed that both education and experience was necessary for servant leaders. This is highlighted by Leader N who stated:

“I think that the education part is important but also you can travel and just see different people and learn different things and you know not your six pals who’ve always lived in the same place” (Leader N).

Additionally, the eight employees who believed education to be important also believed that experience was necessary, which is indicated by Employee B:

“Education... Erm I don’t know I just feel like they all have a lot of education, a lot of like experience, yeah” (Employee B).

One of the ways in which experience was generated for leaders was through mentorship and learning from other leaders. This is something which was noted by six leaders and three employees. Leader B explained:

“I do think having a mentor is actually a really important factor in leadership and which I haven’t had but I think that, well I did have a mentor for just a wee bit, but I think that made a difference” (Leader B).

Additionally, whilst a mentor was not specifically mentioned, Leader G detailed taking inspiration from other leaders:

“There are some very good examples of some very good leaders that I’ve come across, that didn’t need to be so good in a sense because you could argue that you could order people around in the military, but the best leaders never did that. The best leaders didn’t need to order around, so I saw good and bad” (Leader G).

This was also the case with Leader H when he stated:

“I’ve been in a leadership role since the age of 21, I’m now 51. My experiences have probably been from good and bad leadership that I have experienced in my life. And, interestingly enough, in the early years in the navy, there are some very good examples of some very good leaders that I’ve come across”

This indicates that servant leaders learn from mentors, or other experienced leaders around them. Having life skills, which could also be linked to a result of experiences was mentioned by three leaders as being important to them. Leader M states:

“These things all have an effect. Life skills is what you bring to the table”
(Leader M).

This highlights that these leaders believed that their experience was demonstrated through their general life skills, which they brought to the organisation.

Furthermore, four leaders and one employee also highlighted that common sense was a result of their experiences and attributed it to the way they lead. This was indicated by Leader I who stated:

“I have the common sense, it’s just... I have common sense” (Leader I).

Overall, the skill of being professionally experienced either in your field or in terms of education was deemed a necessary technical skill for servant leaders.

4.3.3 REFLEXIVITY

A further sub skill which was determined necessary for technical skills was that of reflexivity. Reflexivity was discussed by leaders with regards to learning from their experiences in their professional life, in order to improve upon their technical skills. This was deemed of high importance to leaders, far more than it was to employees.

In total, 11 leaders found the skill of reflexivity to be important, compared to only 3 employees. This highlights that there is a disparity between the importance of reflexivity according to both leaders and employees.

Leader B best describes the practice of reflexivity as being concerned with learning from the past, stating:

“I think a lot of it is learning from, through mistakes, just reflecting for me personally it’s about why has that happened? Why you know, why do I feel like this? What should I have done differently? So, I do an awful lot of self-analysis. I think it is really important to always reflect on the situation” (Leader B).

Leader F also likened reflexivity to learning from the past in the workplace by stating:

“A reflective period, you understood that’s what you’ve been doing so that was very helpful. I’d never had any kind of management training, just you did it. It was all just on the job in effect and so that was an intense period of solid reflection” (Leader F).

He continued:

“I’d never had any kind of management training, just you did it. It was all just on the job in effect and so that was an intense period of solid reflection” (Leader F)

This was a general sentiment of the leaders within the organisation. They would observe the mistakes or unsuccessful methods of the past and change them going forward. Whilst Leaders L and H did not explicitly mention reflexivity, they did discuss making mistakes and ensuring that they don’t happen again by learning from them. This was further confirmed by Leader K who stated:

“I’m saying in a different context you always learn from what goes wrong compared to what goes right” (Leader K)

Although, as previously mentioned, it was not deemed as important for employees, three employees highlighted the reflexivity of learning from the mistakes of the past. This is highlighted by both Employees G and K who stated:

“I think they’re always looking at the best way to do a different or look at a different way of doing things.” (Employee G).

Overall, leaders and employees stated that observation, and having a grasp on the reality of situations through observation, were important for the reflexivity of servant leaders.

4.4 CONCEPTUAL SKILLS

Conceptual skills were identified as a relevant theme during the thematic analysis process. Conceptual skills are the more abstract of the skills outlined by Katz (1955).

They are concerned with looking at the organisation as a whole and developing an understanding of it. Conceptual skills involve the generation of ideas and concepts regarding the organisation. The subthemes of conceptual skills were as follows: strategic skills, organisational development, innovation and envisioning as seen in figure 4.2.

FIGURE 4.2 CONCEPTUAL SKILLS

Conceptual Skills were determined necessary by both leaders and employees with 14 leaders and 13 employees highlighting their importance. This will now be discussed in further depth.

4.4.1 STRATEGIC SKILLS

One of the sub skills which became apparent throughout the discussion of conceptual skills was that of strategy. Strategic skills were identified by both leaders and employees in several different ways. However, they were deemed far more important for leaders, with 13 leaders agreeing they were necessary, in comparison to only 8 employees. Strategic skills were concerned largely with developing and implementing strategy within organisations.

The importance of having strategic skills was highlighted by Leader A who stated:

“You have to be strategic. Yeah, you’re always thinking about the strategy of the business” (Leader A).

It was further echoed by Leader I, who confirms:

“So, having a strategy and having people fall into strategy is a massive part of the change programme that we have here” (Leader I).

Furthermore, as previously mentioned, strategic skills were also deemed important by employees, which is highlighted by Employee M:

“The strategy type stuff that all gets done at director level, that’s what they need to do. Strategy I would say everything they do benefits the business” (Employee M).

Emphasis particularly was placed on the importance of strategic thinking and problem solving. All leaders stated that they were problem solvers within the organisation and believed that this was an important skill to have. This is highlighted by leader F:

“If we’ve got a problem fix it, I’m very keen that’s the approach so yes” (Leader F).

It was further echoed by Employee F, when discussing his leader:

“I think they’ve had to be, because they’ve come in and had to bring change because it was just one of those kinds of communities where everyone was just set in their ways. All the new people who came in have had to, have come into a list of problems they’ve had to overcome” (Employee F).

Whilst it was the case that both leaders and employees generally agreed that servant leadership involves problem solving, Employee E disagreed that his leader was a problem solver and instead believed that they were the route of the problems, stating:

“Problem causers! I would say it’s one area they are really bad, can’t put my finger on why it’s happening, some of them have got loads of experience” (Employee E).

Additionally, two leaders suggested that rather than being direct problem solvers themselves, they were more concerned with surrounding themselves with the best people and having the correct staff placement. This was explained by Leader E, who stated:

“I’d say I’m more likely to find a problem solver! No, I’m not great at problem solving” (Leader E).

This was also echoed by Leader D:

“Sometimes but again, I think I’m probably more of a problem identifier. And then open that up to a group of people to solve so I certainly don’t lose sleep at night because I haven’t solved a problem” (Leader D).

This also highlights that where a leader recognises that they may not have the best problem-solving skills themselves, through staff placement and surrounding themselves with the best people they are able to solve problems.

Although not intrinsically linked to problem solving, the ability to make decisions to improve or develop strategy were also highlighted as important for the strategic skills of some leaders. Leader C discussed the importance of either being able to make decisions or give others the ability to make decisions to enhance the organisation, stating:

“Because you have to get used to the idea that you’re making the decisions because you’ve made the decision to allow other people to do some of that” (Leader C).

Furthermore, the ability to use judgement when making decisions was highlighted by Leader E, who stated:

“I think you need good judgement, because with the style I have liberty takers”

(Leader E).

Overall, strategic skills were deemed to be important for both leaders and employees.

4.4.2 ORGANISATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Organisational Development (OD) was highlighted as an important subtheme for conceptual skills. It was deemed as important by both employees and leaders, with 11 leaders and employees discussing it during their interviews.

There were many ways in which leaders discussed organisational development, such as investment, managing growth, implementing, and managing change. It was highlighted that there was a need for managing organisational change and advocating this, organisation wide. The need for this was highlighted by 11 leaders and 4 employees. For example, Leader C stated that with regards to organisational change, they have changed the structure of the organisation:

“Organisation, we’ve changed the central structure, the central business support process to lean and agile process so there’s a much more efficient system” (Leader C).

This was echoed by his employee who stated:

“I think probably every care organisation over the years has had to change the way that it works and the way that it operates” – (Employee C).

Whilst Leader C and Employee C had indicated the need to change to grow the organisation, Employee D believed that change was necessary for survival in his field, explaining:

“I think that for a care organisation, over the years, we have always had that ability to change in line with what would be required to survive within the care sector”
(Employee D).

Changes to culture were also identified as important by four leaders, to aid the success of the organisation. Leader I believed that it was necessary to advocate such cultures to get other followers on board, explaining:

“Influencing the culture development of the organisation and the progression of the business so what I’m trying to do is give those people whose heads are maybe stuck in the past a vision of something that is more progressive” (Leader I).

Leader B also believed that follower contribution was also necessary to implement change, stating:

“When an organisation goes wrong or when it flourishes there’s a direct correlation between what people have chosen to do together to create culture, so I think in terms of skills and you know knowledge there’s been a natural progression” (Leader B).

On the other hand, Leader F believed in the need for a combination of both culture change and leaner organisations, stating:

“After two years, I’m beginning to see how that culture has actually changed but I do believe that’s because I don’t feel the need to actually control everything that everybody does. In fact, I actually don’t think you can in this day and age. We are a much leaner organisation” (Leader F).

4.4.3 INNOVATION

When discussing innovation, 13 leaders stated that they would describe themselves as innovative. This was largely triangulated by employees, 14 of whom stated that they believed their leaders are innovative.

The ability to innovate was indicated in a number of ways by both the leaders and employees. Leader C had even gone as far as to indicate that they had set up a programme specifically for innovation within her organisation, stating:

“We set up an innovation programme, so there are different managers and staff from all around the organisation, depending what their expertise is, working on innovations and we’ve actually got a process that they go through. They have to follow the rules, and work on a new piece of innovation” (Leader C).

Leader C believed that innovation was innate to them, explaining:

“I think innovation is part of my DNA and its certainly part of the organisation’s DNA” (Leader C).

This was agreed by the employee who stated:

“You can see that she has a vision for innovation and doing something different” – (Employee C)

All participants who agreed that innovation was important had different ways and means on how innovation should be carried out. Leader M suggested that it is having an awareness of other organisations, and being able to react to the innovations they have implemented and employing them within his own organisation, stating:

“I make no odds about this, If I see some good practice elsewhere, I will steal it and use it myself” (Leader M).

However, Leader E believed that his innovation came with innovations implemented to benefit staff, explaining:

“because I bumped the living wage before anybody else did. I see the opportunity in that, not the negative in that and I think that’s innovative” (Leader E).

Leaders D and F believed that they had been innovative via bringing technology in to his organisations to positively impact upon his SMEs productivity. Leader G believed that innovation was necessary in order to do the job stating:

“Innovation is part of the job. We need to find ways to achieve results in certain ways and we find ways of doing that so yeah, I would say its relatively there.” (Leader G).

Employee C explained that innovation had been brought in since her leader began working there. He helped to bring about change and make the organisation stand out by being proactive in comparison with other industries. A similar sentiment was echoed by Employee D.

Overall, the majority of the leaders and employees agreed that servant leaders should be innovative, and this in turn will positively impact upon performance within SME.

4.4.4 ENVISIONING

The findings from the data showed that respondents were concerned with envisioning skills. Envisioning for the organisation was identified by 12 leaders and 10 employees highlighting its importance. There were different reasons provided for envisioning: Employee J explained that it was important for his leader to envision due to practical changes such as Brexit, Leader O stated that it was necessary to have a vision in order to inspire and motivate work ethic and Leader K believes a vision would help to change attitudes within the organisation. Leader P explains that a vision is necessary for a ‘big picture’ stating:

*“I find it very easy to paint a very big picture and kind of hold it up and say this is what we’re trying to do, so if you say to me what does **** what does success look like for them, I’m very clear in my head what that looks like” (Leader P).*

On the other hand, Employee O believed it was necessary to innovate for the organisation to grow:

“I would say they have a clear vision and that just is quite simply to keep growing the business and keep doing the things that they’re doing well probably” (Employee O).

Leaders also had different opinions with regards to who was more important to align with the vision. For example, Leader I believed that the most important people to align the vision with is the stakeholders, stating:

“Yes, I certainly have vision. You know we have regular meetings with potential investors or financiers, and they all want to know what the vision and mission of this organisation is. We had to sit down and try and understand our vision for our business. So, we have clarity in that now. We are all agreed in that vision now”

(Leader I).

However, four other leaders believed that it was more important to align staff with the vision and to get them on board. They indicated that if this was not done then the vision could not be achieved, which is highlighted by the interview extract by Leader M below:

“Vision, vision I think it’s how you get people bought into the vision, I think we’ve all got vision, I have a vision for this business, most people have seen where I think we can go, that’s a vision but everybody has it and I think part of vision is being able to articulate that and get people bought into it” (Leader M).

Leader L, on the other hand, was less concerned with getting staff on board with the vision and instead discussed the importance of having a strategic vision, aligned with improving the overall strategy of the organisation, explaining:

“I believe you learn things strategically from good experiences. So, in terms of strategic vision, you’ve got to see what doesn’t work, so the IT was an example, and

it took something going wrong in here to see just how IT literate we are now. There's a strength to sort of get this sort of vision, so yeah strategically" (Leader L).

It was also deemed necessary for leaders to be able to envision, so as to determine future directions for the organisation and provide followers clarity as to this vision. Leader N believed that the best way to do this was through an awareness of what was happening within the industry and being able to identify opportunities in this way, explaining:

"I think, as I said to you, you have to be really aware of what's happening and taking the time to read the newspapers, watch the news, go to your industry events because you know what's happening with technology." (Leader N).

Overall, the majority of employees and leaders proposed envisioning, making it the conceptual subskill that was deemed to be the most relevant for servant leadership.

4.5 INTERPERSONAL SKILLS

Interpersonal skills (also referred to as human skills) were also identified by Katz (1955) and are concerned with one's ability to work with and interact with others (Harrison, 2018). They were found to be a key skill necessary for servant leadership by the participants. Within interpersonal skills, there were four subskills identified as necessary for servant leaders. These were communication, empathy, teambuilding and nurturing which will now be discussed. (See Figure 4.3)

FIGURE 4.3 INTERPERSONAL SKILLS

The importance of interpersonal skills according to the participants was deemed to be high. All of the leaders and 11 employees deemed them to be necessary.

4.5.1 COMMUNICATION

Communication was found to be the most important interpersonal skill for the participants, with all leaders and majority of employees deeming it to be important. Communication was discussed in a variety of ways by both the leaders and employees. A generally good overarching definition of communication was provided by Leader A, who stated:

“I mean somebody once said to me what is communication and I said well it’s when you say this or when you say that, and they said well what about animals they communicate without any words dolphins and things. Somebody once gave me the definition that communication is the creation of shared understanding and I think that once you understand that, that’s what communication is” (Leader A).

Leader H also provided overarching examples of communication:

“I think communication, you know whether face to face or via email or just talking to people, I think it’s the key to everything that we do; open honest communication” –
(Leader H)

Employee L also explained what they thought to be the essence of communication from his leader, stating:

“I think you don’t want a leader that does everything themselves, doesn’t communicate to everybody. You want somebody that’s sort of a figure head and also listens to the opinions of others but can also explain what they want everybody else to do I think it’s a communication thing” (Employee L).

Employee A also agreed that listening was key for communication explaining:

“Communication skills is obviously key, they’re good at listening” – (Employee A)

Seven leaders mentioned the importance of listening to their employees, which was also deemed to be important by six employees. Leader I stated that he was able to listen to his employees by being open and approachable to everyone. This was also echoed by Leader J who had an open-door policy, explaining:

“listening to ideas, hearing their ideas, giving them time to tell me if things aren’t going well or if they are. One of the things I notice about myself is, as a leader, people interrupt you all the time. They don’t think to chap the door and say have you got a minute, they just come straight in” (Leader J).

There was a consensus between both the employees and leaders that the best way to listen to their employees was by creating an atmosphere which was open and accessible. There was also mention of the importance of leaders being visible to their employees to encourage them to come in and communicate. This was highlighted by Leader B who discussed it as being visible rather than being ‘stuck in

a box'. The creation of this type of environment highlights the impact that servant leadership can have on the environment of an SME.

Networking was highlighted by both Leader K and Employee K as an important tool for communication. Both highlighted the benefits of their leader networking and encouraging their employees to network in order to bolster their communication skills overall. Furthermore, whilst both Leaders N and E did not specifically mention networking, they did discuss the importance of meeting new people within the industry to improve and work upon their communication skills. Therefore, it can be said that networking was highlighted as an important skill necessary for communication by some leaders and employees.

The need to be honest was brought up repeatedly by both leaders and employees with regards to communication. Leader B believed that they liked to encourage honesty from his staff and themselves so as to communicate effectively, stating:

“People know that I just like honesty. Therefore, if somebody has screwed up, I need them to come to me and say look, this is what’s happened, and I will always encourage them to understand why it happened” (Leader B).

It was also stated by Leader K that honesty was the most important element of communication, and without it, communication would fail. Leader B echoed this sentiment by explaining that he found it easiest to communicate with his employees due to his honesty, which in turn enabled them to be honest. In total five leaders and six employees believed that honesty was necessary for communication.

Overall, leaders and employees showed that communication was the most important subskill for servant leaders’ interpersonal skills.

4.5.2 EMPATHY

Empathy was also determined by both leaders more so than employees as an important interpersonal skill. Empathy is concerned with the ability to understand and

share in the feelings of others. Empathy was deemed important by 10 leaders. However, only 8 employees stated it to be important, highlighting there is a disparity with regards to this subskill.

When Leader B was asked what the most important skill for him was, he answered simply 'Empathy.' This was echoed by Employee A who also believed that empathy was one of the most important skills for his leader. Another example of a leader who believed in its importance was Leader F, who stated it when asked about the skills needed for his role:

“Empathy for their peers and colleagues and anybody they line manage”
(Leader F).

Furthermore, emotional intelligence was noted by Leaders D and K to be important. If one is emotionally intelligent, one is able to understand the feelings of others and, thus, empathise with them. Leader D explained that when he had come to the organisation the emotional intelligence had not been there previously, so he had set about changing this, explaining:

“Emotional intelligence was a big issue here and that’s changing so we are trying to help people come to work enjoy their work, be less emotional about it and be much more respectful to each other. I think that is something I have to do daily” (Leader D).

Leader K on the other hand believed that he had helped enhance emotional intelligence within the organisation and this had improved the general atmosphere of the organisation. Leader O placed it above general education, stating:

“Emotional intelligence has to be pretty good. I mean academically I’m not the cleverest guy that there is, but I think anyway I’m pretty good with people” (Leader O).

There were other aspects of empathy mentioned by both the 10 leaders and eight employees such as being caring and offering forgiveness to their employees if mistakes are made. Overall, there was a consensus that having empathy towards staff has a positive impact on the SME in general.

4.5.3 TEAMBUILDING

When discussing interpersonal skills, there were discussions brought up with regards to cultivating relationships and building teams within the organisation. However, it was deemed to be far more important for leaders than it was for employees, similar to empathy, with only 8 employees highlighting its importance.

Teambuilding was described by Leader H as being necessary for the organisational environment, regardless of the area of the organisation, explaining:

“Therefore, it’s about creating a team environment so that is what I would say are my sort of key requirements or what I believe are essential from a leadership point of view... people know where to come to but be engaging and therefore creating that team environment whether it’s a technical team or an office team or an organisational team” (Leader H).

There were numerous ways in which leaders and employees believed that teams could be built. One of these was by generating trust between the leaders and the employee. Leader B stated that he had been working hard since he joined the organisation in order to cultivate trust, which was echoed by Leader K who believed that the only way to get his team on board was if he had their trust. Leader B believed that team working is necessary to use their strengths by stating:

“You need to pool people together and draw on them. So in other words you know not perfect it’s not your whole responsibility and so therefore it’s about creating a team environment.” (Leader B)

A similar sentiment was made by Employee C, regarding delegating to a team explaining:

“It’s about bringing her team on board with her and all moving forward rather than telling people what they’re going to do.” (Employee C).

There were also discussions of creating a collaborative work environment which involves power sharing and sharing the workload. When Leader L was asked about his leadership style, they described it as 'collaborative' and then proceeded to discuss how important they believed it to be for him to work alongside the team, rather than a figure head. A similar sentiment was echoed by Leader C:

"I am predominantly a collaborative leader. I believe in the power of group and I believe in the power of individuals within that group to contribute" (Leader C).

Leader B even discussed an innovative idea of a 'decision making unit' which they had created within his organisation for employees to check each other's work and share the workload together:

"They have actually got a process that they go through, they have to follow the rules, and work on a new piece of innovation whether that's a service or efficiency or whatever, they then bring that to the DMU. The decision-making unit which again is a collegiate group of their colleagues on whether they've done enough work." (Leader B)

This allowed for collaboration between employees in the workplace and also allowed for power sharing as employees were able to 'check' each other and their productivity. Employee C also highlighted the importance of collaboration for teambuilding within her organisation stating:

"It's always been like a kind of inclusive approach that everybody is entitled to have their opinion, the collective team will make a decision on how best to go forward" (Employee C).

There were also discussions of the necessity of socialising to build teams. Employee C explained that in her organisation this was achieved by having a 'friendlier' relationship with her leader:

“You’re there speaking to these people on a friendship basis. It’s a social friendship relationship with them which runs in tandem with your professional relationship with them” (Employee C).

Leader L echoed this social idea when asked how he socialised with his employees, stating:

“As human beings I relate to them, I’ve got a good social interaction with them” (Leader L).

In total, six employees explained that socialising with their leaders was important for teambuilding, compared to only four leaders. This indicates that employees find socialising important to team building, more so than leaders.

Overall, both leaders and employees deemed teambuilding to be an important subskill, which would help servant leaders to improve their interpersonal skills.

4.5.4 NURTURING

The concept of nurturing employees was also raised by both leaders and employees when discussing interpersonal skills, however, it was deemed more important by leaders, with 11 mentioning in it, compared to employees with only 8 bringing it up. Nurturing in this instance referred to caring for their employees, and helping them to develop in a personal sense, rather than in terms of the workplace.

Being accommodating to their followers was described by one leader and one employee as an important element to nurturing. Employee B discussed how they believed that his leader was able to nurture them by being accommodating, explaining:

“I quite like her approach, she’s very accommodative. Any questions, anything like that, I don’t feel like I’m disturbing her or like she’s too busy or you know you just feel like she can accommodate anyone” (Employee B).

A similar sentiment was echoed by Leader D who believed that one of the most important skills for them as a leader was to be accommodating to his followers, and thus allowing them to feel like they could go to them with anything.

Furthermore, the idea of leaders providing guidance was also discussed. Leader A, when asked how they felt his success had contributed to the success of the organisation, stated:

“I believe I provide in leadership in guidance, and it’s not necessarily from a technical point of view but it’s also from a personal point of view” (Leader A).

The notion of guidance and advising was also suggested to be important by Leaders B and D who believed that providing guidance to their employees was important. Furthermore, two employees explained that their leaders providing them with advice was a key interpersonal skill, with Employee B stating:

“Every day, so it’s easy if there’s any problems or anything. It’s very easy to approach and say, ‘This has happened, can you give me advice, can you help?’ It’s a lot better” (Employee B).

In general, it was mentioned by employees and leaders that being accommodating and providing guidance for employees was important. It was also highlighted by two leaders that this should be done by showing patience. On the other hand, Employee N believed that it was necessary for leaders to nurture ‘home-grown’ talents, explaining:

*“When I first started **** was really good at nurturing home grown talents.”*
(Employee N).

Three employees and two leaders stated that nurturing involves cultivating a relaxing atmosphere. Overall, nurturing was shown to be an important subskill of interpersonal skills for servant leaders.

4.6 SERVANTHOOD

Servanthood was a topic which repeatedly came up with regards to the leaders and employees and was of high importance. It was determined by 9 employees and 11 leaders, highlighting its prevalence.

The main aspects of servanthood which were identified by both the leaders and employees in the research were serving others and serving in the community, which will now be discussed. Whilst most of the leaders and employees agreed that serving others was an important skill for them as leaders, there was greater disparity when it came to the notion of serving in the community, which will now be further explored.

FIGURE 4.4 SERVANTHOOD

4.6.1 SERVING IN THE COMMUNITY

Serving in the community repeatedly came up with regards to employees and leaders and was considered to be of high importance, with 9 employees and 11 leaders discussing it.

The involvement of the organisation with serving in the community was highlighted by Leader E who stated:

“We are very much involved with the local community here; we are really active in fact.” (Leader E).

This was also discussed by Employee G:

“We were one of the categories of the bee’s knees - -which is an annual chamber of commerce awards so there was definitely a desire to become involved with the local business community” (Employee G).

Furthermore, it appeared that there was a different catalyst for each leader to develop this skill. The skill seemed to appear to be of particular importance to leaders whose businesses were based within areas which were of lower socio-economic status. Leader L highlighted that:

*“If you look at this yard, I mean ***** is quite a high unemployment area. The social economic prosperity that this yard brings to the people, they’ve been able to provide good reasonably well-paid jobs in a local area where unemployment is very high” (Leader L).*

This was further confirmed by Employee L, in the same organisation who agreed that:

“If we are getting work in it’s a good idea because some of your scoring on tenders is based on your community involvement, you’re going to do it by default to a certain degree because it makes sense to hire people locally where you can. But there will be a certain degree of the works, you’re trying to get will want to see some sort of community involvement” (Employee L).

It was further echoed by Leader N that serving in the community was important to support impoverished areas, and to ‘give back’:

“Here is a deprived area and we, in the grand scheme of things as a family business, were all earning very good money and we’ve got a very successful business with millions in the bank, we, I feel, we owe it to the community to put a bit back” (Leader N).

Leader E echoed Leader N’s sentiments of highlighting the importance of serving in the community by hiring locally by explaining that this allows leaders to feel like they are doing something good for the local community. Leader A also believed that due

to the social problems in his area (such as alcohol and drug abuse) it was important for them to hire within the community to try and address these issues.

This shows that some leaders believe it was necessary for them to develop the skill of serving in the community, to empower the areas they exist within, which are disadvantaged due to their socio-economic standing. There was a consensus that this would encourage good will amongst the community, and would also allow the organisations to hire locally, whilst encouraging locals to support them. This could be said to show the impact of servant leadership upon the organisation's success, as there was a clear correlation between serving in the community and perceived success of the organisation.

However, it should be highlighted that whilst Employee L agreed that service in the community was important for his leader, he did suggest a potentially ulterior motive for this service:

"It's a tax write off so there's probably two sides to that, you've got the tax write off, from a sensibility point of view it makes sense to get people who are local"
(Employee L).

Overall, eight leaders who agreed that serving in the community was important, did so to 'give back' to the poorer communities within which they were based, which was also echoed by the majority of their employees.

Other leaders had alternate reasons for serving in the community, for example because of the industry that they worked in. Employee E, who worked in the fishing industry, believed that his leader had developed the skill of serving in the community as a result of the businesses detrimental impact on the community:

*"Like I say, it is important for our business because we're a ***** factory and we smell a lot, so we have to try and keep the local community happy"* (Employee E).

On the other hand, Leader L believed it was important to serve in the community because his organisation was based in the care industry and they believed that this was the very nature of his organisation:

“They too have family. Sometimes they are in their community and the whole ethos of our organisation is for people to be cared for in their communities, to be part of their communities” (Leader L).

This was confirmed by the Employee within that organisation, who also said:

“I think it’s as well important that we are involved in kind of local initiatives because we are a charity as well so that we can be seen to be involved in all aspects of society and the community.” (Employee L).

Other leaders believed it was important to develop the skill of serving in the community to generate a visibility of their organisation within the community. Leader E explained that this was even tantamount to the organisation being able to successfully run:

“Yes, I mean there’s defiantly...we couldn’t do any of our work without getting the community on side and you know working with them” (Leader L)

It was also echoed by employees, such as Employee D:

“It is good for the organisation to have a kind of a face within that community” (Employee D).

This sentiment was echoed by five other leaders and was largely agreed with by their employees.

Additionally, Leader A identified that they served their community by way of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), stating:

“We do a fair bit of corporate social responsibility” (Leader A).

However, there were employees who did not agree that serving in the community was an important skill for a leader. For example, Leader E said of serving in the community, that it was the concern of individuals of an organisation rather than the leaders, if they were so inclined, explaining:

“I don’t know how important it is to the success of your business but it’s important probably to the person, no one wants to be disliked” (Leader E).

Employee F also was uncertain as to the importance of serving in the community for a leader, simply replying:

“Don’t know if it’s important” (Employee F).

Leader L out-right believed that it was not important to serve in the community, explaining:

“I didn’t need to have an involvement. There’s merits to it, but I don’t think it’s necessary” (Leader L).

However, Leader L expanded that this was because her business does not impact on or involve the local community unlike the earlier leaders who saw this as a reason to develop their skill of serving in the community.

Overall, the research highlighted that for a variety of different motivations, serving in the community was an important skill for the leaders and employees interviewed.

4.6.2 SERVING PEOPLE

As discussed, serving people also emerged as a prominent subtheme of servanthood which was echoed by both the leaders and employees within the research. However, employees did not deem it to be as important as leaders. A majority of employees at 9 thought serving people was not important, compared to 10 employees.

It was indicated that leaders served their employees through a variety of ways, one of which was by encouraging the strengths of their employees. Leader I explained how he was able to do this by stating:

“I will look at what strengths they have, I will look at what their passions are and who they are as an individual and see if I can cause them to see how they can apply themselves” (Leader I).

This indicates that they served others through helping them to build upon their strengths.

Serving people was also identified by both leaders and employees in the form of being quite flexible to the needs of others. Employee L identified how they felt that his leader’s flexibility served them:

“They are very flexible with us sales guys, we get a very long leash” (Employee L).

This was echoed by Leader I within the same organisation who confirmed this by stating:

“Being quite flexible and also being as I mentioned earlier, really clear” (Leader I).

This shows that by providing their employees flexibility within the workplace, and by being flexible themselves, leaders are able to serve their employees.

Employee I and Leader B were of the mindset that by offering a form of mentoring to their employees, the leaders were demonstrating the skill of serving people, and thus servanthood. Two leaders which were from the same organisation believed that they served their employees by way of values, in adhering to them and applying them within their leadership roles. An example of this is Leader K stating:

“Values, our purpose statement, what are we here for, ties all of that together so for me, everything I do has to have meaning in terms of the whole person, has to have meaning in terms of serving” (Leader K).

Additionally, Employee K believed that the employees were served by way of his leaders offering stability and consistency within the organisation, which was also how Leaders K and L saw themselves as serving the people in their organisation.

Furthermore, responsibility was identified as a form of serving people by Leader B, who believed it was important that they take ownership of the mistakes made within the organisation. Whilst there were some disparities in terms of what constitutes serving others, all leaders agreed that supporting their employees was an important way of serving them. All leaders and employees also agreed that a focus upon the staff was an essential way of serving their employees.

Overall, whilst the ways in which the skill of servanthood was achieved differed in accordance with both the employees and leaders, all participants agreed that it was an important skill for a servant leader.

4.7 PEOPLE MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT

The skill of people management and development emerged as prominently linked with servant leadership during the course of this research. The main aspects of people management and development which were identified in the study were empowerment, employee development and motivating people (Figure 4.5). They will now be explored further.

FIGURE 4.5 PEOPLE MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT

It was highlighted that people management and development was deemed to be important for both leaders and employees, with 13 employees and all leaders determining it necessary.

4.7.1 EMPOWERMENT

With regards to empowerment, this skill was displayed through several ways, as previously mentioned. For an overview of the importance of empowerment to both leaders and employees, it is important to note that all leaders and 13 employees discussed it.

One of the ways in which both leaders and employees believed that empowerment was displayed was through generating and having respect from the followers. Respect was mentioned by all leaders and 13 employees, as being important in empowering people. Employee B highlighted the need for respect from her leader by stating:

“It doesn’t mean that you can’t say what’s on your mind, but I think it’s about being respectful. I think the majority of staff we support understand that, but I think there are times that some staff don’t understand the need to be respectful” (Employee B).

A further example of the need for respect was highlighted by Leader A, who stated:

“I think totally though for respect you know earn it and the guys realise that this was created by nothing really and they buy into that” (Leader A).

Thus, all leaders acknowledged that respect was important for empowerment and most employees also reiterated this.

Other aspects were mentioned as important for empowerment, such as giving space to the followers. For example, Leader L believed that it was important for a leader to trust in people’s knowledge, and thus give them the necessary space to do their job. Leader C also mentioned that they found it important to give followers space so that they felt free to talk whilst Leader E pointed out that they did not want to seem as though they were ‘micromanaging’. However, employees did not mention that they felt it necessary for their leaders to give them space, as such. Additionally, seeking advice and contribution from followers was also deemed necessary to aid the empowerment of employees. Leader L described this as the following:

“Seek the opinions of the people that work for me, and make a decision based on that advice” (Leader L).

Leader D echoed this sentiment, although rather than taking on the advice of the followers they saw it more as taking contributions from the followers:

“I found that I often get the ball rolling and polish that into a better idea with contributions from others” (Leader D).

The notion of advice and contribution was deemed to be important by two leaders, but it was not mentioned as being of importance from the employees. It was also

noted that to encourage empowerment it was important to delegate responsibility to the followers. This was seen as important by 10 leaders and eight employees.

Empowerment can be summarised by Leader B, who stated:

“I think that the organisation does try to empower everybody that it employs” (Leader B).

Furthermore, empowerment was discussed in terms of further training and learning new skills. This was mentioned by two employees:

“I’ve got first-hand experience that he allows employees to improve themselves and develop” (Employee I)

“In terms of encouraging people to use their skills to train to do other things, I would imagine if I said I wanted to do a course in whatever, somebody would say somewhere I can look at that at fact that’s something I’m doing the moment”
(Employee K)

Overall, empowerment is deemed important for both leaders and employees for people management and development.

4.7.2 EMPLOYEE DEVELOPMENT

Employee development was recognised as a necessary subskill important for people management and development. Most of the leaders and a majority of employees found employee development to be important.

Five leaders and one employee thought that the best way to develop their employees was by investing in them. Leader A summarised this by stating:

“We have invested in people. I’ve brought some new team members into the teams, done some basic training and had services come in and do that” (Leader A).

Leader C explained that they had invested in people through the development of a skills academy and believed they had done this through investing in qualifications for employees. Employee B believed that her leaders investing in them was the best way to show their commitment to their development. However, it is interesting to note that out of the five leaders who suggested that investing in their employees was important for development, there was recognition that more could be done to invest in their employees in order to further their empowerment.

Rewarding employees was also highlighted as an important tool for aiding their development by 10 leaders and one employee. Leader E believed that rewarding employees was necessary for them to carry out his job role, and six other leaders believed that rewarding their employees was necessary. Employee B also stated that rewarding employees was important in managing and developing people.

An example of this can be seen by the statement from Leader M:

“I think the line is, ‘Get the best out of them, nurture them and reward them’” (Leader M).

10 leaders believed that it was necessary to develop their employees through training. This was highlighted by Leader B, who stated:

“We do an awful lot of development, we do quite a lot, but in a way it’s a kind of maintenance development of the existing staff and the skillsets that they have and updating them and keeping them up to date” (Leader B).

This was also linked to investing in people, by way of training. Leader C highlighted that this was necessary, explaining:

“It’s that freedom of investing in the people, because they are actually quite hard to get” (Leader C).

Three other leaders agreed that investing in people was important for their development. However, it should be noted that investing in employees was not raised by the employees who participated.

Investing in people can also be linked to promoting employees to aid their development. This link was highlighted by Leader A, who stated:

“We bring them on and invest in them and try and get them to reach their full potential. So yeah, definitely, I’m a great believer in promoting from within you know if people...” (Leader A).

This was also echoed by Employee B, who stated:

“I think there’s like that encouragement and promotion in the business. Like, I’ve only been here under a year, but I’ve seen there’s quite quick progress, I would say, which is quite encouraging” (Employee B).

The concept of potential promotion was also mentioned by Employee M when he explained:

“We are all encouraged to be leaders in our own field; hopefully develop on to be an actual leader” (Employee M)

Finally, it was also noted that coaching employees was necessary for their development. Leader C stated that:

“I spend most of my time coaching” (Leader C).

This was echoed by two other leaders; however, it was not a sentiment which was echoed by any employee in the interviews. Overall, it can be said that servant leadership impacts on SME performance by encouraging employee development and promotion.

4.7.3 MOTIVATING PEOPLE

A further aspect which was deemed necessary for people management and development was the ability to motivate people to work harder and contribute. This was thought to be of more importance by leaders than employees, as it was mentioned by 10 leaders and only 7 employees.

The concept of motivation was best summarised by Leader G, who stated:

“I think in principle a high level of motivation. I would say that one... if you don't have the motivation, however clever you might be, you won't succeed. That's my experience” (Leader G).

This was echoed by four other leaders and one employee who believed that motivating people was an important skill in general. A subtheme which emerged with regards to motivating people was involvement with their employees. Employee A described her leaders' involvement in the following statement:

“You might be facing...yeah there's definitely a lot of involvement you know, not necessarily in the office working 9-5 Monday to Friday, but you know as I say you can always pick up the phone with any problem that you're up against” (Employee A).

This notion was echoed by two further employees and two leaders who all agreed that involvement with the employees was necessary for servant leaders. It was also highlighted that employees should be inspired by their leaders. Employee A, when asked about how she thought his leader had contributed to the success of her organisation, replied saying:

“They've got empathy, they inspire others” (Employee A).

Leader K also believed that by working extra shifts and attending his company's events that they would inspire the employees, stating:

“There’s a passion there, hopefully that inspires the team because I do think it’s important to be seen within the community” (Leader K).

It was also deemed important to energise employees and encourage their energy in order to motivate them. Leader D explained this as:

“I am quite energetic and driven but I’ve certainly evolved in terms of recognising that a huge part of my role is to actually to make other people successful” (Leader D).

Leader G believed a similar idea explainin:

“I need to be the most motivated person around so in leading other people they often rely upon my level of motivation to do their bit” (Leader G)

This was also confirmed by two leaders and three employees, who also believed that the leader’s role was concerned with inspiring others.

Overall, both leaders and employees found motivating people to be an important skill with regards to people management and development.

4.8 ORGANISATIONAL IMPACT OF SERVANT LEADERSHIP

Through analysing the skills apparent within the research this chapter will now proceed to explore how the findings indicated the organisational impact of servant leadership. It will examine this in respect to employee work climates, organisational citizenship behaviour, public service motivation and organisational growth.

4.8.1 EMPLOYEE WORK CLIMATES

It was found that servant leadership impacted on performance of SMEs by way of organisational development, in terms of making organisations leaner, and advocating cultural change within an organisation. The servant leaders in the research were shown to be able to both advocate for and implement cultural change, thus creating more harmonious and open working environments. This is highlighted by Leader D who stated, with regards to employee turnover:

“I think the environment its created is, they don’t feel like numbers, they feel like they are at least valued, and they are treated as human beings not as robots and I think that’s what’s made a difference and that’s why we have a low turnover of staff”
(Leader D).

It was also found that people management and development enabled leaders to manage teams effectively, as stated by Employee E:

“How they show or manage themselves or work around themselves, or how they manage like everyone else from the office, but I’d say yeah.” (Leader E).

This efficiency and effectiveness can be said to be enabling the creation of harmonious employee work climates.

Additionally, as previously mentioned, it was found that servant leaders should be honest in order to communicate. Leader A describes this as:

“in a really healthy way you know being really open and honest and having conversations” (Leader A).

It can be said that having honesty and communication can lead to a more amicable and open workplace, thus enhancing the employee work climate.

4.8.2 ORGANISATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR

Trust was highlighted as important for promoting organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) within the data. Leader F further emphasised this by stating:

“really that questions more about whether people are willing to trust you and to work with you and to take your lead and to follow you in” (Leader F).

Trust promotes OCB and leads to employees being more willing to align with the organisation and the leader’s vision. This can be said to impact upon performance in SMEs as it ensures that leaders are generating vision for the future and bringing the relevant parties on board with this. This is shown by Leader F:

“What they can do with understanding is set tone and set direction and set pace and these are all slightly different things. So, tone is like the way an organisation describes itself and how, therefore, it’s perceived and, depending on the industry and sector you work in, that can be more or less important. If you’re selling widgets, it’s still important but if you’re talking to people about lifestyle or environment or things it’s probably even more important. When you say direction, what are we doing, what does the next year look like, what are we trying to achieve in the next two years, what’s the five-year plan” (Leader F).

Additionally, the concept of people management and development is echoed by Employee B as contributing to the success of the organisation and empowering his employees:

“They do kind of understand it takes all your staff to make an organisation successful and develop so they do try to take the staff on board with them at every level” (Employee B).

Additionally, empowerment was found to impact upon performance within SMEs of the employees, as they feel that they are empowered to partake within the decision-making process. This was further enabled by leaders who stated that they gave their

employees space and flexibility to further their empowerment. This in turn encourages positive OCB.

4.8.3 PUBLIC SERVICE MOTIVATION

Serving in the community was highlighted as a necessary skill for servant leadership, with regards to servanthood. This in turn can be said to be representative of an increase in public service motivation.

Public service gave businesses a positive local reception within the community. Whether this was by giving back or hiring locally, leaders believed that public service motivation helped to positively impact the organisation. It has also been mentioned that leaders felt the need to serve in their communities, particularly those in lower socio-economic areas. This has previously been discussed within this chapter but is further validated by Employee C who states:

“Hiring local people there so that gelled with the local council, it’s the right way of doing it”

Therefore, it is apparent that servant leadership improves public service motivation within organisations.

4.8.4 ORGANISATIONAL GROWTH

Organisational growth and success was a prominent theme which emerged in the literature with regards to an organisational impact of servant leadership, cited by the majority of both leaders and employees.

This was initially highlighted by Leader D who discussed the need for investment to grow the organisation:

“I think we recognise, at the stage of growth we’re at as an organisation, that we need to make further investment in that. The organisation has grown quite organically from a concept and a philosophy, now its needing to hold on to that and not lose that DNA but its needing to invest” (Leader D).

Leader E also discussed the need for organisational success and growth by stating that he has been responsible for growth in the organisation:

“I think I know how to get this business from 16 to 25 just be exponential growth doing what we do now, but if you said to me, you get the business to get into Europe and to get 150 million within 5 years either through acquisitions or through this or that, I would say, I would go and hire a guy that’s got a proven track record of doing that” (Leader E).

The technical skills which were identified, such as education and professional experience, allowed servant leaders to implement their knowledge within their organisations, thereby enhancing growth and progress. This is highlighted by Leader B, who states:

“We started from nothing and we are now a fully functioning and successful and well-respected organisation. My leadership has contributed in a sense sort of my approach from a compliance perspective you know finance background is about controls, people know boundaries, know approaches and that’s fine, and that’s my leadership in directing that” (Leader B).

Aspects of conceptual skills such as organisational development were shown to be able to make organisations leaner and thus perform more effectively. This was highlighted by Leader L, who explained:

“Well, we, two years ago we were a 38-million-pound turnover organisation, we’ve changed the central structure, the central business support process to lean and agile process. So, it’s much more an efficient system supporting everybody and as a result of that ironically our turnover has gone up to 42 million, so another 4 million” (Leader L).

Furthermore, innovation allowed for organisations to stand out from the competition via means such as technology or implementing new ideas. This again allowed for organisational growth.

Overall, it was highlighted that servant leadership positively impacts on organisational growth and development.

4.9: CONCLUSION

4.9.1: RESEARCH OBJECTIVE 1 AND RESEARCH QUESTION 2

With regards to research objective 1 and research question 2 that are concerned with the skills of servant leadership within SMEs, this chapter has shown that these skills are interpersonal skills, conceptual skills, technical skills, people management and development and servanthood. These, alongside various subskills, have been discussed in detail throughout this chapter. These were the most prominent skills that were determined by both leaders and employees as necessary for servant leadership within SMEs.

4.9.2: RESEARCH OBJECTIVE 2 AND RESEARCH QUESTION 3:

This chapter has also addressed research objective 2 and research question 3 which are concerned with the impact of servant leadership upon organisations and organisational performance. As detailed, most of the leaders stated that servant leadership has impacted positively upon their organisations. The ways in which servant leadership impacts upon performance were determined to be employee work climates, organisational citizenship behaviour, public service motivation and organisational growth. This highlights that overall the research has shown that servant leadership has a positive impact upon organisations and organisational performance.

4.9.3: CONCLUSION

This chapter has highlighted the results of the interviews conducted with 30 leaders and employees. It has addressed the skills necessary for servant leadership, as well as the impact of these skill set in their organisation. This research will now proceed to answer the remaining research objectives and questions within the discussion chapter. The discussion chapter will also relate the findings of the study with prior literature in servant leadership.

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSION

5.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter will now proceed to provide a discussion, based upon the findings outlined within Chapter 4. As previously mentioned, leadership is a field which is continuously under development (Harrison, 2018). It has been found that the field is particularly lacking with regards to servant leadership and, more specifically, the skills of servant leaders (Mcquade et al., 2020). As also discussed, the skills era was founded by Katz (1955) and whilst this has been expanded upon with regards to other aspects of leadership, the research regarding the skills necessary for servant leadership remains in its infancy (Mcquade et al., 2020). Whilst skills have been discussed with regards to servant leadership, this is limited, focusing on only one skill, or lacking in empirical validation (Bottum and Lenz, 1998; Gigliotti and Dwyer, 2016; Hu and Liden, 2011). By analysing the findings of the research, this chapter will contribute to the literature, regarding both servant leadership and skills. It will achieve this through discussing and presenting a framework of the skills necessary for servant leadership as this is currently lacking in the field (Mcquade et al., 2020).

This chapter therefore aims to present an analysis of the research findings presented in Chapter 4 in conjunction with the relevant literature in the field. It aims to address the research objectives and questions which have not yet been discussed and expand upon those which were addressed within the previous chapter, in conjunction with the relevant literature.

5.2 MOST PROMINENT SKILLS FOR SERVANT LEADERS IN SMES

Although Chapter 4 determined that the skills necessary for servant leadership were: technical skills; conceptual skills; interpersonal skills; servanthood and people management and development, it is important to explore the skills necessary for servant leadership in more detail with regards to the existing literature, in order to determine how this research has contributed to the field. This will also further address Research Objective 1:

To identify the skills necessary for servant leadership in SMEs

and Research Question 2:

- *What are the most prominent skills for servant leaders within SMEs?*

Servant leadership is a leadership research stream which is receiving increasing scholarly interest (Wu et al., 2013). The review of servant leadership literature presented in Chapter 4 highlighted the main streams of discussion within this field. A significant finding of the literature review was the deficit of empirical research concerning the skills necessary for servant leadership. This research will now proceed to address this deficit.

5.3 TECHNICAL SKILLS

Technical skills were first determined as an area of study necessary for leadership by Katz (1955). It has since been determined as an important consideration when taking into account a leader's performance (Bass, 1990; Harrison, 2018; Katz, 1974). Technical skills generally consist of business, information or product knowledge. They are formed via formal education, work experience and the relevant training (Yukl, 2010). The concept of education has been discussed at length in the servant leadership literature (Austell, 2009; Buchen, 1998; Certosimo, 2009; Crippen, 2004; Hays, 2008; Paul et al., 2013; Punnachet, 2009; Simmons and Branch, 2015; Stoten, 2013; Zhou et al., 2015 etc.). However, the overarching theme of technical skills, with its subsequent sub themes is exclusive to this research. The subthemes included within technical skills can be seen below in Figure 5.1:

FIGURE 5.1 TECHNICAL SKILLS

5.3.1 EDUCATION

Education was identified as a prominent theme both within the servant leadership literature, and within this research, and both leaders and employees have deemed it to be important (Austell, 2009; Buchen, 1998; Certosimo, 2009; Crippen, 2004; Hays, 2008; Paul et al., 2013; Punnachet, 2009; Simmons and Branch, 2015; Stoten, 2013; Zhou et al., 2015 etc.) It is important to note that this is largely concerned with servant leadership practiced within an educational setting. This research focused more upon the education servant leaders receive or continue to receive. To give some examples, Buchen (1998) examines servant leadership in educational institutions; Hays (2008) investigated servant leadership in higher education; Punnachet (2009) looks at catholic servant leadership in education; Simmons and Branch (2015) examined servant leadership in correctional education and Certosimo (2009) looks at servant leadership in dental education. Thus, this research takes a different perspective with regards to education by examining the education of servant leaders rather than the education that they give to others.

The research also found that continuous learning and education was important for servant leaders, to continue their development and improve upon their technical skills. This was discussed through means such as learning from others, learning from cultures and learning from organisations. Again, this was unique to the research as education in terms of the servant leader is an underdeveloped area of study in the field.

5.3.2 PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

As mentioned within the findings chapter, there were different manners of professional experience which were discussed. One of these was military experience. The concept of servant leadership and military experience is also discussed within the literature (Patterson, 2003). However, it is important to point out that the servant leaders in the research largely discussed how their experience within the military had helped shape their servant leadership, whereas existing research explores servant leadership within the military. The same can also be said for healthcare organisations, which again are discussed with respect to being servant leader-led, rather than with regards to their impact on the servant leaders experience (Certosimo, 2009; Gunnarsdottir, 2014; Farrington and Lillah, 2018; McCann et al., 2014; Mueller and Min, 2011; Savel and Munro, 2017; Sturm, 2008). In a more general sense, servant leaders highlighted that their professional experiences in organisations had contributed to their skills as a servant leader, which is a finding which has not yet been determined by the servant leadership literature.

Leaders spoke of taking inspiration from mentors in their lifetime which helped them to build upon their servant leadership. Servant leaders in the research also stated that their professional experiences had been developed by being mentored by, and inspiration from other leaders. Whilst the notion of servant leaders mentoring others has also been touched upon in prior studies, this research found that servant leaders being mentored impacted upon their professional development and experience.

5.3.3 REFLEXIVITY

Reflexivity was deemed a necessary subskill of technical skills by the majority of the leaders and employees within the research. It is a finding which has not yet been examined in the field, thus it is exclusive to this research. This research found that servant leaders reflect on their experiences to further advance their leadership. They learn from the past to improve their leadership going forward. There was also discussion of leaders observing and reflecting within the organisation to improve their leadership, which again has not yet been explored within the field.

Leaders also discussed observing other organisations and previous leaders whom they had worked for and reflecting upon their practices in order to shape their own approach to leadership. This has previously not been discussed with regards to the existing servant leadership literature. This makes observation a unique finding of this research with regards to servant leadership.

5.4 CONCEPTUAL SKILLS

It is important to note, that whilst lacking in the field of servant leadership, skills have been discussed in detail with regards to other streams of leadership research (Mcquade et al., 2020). This is particularly true with regards to the architect of skills research Katz (1955). As mentioned previously within this research, conceptual skills were outlined by Katz (1955). Conceptual skills are concerned with a more holistic outlook of an organisation. They are largely related to theories, concepts and ideas (Harrison, 2018). They view the entity as a whole and understand how the functions interact (Schedutzki and Edwards, 2014).

Conceptual skills allow for the development of vision and goals for an organisation. Conceptual skills can also be considered to be strategic skills (Mumford et al., 2007). Whilst the notion of conceptualisation has been mentioned before with regards to servant leadership, this is largely with reference to traits, rather than conceptual skills (Greenleaf, 1970; Spears, 1995). Furthermore, Wilson (1999) describes how servant leadership can benefit an organisation's overall strategic plans. However, it should

be noted that this research is lacking in empirical evidence. As discussed within the literature review, Hu and Liden (2011) discuss conceptual skills with regards to servant leadership however this is a relatively brief discussion. Therefore, it can be said that this research is the first which frames the notion of conceptual skills from a general perspective, with the incorporation of the relevant subskills found to be necessary for servant leadership.

Furthermore, the research found that the majority of the leaders and employees interviewed proposed that conceptual skills were important for servant leaders. This highlights the empirical gap that this research has filled with regards to determining a skill considered important for servant leadership by both leaders and employees. Whilst this gap was identified with regards to conceptual skills, there were significant association between some of the sub themes identified with regards to conceptual skills and the existing literature, as seen in Figure 5.2:

FIGURE 5.2 CONCEPTUAL SKILLS

These will now be discussed in further detail.

5.4.1 STRATEGIC SKILLS

Strategic skills were noted as a relevant subskill with regards to conceptual skills. However, it is pertinent to note that almost double the number of leaders found strategic skills to be important, compared to employees. This is echoed in the literature by De Hoogh and Den Hartog (2008) who state that servant leadership is more concerned with followers meeting their goals than it is with decision making, which could be linked to why employees did not find it to be of such high priority.

However, with other elements of strategic skills such as problem solving, there are more definitive views provided in the literature than there is with regards to decision making. Bottum and Lenz (1998) proposed that problem solving is a necessary skill for servant leadership, however as discussed in Chapter 1, unlike this research it is not empirically validated. This is echoed by the research within which, all leaders deemed themselves to be problem solvers and only one employee strongly believed that their leaders were not.

Furthermore, with regards to the research it found that servant leaders tend to surround themselves with the best people available and were concerned with staff placement to ensure that this was possible. This was also echoed by Ross et al. (2014) in the literature who stated servant leaders must select the right people for the right tasks to encourage empowerment. This could be beneficial for leadership in SMEs, which as previously mentioned are generally led by entrepreneurs who often find it difficult to surround themselves with the best people, instead trying to take on everything themselves (Perren and Grant, 2010). This can result in burn out for the leader.

5.4.2 ORGANISATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

Follower contribution as a means of promoting organisational development was discussed at length by the leaders. Some leaders stressed that follower contribution was necessary for both organisational growth and success. The concept of follower

contribution as being necessary for success is one which is echoed in the literature, (Cerit, 2009; Taylor et al., 2007; Sendjaya et al., 2008; Shim et al., 2016; Newman et al., 2017; Winston and Fields, 2015). However, it is important to note that follower contributions with regards to organisational development has not been examined within the context of Scottish SMEs, which makes this finding unique to this research.

The research found that servant leaders deemed it important to implement and help manage change within their SMEs. The concept of change and servant leadership is not discussed within the literature. However, it can be said to be important to leaders in SMEs as they need to be flexible and open to change (Mesu et al., 2015).

Additionally, the research found that employees did not provide much information on organisational growth and development and servant leadership compared to the leaders, who generally agreed that there is a link between the two. However, the research generally found that with regards to servant leadership impact on performance in SMEs, it can be said that it impacts positively with regards to organisational development and growth.

5.4.3 INNOVATION

A further prominent subskill which was identified within the findings chapter was innovation. It is also discussed within the servant leadership literature with regards to being an outcome for an organisation (Anderson, 2009; Sendjaya et al., 2018). Sendjaya et al. (2018) found that servant leadership results in creativity and innovation, in studies which were based in organisations in the Western and Eastern context. Anderson (2006) also found that an organisational outcome of servant leadership is creativity and innovation. Newman et al. (2017) discusses the idea that servant leadership leads to empowerment, which in turn leads to innovation in the organisation (Newman et al., 2017). However, it is a unique finding for this research due to its context and its empirical validation.

As mentioned in the previous chapter, leaders believed that it was important for servant leaders to have an awareness of their industry and their competition to innovate. To some extent this is echoed in the literature by Spears (2010) who states that servant leaders should have awareness as one of their key characteristics. However, it should be noted that this research is not validated empirically. The awareness referred to by Spears (2010) is concerned with the servant leader's awareness of him or herself. This research determined that servant leaders need an awareness of their industry in terms of advancement, competition and future projections in order for them to innovate. This means that the identification of awareness in this respect as necessary for servant leaders to innovate is unique to this research. It also highlights the value of servant leadership in SMEs, because as previously stated, leaders with SMEs generally lack awareness, particularly with regards to what is available to them (Wilson, 2014).

It was also shown that to innovate, servant leaders should be both proactive and productive. This is echoed in the literature by Zhen and Luo (2018) who found that servant leadership positively influences both individual and team proactiveness.

5.4.4 ENVISIONING

The notion of servant leaders and envisioning is not unique to this research, however rather than the skill of envisioning being discussed, it is largely the exhibition of behaviours which encourage vision that is discussed within the literature (Bass, 1990; Greenleaf, 1977; Falling et al., 1999; Page and Wong, 2000; Russell and Stone, 2002). This research however discusses the skill of envisioning as opposed to having a vision. This was discussed by participants in a practical sense, with examples given by leaders on issues such as Brexit, where they would need to envision what could be deemed important in the future. It was also practical in terms of identifying opportunities in the industry and being able to envision with regards to the competition, which was not evident in the existing literature.

Prior research talks about servant leaders having vision for the organisation and the followers. This research found this largely to be the case with regards to participants. However, this study found this to be more expansive and showed that servant

leaders were also concerned with involving their stakeholders in their envisioning process. This study also found that leaders envisioned in order to change attitudes within organisations. By presenting a vision to their followers, it was stated that they would be able to change existing mindsets. Again, this was a unique finding of this research.

5.5 INTERPERSONAL SKILLS

Interpersonal (or human) skills are the means through which human experiences, and the experiences between a leader and their employee are formed (Harrison, 2018). They are concerned with the knowledge and ability to work with other people (Harrison, 2018). It is the understanding of people and groups on an emotional level (Harrison, 2018). Interpersonal skills involve negotiating with, influencing, reconciling differences and working alongside those around you (Copeman, 1971; Mintzberg, 1973; Northouse, 2010). It can be summarised as the ability to coordinate your own actions in line with those of others (Mumford et al., 2007).

Interpersonal skills are considered necessary for leadership (Katz, 1955). Similar to technical skills, whilst aspects of interpersonal skills have been discussed in prior studies this was not in a general sense and it was not done with regards to the subskills discussed in this research. Thus, the notion of interpersonal skills as a concept linked to servant leadership is a finding of this research. The subskills discussed within interpersonal skills in this research were communication, empathy, teambuilding and nurturing, which are highlighted in the Figure 5.3. below:

FIGURE 5.3 INTERPERSONAL SKILLS

5.5.1 COMMUNICATION

Communication was identified by the research as a necessary subskill for interpersonal skills and was also identified as a skill necessary for servant leadership by both Gigliotti and Dwyer (2016) and Bottum and Lenz (1998). However, it is important to note that Gigliotti and Dwyer's (2016) research is based in North America and only within one institution and Bottum and Lenz' (1998) work is not empirically validated. Therefore, with regards to organisational scope and empirical evidence, this research differs from that which is already existing. Communication has also been discussed in a more general sense with regards to servant leadership, however not with regards to it as a necessary skill (Greenleaf, 1970; Russell and Stone, 2002). Again, highlighting communication as a necessary interpersonal subskill which has been validated by the existing literature and has also been expanded upon in this study

For effective communication, the research found it was necessary to listen to followers. It was highlighted by leaders that it is necessary to listen to their employees. This finding is validated by the existing research by Bottum and Lenz (1998) who also state that listening is necessary for servant leaders to communicate. Listening is further identified in its own right within the literature, rather than as a

component of communication (Greenleaf, 1970; Russell et al., 2015; Russell and Stone, 2002; Spears, 1995). It was also identified by Sharma and Kwatra (2017) as necessary for healing, rather than communication. Therefore, listening has been perceived in a different way within this research than it is within the general literature.

Participants also noted that in communicating you need to be open and approachable to those within an organisation. This was not found within the existing literature. It may be useful for leaders within SMEs as it has been previously noted in that they are often unwilling to open up to new shareholders (Ang, 1992). Similarly, the notion of networking was also apparent in this research but not in the servant leadership literature. Again, this subskill could be beneficial for leaders in SMEs in line with the EU commission's recommendations that networking in SMEs should be worked upon, which this research found that servant leaders are able to do (European Commission, 2018).

It was found that honesty was necessary for communication. Within the literature, Russell and Stone (2002) discuss honesty as a characteristic of servant leadership, as opposed to a skill of communication, which was determined in this research. Burton and Peachey (2013) and Jaramillo et al. (2009) also found that honesty from servant leaders resulted in positive work climates, again, this is with regards to outcome, rather than communication as this research found.

5.5.2 EMPATHY

Empathy was determined to be an important subskill of communication by both employees and leaders. It has also been determined as necessary for servant leadership within the wider research (Barbuto and Wheeler, 2006; Mittal and Dorfman, 2010; Spears, 1995; Spears, 2010; Washington et al., 2006; Wilson, 1999). However, it should be noted that the majority of these research's evidence are not empirical, compared to this study (Spears, 1995; Spears, 2010). Furthermore, the geographical location of the existing research differs from this research's Scottish context, having been validated in South Africa and North

America, across different cultures and within school environments (Barbuto and Wheeler, 2006; Mittal and Dorfman, 2010).

Moreover, the research determined that empathy was necessary for emotional intelligence within servant leadership. This was echoed within the findings chapter, as emotional intelligence was discussed numerous times, as is also the case within the literature where it is named as a necessary skill for servant leadership (Barbuto et al., 2014; Mukanoweshuro, 2016; Pressis et al., 2015; Rose, 2017; Shamshad, 2016). However, this is out with the concept of interpersonal skills, which this research has found it to be intrinsically linked to.

5.5.3 TEAMBUILDING

Teambuilding was found largely to be important by the leaders in this research, rather than the employees. Therefore, it is arguable that it could be deemed to be an important skill for leaders but be of little concern to their followers. The concept of teams is frequently referred to in the literature in a number of ways. For example, team performance (Irving and Longbotham, 2007; Liden et al., 2015; Song et al., 2015), team conflict management (Wong et al., 2016), teamwork (John, 2011; Russell and Stone, 2002) and team creativity (Yang et al., 2017). Teambuilding is discussed by Page and Wong (2000) with regards to servant leadership, however it is important to note that, as previously mentioned in the systematic literature review, this consisted of a small sample size and was only empirically tested in a pilot study. Thus, making these research findings the most thoroughly validated with respect to teambuilding in servant leadership.

One way in which it was found that leaders could help build teams was through generating trust. Whilst trust is discussed within the literature, this is largely in an organisational performance or outcome perspective (Beck, 2014; Bobbio et al., 2012; Chan and Mak, 2014; Joseph and Winston, 2005; Kashyap and Rangnekar, 2009; Reinke, 2004; Sendjaya and Pekertie, 2010; Shim et al., 2016). However, unlike the existing studies, this research frames trust as necessary for teambuilding, as this is determined by the research participants.

The research also found that sharing the workload and power sharing with employees helped to build teams. Delegation and power sharing are discussed within the literature with regards to servant leaders (Bass, 1990; Ling et al., 2017; Noland and Richards, 2015; Page and Wong, 2000; Russell and Stone 2002). These are not discussed in terms of interpersonal skills or as a necessity for team building, as was found to be the case within this research.

Leaders and employees proposed socialising as necessary for teambuilding. They discussed this in a sense of both socialising in the workplace and at outside events. This has not been proposed in the existing field meaning that this research has identified socialising as necessary for teambuilding and in turn, interpersonal skills.

5.5.4 NURTURING

The concept of nurturing followers in general was not found within the existing literature, however, concepts such as empowerment and development are (Bass, 1990; Cerit, 2009; Dennis and Bocarnea, 2005; Winston and Fields, 2015; Focht, 2015; Harrison, 2018; Heidai et al., 2013; Mittal and Dorfman, 2012; Olesia et al., 2014; Patterson, 2003; Ross et al., 2014; Russell, 2001; Russell and Stone, 2002; Sendjaya et al., 2008; Taylor et al., 2007; Sousa and van Dierendonck, 2017; Van Dierendonck and Nuijten, 2011; Van Winkle et al., 2014; Walker, 2015; Washington et al., 2015). Although similar, nurturing can be said to be more concerned with a general sense of caring for someone, rather than encouraging their promotion within an organisation.

Leaders stated that for their employees to feel that they are being nurtured, they felt it necessary to be accommodating. These were described in the following ways such as being available to talk, being flexible, providing a relaxing atmosphere in the workplace. This concept was not discussed within the literature with regards to empowerment or development, and as previously mentioned not with regards to nurturing, thus making it a unique finding within this research.

There was also discussion of providing guidance to the followers so as to nurture them. Farling et al. (1999) discusses providing guidance, however this is with regards to implementing vision, rather than in order to nurture. It was also stated that to nurture, leaders should be patient. Again, this was found as necessary by Van Dierendonck and Patterson (2014), but this was with respect to showing love as opposed to nurturing. This highlights that in general the skill of nurturing was largely unique to the findings of this research.

5.6 SERVANTHOOD

Servanthood has been stated to be the biblical definition of servant leadership. Within the bible, Greek words are often used to describe leaders as servants (Sendjaya et al., 2008). Servanthood has been defined as being concerned with serving both the group and the vision of the organisation (Wright, 1996). Rather than insinuating a low position, servanthood refers to voluntary subordination on behalf of others (Vine, 1985). Servanthood is often used interchangeably with servant leadership. It has been highlighted that just because one is service orientated, does not necessarily make one a servant leader (Hall, 1991; Page and Wong, 2000).

With its connotations with regards to servant leadership, it is unsurprising that servanthood emerged as a theme during the thematic analysis of the data and deemed a necessity as a skill for servant leaders. There were two prominent subthemes which emerged as important for servanthood within the literature which are detailed in Figure 5.4.

FIGURE 5.4: SERVANTHOOD

5.6.1 SERVING IN THE COMMUNITY

The research largely identified two subskills which were highlighted by the participants as necessary for servanthood. As detailed within the findings chapter, the first of these was serving within the community. It is unsurprising that this concept emerged, particularly within SMEs, as it was earlier detailed that SMEs are heavily influenced by the cultural and political aspects of their local communities (Barrett and Rainnie, 2002). Much of the existing literature however focuses upon servant leaders being able to build and generate a sense of community (Bottum and Lenz; Brubaker, 2013; Laub, 1999; Spears, 1995). Whilst some literature does exist which focuses upon serving in the community this is limited. Olesia et al. (2014) states that it is important to serve in the community to ensure that you are inspiring others. This was not deemed to be a reason behind serving in the community within this research. Additionally, Chen and Mak (2014) outline servant leaders' motivation to public service. Also within the existing literature community building is discussed in a number of different contexts such as healthcare, (McCann et al., 2014; Sturm,

2006); sport (Burton and Peachey, 2013; Crippen, 2017; Rieke et al., 2006; Robinson et al., 2018) and in nature (Chung et al., 2010). Yet, the context of community in SMEs is unique to this research as it was proven to be important by both leaders and employees.

As discussed within the findings chapter, numerous leaders, particularly those whose organisations operate within lower socio-economic areas, believed that it was important for their organisations to serve within the community so as to generate good will. Whilst doing good deeds and serving in the community was discussed in the literature, this was not done specifically with regards to giving back or generating good will in the community, making this a unique finding to the literature.

Furthermore, this research identified serving in the community as a means of promoting visibility or due to a sense of corporate social responsibility. These findings were, again, exclusive to this research.

5.6.2 SERVING PEOPLE

As well as serving in the community, serving people was identified as a necessary component for servanthood. The concept of serving people is discussed frequently within the literature, so the fact that it emerged within the research is not surprising. Vine (1985) states that service and voluntary subordination is everything for the servant leader whether this is serving subordinates or customers. This is echoed by Winston and Fields (2015) who explained that serving others is highly important and necessary for the servant leader. As mentioned in the systematic literature review, Wright (2008) also states that servanthood is concerned with serving the group.

Greenleaf explains that servant leadership is about serving the needs of others, over the organisation (Greenleaf, 1970). The notion of serving others has also been discussed in religious contexts such as within Islam and Christianity, within sports teams, and healthcare (Burton and Peachey, 2013; Crippen, 2017; McCann et al., 2014; Rieke et al., 2008; Robinson et al., 2018; Sturm, 2006). Therefore, the notion

of serving people which was determined within this research was also confirmed by the existing literature.

The research found that some leaders believed that to serve people it was necessary for them to care for their employees, which was a unique finding to this research, as was mentoring employees and consistency. These findings have not yet been examined within the field of servant leadership literature.

The research also highlighted the need for leaders to adhere to their own values whilst serving others. The concept of values occurs frequently within the literature, as does the idea that servant leadership is driven by values (Hays, 2008; Mertel and Brill, 2015; Russell, 2001; Washington et al., 2006). It has been discussed with regards to enabling the creation of a value-based culture in an NHL hockey team (Crippen, 2016), imparting values in the military (Vadell and Ewing, 2011), and in a spiritual sense (Fry et al., 2007). As mentioned in the literature review, the seminal works concerning servant leadership and values are not validated empirically, which makes this research unique in this respect. Furthermore, whilst values are discussed at length within the literature, this has not yet been examined within the context of the Scottish SME, which was done within this research.

Flexibility was identified by both employees and leaders as important for leaders to serve people. This has been echoed in the literature by Anderson (2006), however it is not an extensive theme which is explored in depth. Due to the flexible nature of SMEs and the cultures that they create, it could be argued that it is necessary for the servant leader within an SME to be flexible, which has been shown to be the case within this research (Carrier 1994; Van Strate, 1997).

5.7 PEOPLE MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT

The skill of people management and development was recognised by this research, as discussed within the findings chapter. To lead effectively, it is necessary to develop and manage people (Harrison, 2018). Role modelling and leading by example are considered to be important elements of people management and

development as determined by Harrison (2018). They are also important for the servant leaders in order to effectively carry out their duties (Erhart, 2004; Schwarz et al., 2016).

To effectively manage people and develop them, it is necessary for the leader to understand the training needs of the followers (Hejazi et al., 2012). It is also necessary for servant leaders to understand the needs of their followers to serve and empower them. Approaches to leadership have been discussed previously in specific reference to SMEs, finding that whilst there is no universality to the management styles they adopt, they generally consist of a more entrepreneurial management approach (Carter and Evans, 2006). This research finds that as of yet, there is a gap in the literature concerning people management and development in SMEs which was identified as a skill necessary for servant leadership. Furthermore, this concept in its entirety has not yet been linked to servant leadership within the existing literature. The following subskills (See Figure 5.5) were identified as necessary for people management and development:

FIGURE 5.5 PEOPLE MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT

They will now be discussed with regards to the literature.

5.7.1 EMPOWERMENT

Empowerment emerged as a subtheme of people management and development, and this is validated by the literature, wherein it is also a prominent theme (Bass, 1990; Cerit, 2009; Dennis and Bocarnea; Winston and Fields, 2015; Focht, 2015; Harrison, 2018; Heidai et al., 2013; Mittal and Dorfman, 2012; Olesia et al., 2014; Patterson, 2003; Ross et al., 2014; Russell, 2001; Russell and Stone, 2002; Sendjaya et al., 2008; Taylor et al., 2007; Sousa and van Dierendonck, 2017; Van Dierendonck and Nuijten, 2011; Van Winkle et al., 2014; Walker, 2015; Washington et al., 2015). It has also been identified as necessary for servant leadership in SMEs by McNeff and Irving (2017), further validating this research's findings.

Leaders and employees discussed how important it was for servant leaders to have respect for and engender respect from their employees, which would in turn led to the employees feeling empowered. Being respectful is also mentioned by Lanctot and Irving (2010) within the literature, providing further confirmation that respect is necessary for servant leadership. However, it is only within this research that the finding is empirically validated.

Giving space and distancing themselves from employees was deemed necessary by leaders for empowering employees within the research. The concept of servant leaders in SMEs providing autonomy to their employees was also echoed in the literature by van Winkle et al. (2014). Whilst this is arguably similar, it is not framed under people management and development skills, as was found to be the case within this research.

Additionally, the notion of seeking advice and contribution from the followers which was discussed in the findings, is echoed by the research conducted by Van Winkle et al. (2014). Van Winkle et al. (2014) found that within SMEs which are ran by servant leaders, employees need to feel as though they are impacting upon organisations. However, it is important to note that Van Winkle et al's. (2014) research was conducted in the North American context; meaning this research is unique with regards to its geographical context.

5.7.2 EMPLOYEE DEVELOPMENT

The concept of employee development in order to empower employees, was determined by the research and is also prevalent within other studies (Bareas et al., 2017; Graham, 1991; van Dierendonck, 2011). It is unsurprising that employee development emerged as a subtheme which was confirmed by both leaders and employees. This is due to the fact that it has been stated that servant leadership is concerned with the development of others, rather than oneself (Graham, 1991).

Investing in employees was brought up by leaders and employees with regards to financially investing in their development. Whilst development has been discussed in the literature, the financial aspect of this has not yet been covered, making it a unique aspect of this research.

Rewarding employees was also discussed by most leaders with respect to employee development. It is important to note that only one employee deemed this to be of relevance, which is perhaps why it is only briefly discussed in the literature. Sihombing et al. (2011) also explored rewarding by servant leaders. This research focused on a bank in Indonesia meaning that this is a unique finding to this research in terms of context and geographical location.

Delegating as a means of enhancing employee development was also deemed to be important by the leaders and employees within this research. This supports the existing literature (Bass, 1990; Ling et al., 2017; Noland and Richards, 2015; Olesia et al., 2014; Page and Wong, 2000; Russell and Stone 2002;). As stated within the literature, leaders in SMEs often lack the ability to delegate, meaning that this research is unique in its finding that within SMEs, servant leaders do in fact can delegate to staff.

Coaching was mentioned by leaders as an integral part of their ability to further develop their followers. Whilst coaching has been discussed within the literature, this is largely concerned with servant leadership in sport (Heideri et al., 2013; Mielke, 2014; Rieke et al., 2008). This research is the first to determine the concept of

servant leaders coaching within a business organisation to promote employee development.

5.7.3 MOTIVATING PEOPLE

Motivating people has been determined as necessary by leaders and employees. It has also been explored at length within the existing literature (Awan et al., 2012; Chan and Mak, 2014; Olesia et al., 2014; Patterson, 2003; Rieke et al., 2008). However, this has not yet been explored within the context of servant leadership and SMEs, until this research.

Involvement with employees was identified as necessary for motivating people. This was explained by some participants as being available and visible to their employees within the workplace, rather than remaining in an office. This has not been echoed in the existing literature, making this a unique finding to this research.

Inspiring employees was noted by both leaders and employees as necessary to motivate them, which was mirrored within the literature (Hunter et al., 2013; Monroe, 2013; Patterson, 2003; Sendjaya et al., 2007; Taylor et al., 2007). Taylor et al. (2007) discussed servant leadership in teachers leading to inspiration and Hunter et al. (2013) discussed inspiration as an organisational outcome. However, Patterson's (2003) research found that servant leaders should inspire others which is exactly what was found within this research.

This section therefore satisfies research objective one:

To identify the skills necessary for servant leadership within SMEs

It also addresses research question two:

What are the skills necessary for servant leadership within SMEs?

5.8 ORGANISATIONAL IMPACT OF SERVANT LEADERSHIP ON SMES

The impact of servant leadership on organisations is discussed at length within the literature (Burton et al., 2017; Chan and Mark, 2014; Liu et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2012). It is largely agreed that servant leadership impacts positively on organisations, which was also echoed by the findings of this literature. This research found that the servant leadership impacted on employee work climates; organisational citizenship behaviour; public service motivation and organisational growth. These will now be discussed further.

5.8.1 EMPLOYEE WORK CLIMATES

Within the literature it was found that employee work climates within servant leadership led organisations were positively impacted and led to the creation of a humane workplace (Burton et al., 2017; Burton and Peachey, 2013; Jaramillo et al., 2015; Linesa - Langeros, 2017; Ozyiliaz and Cicek, 2015; Reed et al., 2011). Burton et al. (2017) and Jaramillo et al. (2015), found that honesty of servant leaders created a positive working environment. This research also determined that honesty was necessary for servant leaders in communicating with their followers, which in turn could be argued to impact upon an open work climate. Open climates in the workplace and being approachable were discussed by leaders at length in this research, with regards to communication. However, this was not found in the wider literature. By communicating with their employees, this research has found that servant leaders are able to create a positive employee work climate.

5.8.2 ORGANISATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR

As mentioned in the literature, servant leadership has also been measured with regard to its effects on organisational citizenship behaviour (OCB) (Erhart, 2004; Harwikis, 2015; Newman et al., 2015; Shim et al., 2016; Tuan, 2016 etc.). Shim et al. (2016) determined that trust in servant leaders is necessary to promote organisational citizenship behaviour in organisations. Trust has been stated as a

general outcome of servant leadership behaviours (Beck, 2014; Bobbio et al., 2012; Chan and Mak, 2014; Joseph and Winston, 2005; Kashyap and Rangnekar, 2009; Reinke, 2004; Sendjaya and Pekertie, 2010; Shim et al., 2016).

This was also echoed by this research which found that trust was necessary to promote effective positive organisational citizenship behaviour. This research also identified that giving employees space encouraged their organisational citizenship behaviour as it promoted a sense of empowerment. This research also found that flexibility was necessary in creating organisational citizenship behaviour. Both findings were unique to the literature in the servant leadership domain.

5.8.3 PUBLIC SERVICE MOTIVATION

Green et al. (2015) states that servant leadership should be concerned with the creation of value out with the organisation. Additionally, Chen and Mak (2014) also discuss servant leaders' motivation to public service. This research has discussed at length the necessity of servanthood and serving in the community, which was outlined by the participants, and is validated by the findings of the wider literature. As detailed within this chapter and the findings chapter, the concept of serving in the community was deemed important by both leader and employees. This can be said to be essentially public service, which as discussed in Chapter 4, leaders were motivated to do, for a number of reasons. These included hiring locally, charitable acts, and giving back to the community, with each amounting to public service.

5.8.4 ORGANISATIONAL GROWTH

Organisational development was deemed to be a more important subskill for leaders than it was for employees. Growth and success of organisations were mentioned by leaders, with regards to organisational development, because of their servant leadership. This is echoed in the literature. For example, Harrison (2018) states that servant leadership promotes success in organisations. On the other hand, the literature provides evidence as to where servant leadership has been proven to

promote success in settings such as sports, national service and healthcare (Burton and Peachey, 2013; Chung et al., 2010; Crippen, 2017; McCann et al., 2014; Robinson et al., 2018; Sturm, 2008). It should also be taken into account that, Winston and Fields (2016) state that servant leadership transcends organisational success and is largely more concerned with the follower's wellbeing and development.

This therefore satisfies research objective 2:

To determine the organisational impact of servant leadership in SMEs

Further it answers research question 3:

What is the organisational impact of servant leader's skills' on SMEs?

5.9 THE PROMINENT SKILLS OF SERVANT LEADERSHIP IN SMES FRAMEWORK

As discussed, the skills outlined by Katz (1955); interpersonal, technical and conceptual, are adapted by this research in order to investigate the skills necessary for servant leadership. Furthermore, the research identified two additional skills necessary for servant leadership: servanthood and people management and development. They will be incorporated into the framework, with the addition of skills specific to servant leadership, which were determined within the analysis. It should be noted that Katz (1955) framework has generally been accepted for use within larger organisations, rather than SMEs (Hayton, 2015). However, this research has found that it can be applicable to SMEs, which is particularly useful as it has been found that there is generally an uneven skillset within SMEs (Hayton, 2015).

Whilst research has been conducted with regards to SMEs in servant leadership, as of yet a skills framework has not been developed (Charles, 2015; Claxton, 2014; McNeff and Irving, 2017; Van Winkle et al., 2014). Whilst many frameworks have been developed with regards to servant leadership, this is not the case with the skills necessary for servant leadership (Dennis and Winston, 2003; Irving and

Longbotham, 2007; Liden et al., 2015; Liu et al., 2015; Pekertie and Sendjaya, 2010; Polleys, 2002, Punnachet, 2009; Rai and Prakesh, 2012; Savel and Munro, 2017). Some skills have been discussed but rather than overarching frameworks, these tend to focus on one or two skills specifically (Barbuto et al., 2014; Gigliotti and Dwyer, 2016; Hu and Liden, 2011; Rose, 2017). Within the wider context of leadership, literature and frameworks, concerning skills have been outlined by researchers. (Mumford et al., 2007; Northouse, 2012; Yukl, 2012). As previously mentioned throughout this research, the skills required for servant leadership are only briefly covered within the literature (Barbuto et al., 2014; Bottum and Lenz, 1998; Chinomona et al., 2013; Covey, 1998; Gigliotti and Dwyer; 2016; Pressis et al., 2015; Mukimoweshura, 2016; Shamshad, 2016).

One framework was developed with regards to servant leadership skills, as previously mentioned in Chapter 1, however it is important to note that this research is not empirically validated (Bottum and Lenz, 1998).

This research will now present its framework of the skills necessary for servant leadership, as discussed throughout this research.

FIGURE 5.6 SERVANT LEADERSHIP IN SMES SKILLS FRAMEWORK

The resulting model illustrates the key servant leadership skills identified in the research; technical skills; conceptual skills; interpersonal skills; servanthood and people management and development. Additionally, the model shows a representation of the interaction between servant leaders and the context of SMEs within which they operate in this research. Through this, the model is able to provide a rich and detailed description of servant leadership based on skills.

The skills presented within this model are a result of the triangulation of the perspectives of both leaders and employees. The subskills identified were also the result of discussions with employees and leaders in such SMEs. The skills and subskills outlined within the model form dependent variables which impact upon the success and effectiveness of servant leadership in SMEs. These skills result in organisational success within SMEs being achieved by the servant leader. These skills were identified as being necessary for employee work climates; organisational citizenship behaviour; public service motivation and organisational growth. This model highlights that for SMEs to achieve these outcomes, and thus, organisational success, servant leadership, with the outlined skills, is necessary.

The framework highlights the necessary skills and subskills that this research deemed to be necessary for servant leadership within SMEs.

This satisfies research objective 3:

To develop an empirical based framework of the servant leadership skills necessary for servant leadership within SMEs which contributes to the existing theory

5.10 HOW CAN SERVANT LEADERSHIP BE DEFINED?

It has been stated that servant leadership needs to draw boundaries around itself to allow for the development of a more cohesive concept (Bryant et al., 2016; Fieldman, 2016). Whilst frameworks and concepts of servant leadership have been determined, as previously outlined, there is of yet no one cohesive definition of servant leadership (Dennis and Winston, 2003; Greenleaf, 1970; Irving and Longbotham, 2007; Liden et al., 2015; Liu et al., 2015; Pekertie and Sendjaya, 2010; Polleys, 2002, Punnachet, 2009; Rai and Prakesh, 2012; Savel and Munro, 2017). This research has outlined the skills necessary for servant leadership, the experiences of servant leaders which have enabled them to develop these skills and the effects that this has on organisations. This research therefore defines servant leadership below:

“Servant leadership is a form of leadership which consists of serving the followers in order to empower and develop them, resulting in organisational success”

This satisfies research objective 4:

To provide a definition of servant leadership

And answers research question 1:

How can servant leadership be defined?

5.11 CONCLUSION

This chapter has discussed the findings of the research, in line with the relevant literature. It has further addressed the research questions and objectives and expanded upon the findings of the previous chapter. It has determined the skills necessary for servant leadership, provided an empirical based framework of these skills, along with an overview of the concept of servant leadership and discussed its impact on organisations. This research will now proceed to the final chapter where it will summarise the overall findings of the research.

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION

6.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter will summarise the general content of this thesis before presenting a final overview of the study. The chapter will also demonstrate this study's contribution to knowledge within the field of servant leadership, with regards to its empirical, theoretical and methodological contributions. It will also expand upon the implications this research has for practice as well as acknowledging its limitations. It will conclude by suggesting future research opportunities in the field of servant leadership and skills.

6.2 SUMMARY OF THESIS

This thesis examined the servant leadership paradigm and contributed original, empirical knowledge to further its development.

6.3 RESEARCH AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The aim of this research was to examine servant leadership within SMEs and to determine the necessary skills for organisational success. The research was based in SMEs in Scotland. It investigated the skills necessary for servant leadership in SMEs and the impact that this has on organisations.

The objectives for this research were as follows:

- *To identify the skills necessary for servant leadership within SMEs*
- *To determine the organisational impact of servant leadership on SMEs*
- *To develop an empirical based framework of the servant leadership skills necessary within SMEs which contributes to the existing theory*
- *To provide a definition of servant leadership*

The research questions for this research were:

- *Can servant leadership be defined?*
- *What are the most prominent skills for servant leaders within SMEs?*
- *What is the organisational impact of servant leader's skills' on SMEs?*

This study addressed the research aim through achieving the research objectives and answering the research questions. A systematic literature review of servant leadership provided an extensive overview and understanding of this field and its relevant literature. This consisted of an overview of servant leadership, a breakdown and discussion of the themes identified in the literature, concluding with a thematic analysis. The research also employed semi-structured interviews which were able to explore the experiences of the servant leaders who operated within SMEs. The findings of these interviews were explored at length which allowed for the development of an empirical model of the servant leadership skills necessary in SMEs, within a Scottish context.

6.3.1 LITERATURE REVIEW

As discussed in Chapter 4, an extensive literature review was conducted within this research, in accordance with the research's aim, objectives and questions. It began with an exploration of the field of leadership. This was based on Clark and Harrison's (2018) model which presents a chronological overview of leadership according to its various eras. Clark and Harrison (2018) determined these eras to be Personality; Influence; Behavioural; Transactional; Cultural and Skills. This research expanded upon Clark and Harrison's (2018) eras by also including a Serving era. The research then presented an overview of the literature concerning SMEs, including its various definitions and classifications.

The research then conducted a systematic literature review. This was deemed an appropriate method to employ as it identifies the relevant literature in an explanatory, transparent and heuristic fashion (Tranfield et al., 2003; Usman, 2011). The literature review presented both quantitative and qualitative results. The quantitative results consisted of geographical types; methodological approaches; modes of data

collection; number of publications by year; article citations and journal publications. Whilst one study was found to have been conducted in the United Kingdom, no studies were found to have been conducted specifically in Scotland. The quantitative findings found that 17% of research conducted in the field was qualitative. This highlights that it is an acceptable approach to research within the field, but also one which can be expanded upon. The qualitative analysis consisted of a thematic analysis which included values; literature reviews; behaviour; performance; theoretical and characteristics. The qualitative analysis highlighted a gap in the field with regards to the skills necessary for servant leadership.

6.3.2 METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed by this research was also informed by the research's aim, objectives and questions. The research adopted an inductive approach to link the existing literature to the data gathered in order to generate knowledge (Thomas, 2006). This approach was decided on because this research did not have an existing hypothesis, nor had it conducted any prior observation. This research was also free of any prior conceptions, as a result of the lack of literature and research currently in existence, concerning the skills necessary for servant leadership. This therefore allowed the research to develop the framework of the skills necessary for servant leadership, without the influence or bias of previous works. The research also adopted an interpretivist paradigm, which largely focuses on the meanings within the lived experiences and practices of the participants (Creswell, 2014). This was deemed suitable for this research as it aimed to interpret the data received from the participants in order to determine the skills necessary for servant leadership. In addition, using entirely qualitative methods, a contribution is made to the field with regards to empirical research. This research further adopted a social constructionist and interpretivist philosophy (Saunders et al., 2012). This was deemed appropriate as it is concerned with knowledge which is constructed through interactions with others (McKinley, 2005).

Due to its qualitative nature and interpretivist and social constructionist philosophy this study determined that semi-structured interviews were the most appropriate data

collection method. This was further validated by the fact that semi-structured interviews allow the researcher to explore the more appropriate topics. They also allow the participant to divert and thus divulge more relevant information to the phenomenon (Silverman, 2000). Furthermore, the social constructionist aspect of this research meant this was necessary in order to explore the human element of the participants. The interviews were based on Katz (1955) skills framework. This was used to guide the 30 participants: 15 leaders and 15 employees. The interviews were then transcribed and thematically analysed in accordance with Braun and Clarke's (2006) six stage process. The interview findings provided two main themes: servant leadership skills and the impact of servant leadership on organisations. The skills identified were technical skills; conceptual skills; interpersonal skills; servanthood and people management and development. The impact on organisations identified were employee work climates; organisational citizenship behaviour; public service motivation and organisational growth.

6.4 CONTRIBUTION TO KNOWLEDGE

This research has contributed to the knowledge in a theoretical, empirical and methodological sense. These will now be discussed.

6.4.1 THEORETICAL CONTRIBUTION

The systematic literature review of servant leadership provided an extensive overview of the field as it is at present. Upon completion, it was the first systematic literature review of servant leadership to be replicable, outlining the review protocol undertaken in its entirety.

Whilst the impact of servant leadership on organisations has been researched at length, it has not yet been examined with regards to skills (Al-Mahdy et al., 2016; Amah, 2018; Barbuto et al., 2014; Barbuto and Gifford, 2010; Rodríguez-Carvajal et al., 2018; Crippen, 2017; Dennis and Bocarnea, 2005; Hale and Fields, 2007; Han et al., 2010; Liu et al., 2017; Mehjeirkouni, 2018; Rieke et al., 2008; Rodriguez-Carvajal et al., 2014; Stoten, 1987; Sousa and van Dierendonck, 2014; Xu et al., 2015).

This research contributes theoretically as it conducts an empirical investigation with regards to servant leadership skills and their impact upon organisations.

6.4.2 EMPIRICAL CONTRIBUTION

This study has contributed to the understanding of both servant leadership and skills theory, through its research in SMEs in Scotland. As previously mentioned in Chapter 1, this is geographically and contextually a unique context for this research. These skills have the potential to be applied to larger organisations.

This study also provides a definition of servant leadership which could be used widely in the field by servant leadership researchers. Previously such a definition has been lacking in the field, now one exists which has been empirically validated.

Furthermore, the organisational impacts of servant leadership which have been discussed in this research could potentially be applied to different contexts and compared to other leadership approaches.

6.4.3 METHODOLOGICAL CONTRIBUTION

As noted within the systematic literature review qualitative research is lacking within the field of servant leadership. This research contributed with regards to adding to the qualitative examination within the field. Additionally, the use of semi-structured interviews is limited, as shown in the systematic literature review, which this research employed.

The quantitative analysis provides an in-depth depiction of the current state of the field. The quantitative analysis allowed for an understanding of the most influential researchers in the field, with the number of publications and citations. It also allows for an understanding that servant leadership literature is largely concentrated in the western world and is largely quantitative. Researchers may see these as areas to expand upon in future. The systematic literature review overall contributed in two

significant respects. Firstly, it led to the development of the empirical framework of servant leadership skills and secondly it led to the generation of a definition of servant leadership. Both of these were lacking in the existing literature. Through this, the study contributes to and expands the knowledge within the field.

The research offers a framework which examines servant leadership skills, their relationship to SMEs and impact upon organisations. A framework such as this which has been empirically validated, does not yet exist with the field. Therefore, in a methodological sense this research has built upon the existing knowledge of the phenomenon of servant leadership.

6.5 IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE

The implications for theory from the findings of this research are substantial. It has developed a new area of servant leadership, which could still be further explored. This could be expanded to include other organisational contexts such as large business or non-profit organisations.

6.5.1 IMPLICATIONS FOR SMES

This research has shown that servant leadership positively impacts on SMEs and leaders in SMEs. It can be used by any organisation which may wish to adopt the framework to bolster their organisation's success. SMEs who are looking to generate positive work climates, organisational citizenship behaviour or organisational growth could adopt the framework of this research to positively impact upon their organisations. Furthermore, SMEs wishing to adopt a more moral and follower centric approach to leadership may apply the framework to achieve this.

6.5.2 IMPLICATIONS FOR SERVANT LEADERS

Those who are practicing servant leaders may wish to adopt this research's framework to apply it to their practice and enhance it. It could also be useful for those

wishing to become servant leaders. Furthermore, it is useful for leadership programs as an alternative to heroic leadership for future potential leaders. The findings and the framework can also be used as a learning tool by practitioners of servant leadership, potential future leaders, and as a training aid for employees within the workplace. This research is also useful for those interested in leadership skills, to expand their current narrative, or to conduct comparative research with the existing theory.

6.6 LIMITATIONS OF THE RESEARCH

6.6.1 SAMPLE

Organisations were identified in accordance with the UK SME criteria (Ward and Rhodes, 2014). It could be said that had wider criteria been used, more participants could have been included in the study. It should be noted that as this study was based in Scotland, it was determined that the UK SME definition was the most appropriate.

It is also arguable that the research was limited in respect to its sample size of 30 participants, 15 leaders and 15 employees. Yet, as saturation was reached during the research process, it could be said that further participants may not actually have enhanced the research.

6.6.2 TRANSFERABILITY

This research was conducted in the relatively small context of SMEs in Scotland. It should therefore be considered whether this research can be transferred to other geographical and organisational contexts. As research has already been conducted regarding servant leadership in SMEs, it could be argued that it is already transferable to the North American context (McNeff and Irving, 2017; Van Winkle et al., 2014). Thus, it could, in theory, be transferred to other geographical contexts.

Furthermore, the SME context could also be said not to be a limitation, but a base for wider study into larger organisations. It should also be noted that it was not the aim of this research to be transferable, and it has achieved what it initially intended.

6.7 FUTURE AREAS FOR RESEARCH

6.7.1 ORGANISATIONAL CONTEXTS

As previously mentioned throughout the research this research was conducted in SMEs in Scotland. There is scope for this research and the skills in the servant leadership framework to be applied to another organisational context, such as larger or non-profit organisations.

As discussed in Chapter 2, servant leadership has been examined in a wide variety of contexts such as healthcare, sports, education, national parks etc. (Al-Mahdy et al. 2016; Crippen, 2014; Charles, 2015; Chung et al., 2010; Farrington and Lilan, 2018; Gunnarsdottir, 2014; Mayer et al., 2008; McCann, 2014). This research's framework and findings could be taken and applied to all these different contexts to determine the skills necessary for servant leadership in different circumstances.

6.7.2 GEOGRAPHICAL CONTEXT

The researcher selected Scotland as the context for this research due to its uniqueness as an underdeveloped location with regards to servant leadership literature. The systematic literature review showed that servant leadership research has been conducted in Australia, Canada, China, Dubai, Haiti, Iceland, India, Indonesia, Italy, Korea, Netherlands, Nigeria, Pakistan, Portugal, South Africa, Spain, Tasmania, Thailand, Turkey, UK and USA. This research could be conducted or expanded in a new geographical context to further validate its finding and subject its framework to further testing.

6.7.3 GENDER

As highlighted in Chapter 3, the participants were limited with regards to females, particularly leaders. Only two female servant leaders were included within the research. This could be an area for future research. One could examine whether this is specific to Scotland, to SMEs or to servant leadership and why this is the case.

Additionally, the research could be conducted with the inclusion of more females, in order to further validate the results.

6.8 ANSWERING THE RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The conclusion will now provide summarising answers to each of the research questions.

6.8.1 HOW CAN SERVANT LEADERSHIP BE DEFINED?

Through analysis of the data gathered, the research concludes that servant leadership can be defined as:

“Servant leadership is a form of leadership which consists of serving the followers in order to empower and develop them, resulting in organisational success”

6.8.2 WHAT ARE THE MOST PROMINENT SKILLS FOR SERVANT LEADERS IN SMES?

The research concluded that the most prominent skills for servant leaders in SMEs were conceptual skills, technical skills, interpersonal skills, people management and development and servanthood.

6.8.3 WHAT IS THE ORGANISATIONAL IMPACT OF SERVANT LEADERS' SKILLS ON SMES?

The research determined that servant leadership positively impacts on organisations in terms of, public service motivation, employee work climates, organisational citizenship behaviour and organisational growth.

6.9 CONCLUSION

This study has explored servant leadership in SMEs in Scotland, in order to determine the skills necessary for organisational success. The participants of this research, both leaders and employees, provided the researcher with rich and thorough data via semi-structured interviews. The data was then thematically analysed in accordance with Braun and Clarke's (2006) six stage process and the results provided a definition of servant leadership; an overview of the skills necessary for servant leadership and an insight into the organisational impact of servant leadership in SMEs.

A model of the skills necessary for servant leadership was determined from the findings of this study. Servant leaders were found to have the skills necessary to positively impact on their SMEs. Furthermore, a unique definition of the concept was proposed. Overall, this study is the first empirical exploration of servant leadership within the Scottish SME sector.

This study has contributed to knowledge: empirically and theoretically and methodologically. It has also identified the implications for practice. In conclusion, this research has contributed to and expanded the knowledge of the field of servant leadership.

7. REFERENCES

- Abdullah, M.A. (1998). The Impact of Industrialization on Human Resource Development in Malaysia. *Industry and Higher Education*. 12 (5), pp. 313-321.
- ACCA. (2012). *SMEs and their Advisers: Measuring Trust and Confidence*. Available: <https://www.accaglobal.com/gb/en/technical-activities/technical-resources-search/2012/may/smes-and-advisers.html>. Last accessed 8/4/21.
- Ahire, S., Golhar, D. and Waller, M.. (1996). Development and Validation of TQM Implementation Constructs. *Decision Sciences*. 27 (1), pp. 23-56.
- Akbar, Y., Balboni, B., Bortoluzzi, G. and Tracogna, A. (2017). SME export performance, capabilities and emerging markets: the impact of institutional voids. *European Journal of International Management*. 11 (2), pp. 201 - 226.
- Al-Mahdy, Y., Al-Harhi, A., El-Din, S. and Nesren, S. (2016) Perceptions of School Principals' Servant Leadership and Their Teachers' Job Satisfaction in Oman. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*. 15(4), pp. 543-566.
- Alikhan, S., and Mashelkar, R. A. (2009). *Intellectual property and competitive strategies in 21st century* . 2nd ed. Aspen: Kluwer Law International. pp. 1- 221.
- Amah, O. (2018) Determining the antecedents and outcomes of servant leadership. *Journal of General Management*. 43(3), pp.126-138.
- Amanchukwu, R., Stanley, G. and Ololube, N. (2015). A Review of Leadership Theories, Principles and Styles and Their Relevance to Educational Management. *Industrial Psychology*. 5 (1), pp. 6 -14.
- Analoui, F. and Karami, A. (2003) *Strategic Management in Small and Medium Enterprises*. London: Cengage Learning EMEA.

- Andersen, J. (2009). When a Servant-Leader Comes Knocking. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*. 30 (1), pp. 4-15.
- Ang, J. (1992). On the Theory of Finance for Privately Held Firms. *Journal of Small Business Finance*. 1 (3), pp. 185-203.
- Appelbaum, S. H., Audet, L. and Miller, J. C. (2003). Gender and leadership? Leadership and gender? A journey through the landscape of theories. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 24 (1), pp. 43–51.
- Arnold, D.M., Burns, K.E., Adhikari, N.K., Kho, M.E., Meade, M.O. and Cook, D.J. (2009). The design and interpretation of pilot trials in clinical research in critical care. *Critical Care Medical*. 37(1), pp. S69–S74.
- Arksey, H. and O'Malley, L. (2005). Scoping studies: towards a methodological framework. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology* . 8 (1), pp. 19-32.
- Arsawan, W., Pasek, K., Putu, Ni, and Suryantini, S. (2017). Impact of Transformational and Transactional Leadership Styles on Organizational Commitment and SMEs Business Performance: A Comparative Analysis. *International Business Management*. 87 (11), pp. 1583 - 1591.
- Asian Development Bank. (2014). *Asia Small and Medium-sized Enterprise (SME) Finance Monitor 2014*. Available: <https://www.adb.org/publications/asia-sme-finance-monitor-2014>. Last accessed 14/4/21.
- Australian Bureau of Statistics. (2001). *Small Business in Australia*. Available: <https://www.abs.gov.au/AUSSTATS/abs@.nsf/Lookup/1321.0Main+Features12001?OpenDocument>. Last accessed 8/4/21.
- Awan, K., Qureshi, I. and Sadi, A. (2012). The Effective Leadership Style in NGOs: Impact of Servant leadership Style on Employees' work Performance and mediation effect of work motivation. *International Journal of Economics & Management Sciences*. 1 (11), pp. 43-56

Ayyagari, M., Beck, T. and Demirgüç-Kunt, A. (2007). Small and Medium Enterprises across the Globe: A New Database. *Small Business Economics*. 29 (NA), pp. 415–434.

Aziz, R., Abdullah, M.H., Tajudin, A. and Mahmood, R. (2013), The effect of leadership styles on the business performance of SMEs in Malaysia. *International Journal of Economics and Management Studies*, 2(2), pp.45-52.

Babbie, E. (2014). *The basics of social research*. 6th ed. Belmont California: Wadsworth, Cengage Learning.

Bache, I. and Flinders, M. (2004). *Multi-level Governance*. Oxford: University Press

Bailey, Kenneth D. (2008). *Methods of Social Research* (4. ed.). New York: Free Press.

Barbuto, J. and Gifford, G. (2010). Examining Gender Differences of Servant Leadership: An Analysis of the Agentic and Communal Properties of the Servant Leadership Questionnaire. *Journal of Leadership Education*. 9 (2), pp. 4-22.

Barbuto, J. and Wheeler, D. (2006). Scale Development and Construct Clarification of Servant Leadership. *Faculty Publications: Agricultural Leadership, Education & Communication Department*. 51 (6), pp. 300-326.

Barbuto, J., Gottfredson, R. and Searle, T. (2014). An Examination of Emotional Intelligence as an Antecedent of Servant Leadership. *Journal of Leadership and Organisational Studies*. 21 (3), pp. 315-323.

Barnabas, A., Paul, C. and Anbarasu, J. (2010). The Need for Awareness of Servant Leadership in Business Schools. *Academic Leadership*. 8 (8), pp. 37-42 .

Barrett, D and Twycross, A. (2018). Data collection in qualitative research. *Evidence Based Nursing*. 21 (3), pp. 63-64.

Barrett, R. and Rainnie, A. (2002). What's So Special About Small Firms?: Developing an Integrated Approach to Analysing Small Firm Industrial Relations. *Work, Employment and Society*. 16 (3), pp. 415-431.

Barth-Farkas, F. and Vera, A. (2014). Power and transformational leadership in public organizations. *International Journal of Leadership in Public Services*. 10 (4), pp. 217-232.

Bass, B. (1990). From transactional to transformational leadership: Learning to share the vision. *Organizational Dynamics*. 18 (3), pp. 19-31.

Bass, B. and Steidlmeier P. (1999). Ethics, character, and authentic transformational leadership behaviour. *The Leadership Quarterly*. 10 (2), pp. 181-217.

Bass, B. M. (1985). *Leadership and performance beyond expectation*. New York: Free Press.

Bass, B. M. (1990). *Bass and Stogdills handbook of leadership*. New York: Free Press.

Bass, B. M. and Avolio, B. J. (1990). *Transformational leadership development: manual for multifactor leadership questionnaire*, California: Palo Alto Consulting Psychologists Press.

Bass, B. M. and Bass, R. (2009). *The Bass handbook of leadership: Theory, research, and managerial applications* (4th ed.). New York: Free Press.

Bass, B., Avolio, B., Jung, D. and Person, Y. (2003). Predicting Unit Performance by Assessing Transformational and Transactional Leadership. *Journal of Applied Psychology*. 88 (2), pp. 207-18.

Beazley, D. and Gemmil, G. (2010). Spirituality and Servant Leader Behavior. *Journal of Management, Spirituality and Religion*. 3 (3), pp. 258-270.

Beck, C. (2014). Antecedents of Servant Leadership A Mixed Methods Study. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*. 21 (3), pp. 299–314.

Benger, J., Coates, D., Davies, S., Greenwood, R., Nolan, J. and Rhys, M. (2016) Randomised comparison of the effectiveness of the laryngeal mask airway supreme, i-gel and current practice in the initial airway management of out of hospital cardiac arrest: a feasibility study. *British Journal of Anaesthesiology*. 116(2), pp. 62–268.

Bennis, W. and Townsend, R (1995). *Reinventing Leadership: Strategies to Empower the Organization*. New York: Harper Collins. pp. 1 – 208.

Bennis, W. G. and Nanus, B. (1985). *Leaders: The strategies for taking charge*. New York: Harper & Row.

Berger, A. and Frame, W. (2007). Small Business Credit Scoring and Credit Availability. *Journal of Small Business Management*. 45 (1), pp. 5-22.

Berger, A.N. and Udell, G.F., (2006). A more complete conceptual framework for SME finance. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 30(11), pp. 2945-2966.

Black, G. L. (2010). Correlational Analysis of Servant Leadership and School Climate. *Journal of Catholic Education*. 13 (4), pp. 437-466

Blackburn, R. and Schaper, M (2012). *Government, SMEs and Entrepreneurship Development Policy, Practice and Challenges*. Oxfordshire: Routledge.

Boateng, C. (2012). Evolving Conceptualization of Leadership and Its Implication for Vocational Technical Education. *World Journal of Education*. 2 (4), pp. 4 - 45.

Boaz, A., and Ashby, D. (2003). *Fit for purpose? Assessing research quality for evidence based policy and practice*. London: ESRC UK Centre for Evidence Based Policy and Practice. Available:
<https://www.kcl.ac.uk/sspp/departments/politicaeconomy/research/cep/pubs/papers/assets/wp11.pdf>

Last accessed: 15/4/21

Bobbio, A., van Dierendonck, D. and Manganelli, A. (2012). Servant leadership in Italy and its relation to organizational variables. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*. 8 (3), pp. 229-243.

Bogdan, R., and Biklen, S. K. (1998). *Qualitative Research for Education: An introduction to theories and methods*. Boston: Allyn and Bacon, Inc.

Booth, W., Colomb, G and Williams, J. (1995). *The Craft of Research*. 2nd ed. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.

Bottum, B. and Lenz, D. (1998). *Within Our Reach. Servant-Leadership for the Twenty-first Century*. In L. Spears, ed. *Insights on Leadership: Service, Stewardship, Spirit, and Servant- Leadership*. New York, NY: John Wiley pp. 157-169.

Bowman, N. (2010). Assessing learning and development among diverse college students. *Special Issue: Diversity and Educational Benefits*. 145 (Spring), pp. 53-71.

Bowman, R. (2005). Teacher as Servant Leader, *The Clearing House. A Journal of Educational Strategies, Issues and Ideas*, 78 (6), pp. 257-260.

Boyum, G. (2006, August). *The historical and philosophical influences on Greenleaf's concept of servant leadership*. Paper presented at the Proceedings from the 2006 Servant Leadership Research Roundtable, Virginia Beach, VA.

Bradley, Y. (1999). Servant Leadership: A Critique of Robert Greenleaf's Concept of Leadership. *Journal of Christian Education*. 42 (2), pp. 43-54.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*. 3(2), pp. 77-101.

Britten, N. (1999). Qualitative Interviews in Medical Research. *British Medical Journal Clinical Research*. 311 (6999), pp. 251-3.

Bronowski, J. (1967). The conscience of a scientist. *The Sciences*. 7 (6-7), pp. 4-6.

Brown, G. (2017). Doctoral Education in Quantitative Research Methods: Some Thoughts About Preparing Future Scholars. *Frontiers in Applied Mathematics & Statistics*. 3 (25), pp. 1-4.

Brown, R. and Lee, N. (2017). Innovation, SMEs and the liability of distance: the demand and supply of bank funding in peripheral UK regions. *Journal of Economic Geography*, 17 (1), pp. 233-260.

Brown, R., Kalafsky, R., Mawson, S. and Davies, L. (2018). Shocks, uncertainty and regional resilience: The case of Brexit and Scottish SMEs. *Local Economy: The Journal of the Local Economy Policy Unit*. 35 (7), pp. 655-675.

Bryant, P. and Brown, S. (2015). Getting to Know the Elephant: A Call to Advance Servant Leadership through Construct Consensus, Empirical Evidence, and Multilevel Theoretical Development. *Servant Leadership: Theory and Practice*. 2 (5), pp. 10-35.

Bryman, A. (1987). The generalizability of implicit leadership theory. *The Journal of Social Psychology*. 127(2), pp. 129–141.

Bryman, A., and Bell, E. (2007). *Business Research Methods*. 3rd ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

Buchen, I. (1998). Servant Leadership: A Model for Future Faculty and Future Institutions. *Journal of Organizational Studies*. 5 (1), pp. 125-134.

Burns, J (2004). *Transforming Leadership: A New Pursuit of Happiness*. USA: Grove Press.

Burns, R (2000). *Introduction to Research Methods*. California: SAGE Publications Ltd.

Burns, R.B. (1997). *Introduction to social research methods* (3rd ed.) Australia: Longman.

Burrell, G. and Morgan, G. (1979). *Sociological Paradigms and Organisational Analysis*. Abingdon: Routledge.

Burton L. and Peachey P. (2013). The Call for Servant Leadership in Intercollegiate Athletics. *Quest*. 65(3), pp. 354-371

BVA-BDRC. (2016). *SME Finance Monitor*. Available: https://www.bva-bdrc.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/06/BDRCContinental_SME_FM_Annual_Report_2016.pdf. Last accessed 13/4/21.

Caillier, J. (2014). Toward a Better Understanding of the Relationship Between Transformational Leadership, Public Service Motivation, Mission Valence, and Employee Performance: A Preliminary Study. *Public Personnel Management*. 43 (2), pp. 218-239.

Cairney, P. (2018). Three habits of successful policy entrepreneurs. *Policy & Politics*. 46 (2), pp. 199–215.

Caldwell, C (2004). *Leadership Skills for Managers*. 4th ed. USA: Amacom.

Camille, C. (1994). Intrapreneurship in Large Firms and SMEs: A Comparative Study. *International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship*. 12 (3), pp. 54-61.

Carr, L. (1994). The strengths and weaknesses of quantitative and qualitative research: what method for nursing? *Journal of Advanced Nursing*. 20 (4), pp. 716-21

Carter, D. and Baghurst, T. (2014). The Influence of Servant Leadership on Restaurant Employee Engagement. *Journal of Business Ethics*. 124 (3), pp. 453-464.

Carter, S. and Jones Evans, D. (2012). *Enterprise and Small Business: Principles, Practice and Policy*. 3rd ed. New York: Pearson Education. pp. 1-592.

Cawthon, D. (1996). Leadership: the great man theory revisited. *Business Horizons*. 39 (3), pp. 1+.

Central Bank of Nigeria. (2017). *Guidelines for the operations of the Agri-Business small and medium enterprises investment scheme*. Available: <https://www.cbn.gov.ng/out/2017/dfd/guidelines%20on%20agsmeis.pdf>. Last accessed 8/4/2021.

Cerit, Y. (2010) The effects of servant leadership on teachers' organizational commitment in primary schools in Turkey. *International Journal of Leadership in Education*. 13(3), pp. 301-317.

Cerit, Y. (2009). The Effects of Servant Leadership Behaviours of School Principals on Teachers' Job Satisfaction. *Educational Management Administration and Leadership*. 37 (5), pp. 600-623.

Certosimo, F. (2009). The servant leader: a higher calling for dental professionals. *Journal of Dental Education*. 73 (9), pp. 1065-1068.

Chan, S. and Mak, W. (2014) The impact of servant leadership and subordinates' organizational tenure on trust in leader and attitudes. *Personnel Review*. 43(2), pp.272-287.

Chang, L., Doll, B., Wout, M.V. and Frank, M. (2000). Seeing is believing: Trustworthiness as a dynamic belief. *Cognitive Psychology*. 61 (2), pp. 87-105.

Chapman, P., James-Moore, M. Szczygiel, M. and Thompson, D. (2000). Building internet capabilities in SMEs. *Logistics Information Management*. 13 (6), pp. 353-361.

Charles, D. (2015). Effects of Servant Leadership on Satisfaction with Leaders: Inclusion of Situational Variables. *Emerging Leadership Journeys*. 8 (1), pp. 46-62.

Chen, Z. Zhu, J. and Zhou. M. (2015). How does a servant leader fuel the service fire? A multilevel model of servant leadership, individual self-identity, group competition climate, and customer service performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*. 100(2): pp. 511–52.

Chen, Z., Liu, Y. and Gao, Z. (2016). An identification perspective of servant leadership's effects. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*. 31 (5), pp. 898-913.

Chopra, S. and Meindl, P (2016). *Supply Chain Management: Strategy, Planning, and Operation*. 6th ed. Stanford: Pearson.

Choudray, A. and Zaheer, A. (2013). Impact of Transformational and Servant Leadership on Organizational Performance: A Comparative Analysis. *Journal of Business Ethics*. 116 (2), pp. 433-440.

Christensen, L., Johnson, R. and Turner, L. (2020). *Research Methods, Design, and Analysis*. 13th ed. New York: Pearson.

Chughta, A. (2017). Examining the Effects of Servant Leadership on Life Satisfaction. *Springer Netherlands*. 10(10), pp. 1-17.

Chung, J., Su Jung, C., Gerard, K. and Petrick, J. (2010). Servant Leadership and Procedural Justice in the U.S. National Park Service: The Antecedents of Job Satisfaction. *Journal of Park & Recreation Administration*. 28 (3), pp. 1-15.

Claes, M. (1999). Women, men and management styles. *International Labour Review*. 138(4), pp. 431-446.

Clark, C.M. and Harrison, C. (2018). Leadership: the complexities and state of the field. *European Business Review*. 30(5), pp. 514-528.

Claxton, J. (2014). How do I know I am valued? *Journal of Workplace Learning*. 26 (3/4), pp. 188-201.

- Colbert, A., Judge, T. and Choi, D. (2012). Assessing the trait theory of leadership using self and observer ratings of personality: The mediating role of contributions to group success. *The Leadership Quarterly*. 23 (4), pp. 670-685.
- Conger, J. A. and Kanungo, R. N. (1992). Perceived behavioural attributes of charismatic leadership. *Canadian Journal of Behavioural Science / Revue canadienne des sciences du comportement*, 24(1), 86–102.
- Contreas, F. (2016). Journal of Human Values. *Servant and Spiritual Leadership Theories: Are They Two Different Notions?* 22 (3), pp. 202-208.
- Cook, T. and Campbell, D. (1979). *Quasi-experimentation: design and analysis issues for field settings*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin.
- Cooper, H. and Hedges, L.V. (1994). *The handbook of research synthesis*. New York, NY, US: Russell Sage Foundation.
- Cowley, W. H. (1931). The traits of face-to-face leaders. *The Journal of Abnormal and Social Psychology*. 26(3), pp. 304–313.
- Creswell, J (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches*. California: Sage Publications, Inc.
- Creswell, J.W. (2003) *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. (2nd ed.) Thousand Oaks California: Sage Publications
- Crichton, A. and Kinash, S. (2008). Virtual Ethnography: Interactive Interviewing Online as Method. *Canadian Journal of Learning and Technology*. 29 (2), N.P.
- Crippen, C. (2004). Journal of Women in Educational Leadership. *Pioneer Women in Manitoba: Evidence OF Servant-Leadership*. 2 (4), pp. 257-271.
- Crippen, C. (2017). A Case Study of Servant Leadership in the NHL. *Interchange*. 48 (2), pp 205–216.

Crotty, M (1998). *The Foundations of Social Research Meaning and Perspective in the Research Process*. California: SAGE Publications, Inc.

Crowther, D. and Lancaster, D (2008). *Research Methods*. 2nd ed. Abingdon: Routledge.

Cruz-Cunha, M.M., Varajao, J., Powell, P. and Martinho, R. (2011). *Enterprise Information Systems*. Portugal: International Conference. Part 2.

Cuilla, J (2003). *The Ethics of Leadership*. Belmont, CA: Wadsworth/Thomson.

Cunningham, J., Salomone, J. and Wielgus, N. (2015). Project Management Leadership Style: A Team Member Perspective. *International Journal of Global Business*. 8 (2), pp. 27-54.

Daft, R. L., Kendrick, M. and Vershinina, N. (2010). *Management*. Singapore: South Western Cengage Learning.

Dannhauser, Z. and Boshoff, A. (2007). Structural Equivalence of the Barbuto and Wheeler (2006) Servant Leadership Questionnaire on North American and South African Samples. *International Journal of Leadership Studies*. 2 (2), pp. 148-168.

Dawson, C. (2013). *Advanced Research Methods*. U.K.: Little, Brown Book Group Limited.

Day D. and Haipin, S. (2001). Leadership Development: A Review of Industry Best Practices. *US Army Research Institute for the Behavioural and Sciences*. 111 (N/A), pp. 1 - 65.

De Hoogh, A. and Den Hartog, D. (2008). Ethical and despotic leadership, relationships with leader's social responsibility, top management team effectiveness and subordinates' optimism: A multi-method study. *The Leadership Quarterly*. 19 (3), pp. 297-311.

De Kok, J, Vroonhof, P, Verhoeven, W, Timmermans, N, Kwaak, T, Snijders, J and Westhof, F (2011). Do SMEs create more and better jobs? European Commission Study on the SMEs impact on the EU labour market. Available:

https://ec.europa.eu/growth/sites/default/files/docs/body/do-smes-create-more-and-better-jobs_en.pdf Last accessed: 14/4/21

De Pree, M. (1989). *Leadership is an art*. New York: Dell Publishing.

Dearden, L., Machin, S. and Reed, H. (1997). Intergenerational Mobility in Britain. *The Economic Journal*. 107 (440), pp. 47-66.

Denmark, F. L. (1993). Women, leadership, and empowerment. *Psychology of Women Quarterly*. 17 (3), 343–356.

Dennis, R. and Bocarnea (2005). Development of the servant leadership assessment instrument. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*. 26 (8), pp. 600-615.

Dennis, R. and Winston, B. (2003). A factor analysis of Page and Wong's servant leadership instrument. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*. 24 (8), pp.455-459.

Denyer, D. and Tranfield, D. (2009). Producing a systematic review. In D. A. Buchanan & A. Bryman (Eds.), *The SAGE handbook of organizational research methods* (pp. 671–689). London: Sage Publications Ltd.

Denzin, N. K. and Lincoln, Y. S. (Eds.). (1994). *Handbook of qualitative research*. California: Sage Publications, Inc.

Desouza, K. M. and Awazu, Y. (2006). Knowledge management at SMEs. *Journal of Knowledge Management*. 10 (1), pp. 32-43.

Diesing, P. (1966). Objectivism vs. subjectivism in the social sciences. *Philosophy of Science*. 33 (1/2), pp. 124-133.

Donnelly, C., Simmons, G. and Armstrong, G. (2015). Digital loyalty card 'big data' and small business marketing: formal versus informal or complementary? *International Small Business Journal*. 33(4), pp. 422-442.

Drever, E. (1995). *Using Semi-Structured Interviews in Small-Scale Research. A Teacher's Guide*. Edinburgh: Scottish Council for Research in Education.

Dyczkowska, J. and Dyczkowski, T. (2018). Democratic or Autocratic Leadership Style? Participative Management and its Links to rewarding Strategies and Job Satisfaction in SMEs. *Journal of Business and Economics*. 43 (2), pp. 194-217.

Ebener, D. and O'Connell, J. (2010). How might servant leadership work? *Nonprofit Management and Leadership*. 20(3), pp. 315-335.

Edinburgh Group. (2012). *Growing the Global Economy through SMEs*. Available: http://www.edinburgh-group.org/media/2776/edinburgh_group_research_-_growing_the_global_economy_through_smes.pdf, 2012. Last accessed 8/4/2021.

Emerald Insight. (2020). *About Us*. Available: <https://www.emeraldgrouppublishing.com/about>. Last accessed 14/4/21

Ensari, M. and Karaby, M. (2014). What Helps to Make SMEs Successful in Global Markets? *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. 10 (NA), pp. 192-201.

Erich, K., Freeman, G., Richards, S., Robinson, I. and Shepperd, S. (2002). Research Policy and Planning. *How to do a Scoping Exercise: Continuity of Care*. 20 (1), pp. 25-29.

Errol, J. and Winston, B. (2005). A correlation of servant leadership, leader trust, and organizational trust. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 26 (1), pp.6-22.

Ethiopia. YaMā'ekalāwi stāistikis bālaśelṭān. (2009). *Report on small scale manufacturing industries survey*. Ethiopia: Addis Ababa : Central Statistical Authority. N.P.

European Commission. (2012). *A recovery on the horizon?*. Available: <https://www.escholar.manchester.ac.uk/api/datastream?publicationPid=uk-ac-man-scw:212438&datastreamId=FULL-TEXT.PDF>. Last accessed 8/1/21.

European Commission. (2016). *Annual report on European SMEs - 2016-2017*. Available: <https://www.smeacademy.eu/reports--results/annual-report-on-european-smes-2016-2017>. Last accessed 8/4/21.

European Commission. (2018). *SME Performance Review*. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/growth/smes/sme-strategy/performance-review_en. Last accessed 13/4/21

European Union. (2003). *SME definition*. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/growth/smes/sme-definition_en. Last accessed 8/4/2021.

Eva, N., Mulyadi, R., Sendjaya, S., van Dierendonck, D. and Liden, R. (2018). Servant leadership: A systematic review and call for future research. *The Leadership Quarterly*. 30 (1), pp. 111-132.

Farling, M.L., Stone, A.G. and Winston, B.E. (1999), Servant leadership: setting the stage for empirical research, *The Journal of Leadership Studies*, 6(1/2), pp. 49- 72.

Farmaki, A. (2017). The tourism and peace nexus. *Tourism Management*. 59 (C), pp. 528-540.

Farrington, S, and Lillah, R. (2018) Servant leadership and job satisfaction within private healthcare practices. *Leadership in Health Services*. 32(1), pp. 148-168

Federal Ministry of Economics and Technology. (N.D.). *www.bmwi.de German Mittelstand: Engine of the German economy*. Available: http://webcache.googleusercontent.com/search?q=cache:snY_9ck2YPsJ:policy.nl.gov.kr/cmmn/FileDown.do%3FatchFileId%3D137262%26fileSn%3D16862+&cd=11&hl=en&ct=clnk&gl=uk&client=safari. Last accessed 8/4/21

Federation for Small Business in Scotland. (2017). *Scotland Q4 2017 Small Business Index*. Available: <https://www.fsb.org.uk/resources-page/fsb-scotland-sbi-q4-2017-pdf.html>. Last accessed 13/4/21.

Felix, C., Ahmad, H. and Arshad, R. (2015). Examining Ethical Reasoning and Transactional Leadership Style In The Nigerian Public Sector. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. 20(6), pp. 88-94.

Ferguson Career Skills Library (2009). *Leadership Skills for Managers* . 3rd ed. New York: Ferguson Publishing.

Ferris, G., Treadway, D., Perrewe, P. and Brouer, R. (2007). Political Skill in Organizations. *Journal of Management Studies*. 33 (3), pp. 290-320.

Filho, E.E., Albuquerque, A.F., Nagano, M.S., Philippsen Junior, L. and Oliveira, J. (2017). Identifying SME mortality factors in the life cycle stages: an empirical approach of relevant factors for small business owner-managers in Brazil. *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*. 7 (5), pp. 1-15.

Fischer, E. and Reuber, R. A. (2003). Targeting Export Support to SMEs: Owners' International Experience as a Segmentation Basis. *Small Business Economics*. 2014 (1), pp. 69-82.

Flanagan, D. J. and Deshpande, S. P. (1996). Top management's perceptions of changes in HRM practices after union elections in small firms. *Journal of Small Business Management*. 34(4), pp. 23–34.

Franco, M. and Matos, P. G. (2015). Leadership styles in SMEs: A mixed-method approach. *International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal*. 11(2), Pp. 425–451

Freeman, E. and Auster, E. (2011). Values, Authenticity, and Responsible Leadership. *Journal of Business Ethics*. 98 (7), pp. 15–23.

- Fry, L.W. (2003). Toward a theory of spiritual leadership. *Leadership Quarterly*. 14 (6), pp. 693-727.
- Gallagher, C., Daly, M., Campbell, M. and Robson, G. (1991), "Job Creation 1987-89: The Contributions of Small and Large Firms, *Employment Gazette*: November.
- Galletta, A. (2013). *Mastering the Semi-Structured Interview and Beyond: From Research Design to Analysis and Publication*. New York: NYU Press.
- Garber J., Madigan A., Click E. and Fitzpatrick J. (2009). Attitudes towards collaboration and servant leadership among nurses, physicians and residents. *Journal of Interprofessional Care*. 23 (4), pp. 331-340.
- Gardiner, R. A. (2017). Authentic Leadership Through an Ethical Prism. *Advances in Developing Human Resources*. 19 (4), pp. 467–477.
- Gardner, L. and Stough, C. (2002). Examining the relationship between leadership and emotional intelligence in senior level managers. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*. 23 (2), pp. 68-78.
- Ghobadian, A. and Gallear, D. (1997). TQM and organization size. *International Journal of Operations & Production Management*. 17 (2), pp. 121-163.
- Ghosal, Y. and Ye, Y. (2015). Uncertainty and the employment dynamics of small and large businesses. *Small Business Economics*. 44(3), pp. 529-558.
- Giessner, S., Kollee, J., van Gils, S. and Van Quaquebeke, N. (2013). The Interactive Effects of Leader and Follower Moral Identity on Ethical Leadership and LMX Quality. *Academy of Management Annual Meeting Proceedings*. (1), pp. 11913.
- Gigliotti, R and Dwyer, B. (2016). Cultivating Dialogue: A Central Imperative for the Study and Practice of Servant Leadership. *Servant Leadership: Theory & Practice*. 3 (4), pp. 69-88.

Gill, P., K. Stewart, K., Treasure, E. and Chadwick B. (2008). Methods of data collection in qualitative research: interviews and focus groups. *British Dental Journal*. 204 (1), pp. 291–295.

Given, L. (2012). *The SAGE Encyclopedia of Qualitative Research Methods*. California: SAGE Publications Ltd.

Goleman, D. (2000). *Leadership That Gets Results*. Available: <https://hbr.org/2000/03/leadership-that-gets-results>. Last accessed 13/4/2020.

Goleman, D. (2014). Leading for the Long Future. *Leader to Leader*. 2014 (72), pp. 34-39.

Gordon, R.L. and Curlee, W. (2011). *The virtual project management office: Best practice, proven methods*, Management Concepts Inc.: Vienna, VA.

Gov U.K. (2019). *Small and medium-sized enterprises action plan*. Available: https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/961722/SME-Action-Plan.pdf. Last accessed 8/1/2019.

Graham, J. (1991). Servant-leadership in organizations: Inspirational and moral. *Leadership Quarterly*. 2 (2), pp. 105-119.

Greenleaf, R. K. (1998). Servant leadership. In L. C. Spears (Ed.), *Insights on Leadership* (pp. 15–20). New York: Wiley.

Grewal, A. Kataria, H. and Dhawan, I. (2016). Literature search for research planning and identification of research problem. *Indian Journal of Anaesthesia*. 60 (9), pp. 635-639.

Guest, G., Maqueen, K. and Namey E (2012). *Applied Thematic Analysis*. New York: SAGE Research Methods.

Guillame, B., Honeycutt, A. and Cleveland, C. (2012). Servant Leadership Trends Impact on 21st Century Business. *International Journal of Business and Social Research*. 2 (5), pp. 1 -7.

Gunnarsdóttir, S. (2014). Is Servant Leadership Useful for Sustainable Nordic Health Care? *Nordic Journal of Nursing Research*. 34 (2), pp. 53-55.

Hale, A.J. and Cragg, P.B. (1996) Business process re-engineering in the small firm: A case study *INFOR*, 34(1), pp. 15-27.

Hale, J. and Fields, D. (2007). Exploring Servant Leadership across Cultures: A Study of Followers in Ghana and the USA. *Leadership and Policy in Schools*. 3 (4), pp. 397-417.

Hall, A. S. (1991). "Why a Great Leader." In K. Hall *Living Leadership: Biblical Leadership* Anderson, IN: Warner Press. pp.14.

Hall, G. Hutchinson, P. and Michaelas, N. (2004). Determinants of the Capital Structures of European SMEs. *Journal of Business Finance and Accounting*. 31 (5-6), pp. 711-728.

Hall, P., Childs-Bowen, D., Cunningham-Morris, A., Pajardo, P. and Simeral A (2006). *The Principal Influence: A Framework for Developing Leadership Capacity in Principals*. USA: ASCD.

Hallberg, K. (2000). *A Market-oriented Strategy for Small and Medium Scale Enterprises*. Washington: The International Finance Corporation. pp. 1 -24.

Hamilton, L. C. and Asundi, R. (2008) Technology usage and innovation – its effects on the profitability of SMEs. *Management research News*. 31(11), pp. 830-845.

Han, Y., Kakabadse, N. and Kakabadse, A. (2010). Servant leadership in the People's Republic of China: a case study of the public sector. *Journal of Management Development*. 29(3), pp.265-281.

Hannay, M. (2008). The Cross-Cultural Leader: The Application of Servant Leadership Theory in the International Context. *Journal of International and Cultural Studies*. 1 (1), pp. 59-69.

Hargrove, E. and Owens, J. (2004). *Leadership in Context*. USA: Rowman & Littlefield Publishers.

Harris, A. (2010) Leading system transformation. *School Leadership & Management*. 30 (3), pp. 197-207.

Harrison, C., Paul, S. and Burnard, K. (2016). Entrepreneurial leadership: a systematic literature review. *International Review of Entrepreneurship*. 14(2), pp. 235-264.

Harrison, C. (2018). *Leadership Theory and Research: A Critical Approach to New and Existing Paradigms*. Switzerland: Palgrave MacMillan.

Hassan, H. (2017). Factors influencing cloud computing adoption in small and medium enterprises. *Journal of ICT*. 16 (1), pp. 21-41.

Hays, J. (2008). Teacher as Servant: Applications of Greenleaf's Servant Leadership in Higher Education. *Journal of Global Business Issues*. 2(1), pp. 113.

Hayton, J. (2015). *Leadership and Management Skills in SMEs*. Warwick Business School: Department of Business, Industry and Skills.

Hemphill, J. K. and Coons, A. E. (1957) 'Development of the Leader Behavior Description Questionnaire'. in R. M. Stodgill and A. E. Coons (Eds.) *Leader Behavior: Its Description and Measurement*. Columbus, Ohio: Bureau of Business Research. pp. 6-38.

Hesse, H. (1956) *The Journey to the East* New York: Picador.

Hiller, J. (2016). Epistemological Foundations of Objectivist and Interpretivist Research. In: Wheeler, B. *An Introduction to Music Therapy Research*. Texas: Barcelona Publishers. pp. 99-127.

Hoch, J.E., Bommer, W.H., Dulebohn, J.H. and Wu, D. (2018). Do Ethical, Authentic, and Servant Leadership Explain Variance Above and Beyond Transformational Leadership? A Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Management*. 44 (2), pp. 501-529.

Hofer, B. and Pintrich P. (1997). The Development of Epistemological Theories: Beliefs About Knowledge and Knowing and Their Relation to Learning. *Review of Educational Research*. 67 (1), pp. 88-140.

Hofstede, G. (1983). The Cultural Relativity of Organizational Practices and Theories. *Journal of International Business Studies* volume. 14 (Fall), pp. 75–89.

Hong, P. and Jeong, J. (2006). Supply chain management practices of SMEs: From a business growth perspective. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*. 19 (3), pp. 292-302.

Hosking, D. (1988). Organising, Leadership and Skilful Process. *Journal of Management Studies*. 25 (2), pp. 147-166.

Howell, J. and Avolio, B. (1992). The Ethics of Charismatic Leadership: Submission or Liberation? *The Executive*. 6(2), pp. 43-54.

Howell, K. (2003). *An Introduction to the Philosophy of Methodology*. New York: Sage Publications, Inc.

Hu, J. and Liden, R. (2011). Antecedents of Team Potency and Team Effectiveness: An Examination of Goal and Process Clarity and Servant Leadership. *Journal of Applied Psychology*. 96 (4), pp. 851-62.

Huczynski, A. and Buchanan, D (1991). *Organizational Behaviour: An Introductory Text*. USA: Prentice Hall.

Hudson, L. A. and Ozanne, J. L. (1988). Alternative ways of seeking knowledge in consumer research. *Journal of Consumer Research*. 14 (4), pp.508–521

Humpherys, J., Williams, A., Haden, S. and Hayek, M. (2014). Servant Leadership: Approaching the Paradox from the Life-Stories of Ping Fu. *The Journal of Applied Management & Entrepreneurship*. 19 (4), pp.43-60.

Hunter, E., Neubert, M., Perry, S.L., Witt, L.A., Penney, L. and Weinberger, E. (2013). Servant leaders inspire servant followers: Antecedents and outcomes for employees and the organization. *The Leadership Quarterly*. 24 (2), pp. 316-331.

In, J. (2017). Introduction of a pilot study. *Korean J Anesthesiology*. 70 (6), pp. 601-605.

Industry Canada. (2013). *Key Small Business Statistics*. Available: [https://www.ic.gc.ca/eic/site/061.nsf/vwapj/KSBS-PSRPE_August-Aout2013_eng.pdf/\\$FILE/KSBS-PSRPE_August-Aout2013_eng.pdf](https://www.ic.gc.ca/eic/site/061.nsf/vwapj/KSBS-PSRPE_August-Aout2013_eng.pdf/$FILE/KSBS-PSRPE_August-Aout2013_eng.pdf). Last accessed 8/4/2021

Informa. (2017). *Trading Update*. Available: <https://www.informa.com/globalassets/documents/investor-relations/2017/20170525-informa-agm-trading-update.pdf>. Last accessed 13/4/21.

Ingram Jr., O. (2016). Servant Leadership as A Leadership Model. *Journal of Management Science and Business Intelligence*. 1(1), pp.21-26.

Irving, A. and Longbotham, G. (2007). Team effectiveness and six essential servant leadership themes: A regression model based on items in the Organizational Leadership Assessment. *International Journal of Leadership Studies*. 2 (2): pp. 98-113

Jaques, E. and Clement, S. (1994). *Executive leadership: a practical guide to managing complexity*. Malden, Mass: Blackwell.

Jaramillo, F., Bande, B. and Varela, J. (2015). Servant leadership and ethics: a dyadic examination of supervisor behaviors and salesperson perceptions. *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*. 35 (2), pp. 108-124

Jaramillo, F., Grisaffe, D., Chonko, L. and Robert, J. (2009). Examining the Impact of Servant Leadership on Sales Force Performance. *The Journal of Personal Selling and Sales Management*. 29 (3), pp. 257-275.

Jenkins, H. (1991). *Getting it Right: Handbook for Successful School Leadership*. Hemel Hempstead: Simon & Schuster Education. pp. 1-191.

Jit, R., Sharma, C. and Kawatra, M. (2017). Healing a Broken Spirit: Role of Servant Leadership. *Vikalpa: The Journal for Decision Makers*. 42 (2), pp. 80-94.

Jonker, J .and Pennink, B.J.W. (2010). *Essence of research methodology: A concise guide for master and phd students in management science*. Heidelberg: Springer.

Joseph, E. and Winston, B. (2005). A correlation of servant leadership, leader trust, and organizational trust. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*. 26(1), pp. 6-22.

Judge, T., Heller, D., Heller, D. and Mount, M. (2002). Five-Factor Model of Personality and Job Satisfaction: A Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Applied Psychology*. 87 (3), pp. 530-41.

Kallet, R. (2004). How to Write the Methods Section of a Research Paper. *Respiratory Care*. 49 (10), pp. 1229-1232.

Karanxha, Z., Agosto, V., and Elam, D. (2011). The journey of Elam: her servant leadership pedagogy as a public intellectual. *Vitae Scholasticae* 21. (2), pp. 65

Kashyap, V. and Rangnekar, S. (2016). Servant leadership, employer brand perception, trust in leaders and turnover intentions: A sequential mediation model. *Review of Managerial Science*. 10(3), pp. 437–461.

Katz, R. L. (1955). Skills of an effective administrator. *Harvard Business Review*. 33(1), pp. 33–42.

Kempster, S. and Cope, J. (2010). Learning to lead in the entrepreneurial context. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*, 16 (1), pp. 5–34.

Khalique, M., Shaari, J.A.N. and Isa, A.H.M. (2011). Intellectual capital and its major components. *International Journal of Current Research*, 3 (6). pp.343–347.

Kim, B. (2001). Social Constructivism. *Emerging perspectives on learning, teaching, and technology*. 1 (1), pp.1-16.

Kim, Y. (2010) The pilot study in qualitative inquiry: Identifying issues and learning lessons for culturally competent research. *Qualitative Social Work*. 10 (2), pp. 190-296.

Kim, K., Choi, S., Ullah, E. and Kang, S.W. (2004). How transformational leadership facilitates innovative behaviour of Korean workers. *Personnel Review*. 45 (3), pp. 459-479.

King, A.S. (1990) Evolution of leadership. *Vikalpa*. 15 (2), pp. 43-54.

Koch, C. L. Y. and Van Straten, E. (1997). '*Personeelsbeleid in Enkele MKB Bedrijven*' [*Personnel Management in Several SMEs*], *EIM Strategic Study 9703*. Zoetermeer, the Netherlands: EIM Business and Policy Research.

Kolb, J. A. (1999). The effect of gender role, attitude toward leadership and self-confidence on leader emergence: Implications for leadership development. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*. 10 (4), pp. 305–320

Kotter, J. P. (1990). *A force for change: How leadership differs from management*. New York: The Free Press

Koyuncu, M., Burke, R., Astakhova, M., Eren, D and Cetin, H. (2014). Servant leadership and perceptions of service quality provided by front-line service workers in hotels in Turkey: Achieving competitive advantage: Servant leadership and perceptions of service quality. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*. 26 (7), pp.1083-1099.

Lambert D. and Cooper, M. (2000). Issues in Supply Chain Management. *Industrial Marketing Management*. 29 (1), pp. 65-83.

Lanctot, J. D., and Irving, J.A. (2010). Character and Leadership: Situating Servant Leadership in a Proposed Virtues Framework. *International Journal of Leadership Studies*. 6 (1), pp. 28-50.

Lange, T., Ottens, M. and Taylor, A. (2000). Journal of European Industrial Training. *SMEs and Barriers to Skills Development: A Scottish Perspective*. 24 (1), pp. 5-11.

Laub, J. (1999). Assessing the servant organization: Development of the servant organizational leadership (SOLA) instrument. *Dissertation Abstracts International*, 60 (2) pp. 308

Leatherman, R. (2008). *Quality Leadership Skills: Standards of Leadership Behaviour*. 3rd ed. Massachusetts: HRD Press

Lee-Ross, D. and Lashley, C. (2009). *Entrepreneurship and Small Business Management. The Hospitality Industry*. Oxford: Butterworth Heinemann. pp. 15

Leininger, M. (1994). Evaluation criteria and critique of qualitative research studies. In J. M. Morse (Ed.), *Critical issues in qualitative research methods* (pp. 95-115). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications Inc.

Leitch, C.M., McMullan, C. and Harrison, R.T. (2009). Leadership development in SMEs: an action learning approach. *Action Learning: Research and Practice*. 6 (3) pp. 243-263.

Leitch, C.M., McMullan, C. and Harrison, R.T. (2009). Leadership development in SMEs: an action learning approach. *Action Learning: Research and Practice*, 6 (3), pp. 243-263.

Li, Y., Diwan, L., Tu, Y. and Liu, J. (2018). How and when servant leadership enhances life satisfaction. *Personnel Review*, 47 (5), pp.1077-1093

Liden, R.C., Wayne, S.J., Meuser, J.D., Hu, J., Wu, J. and Liao C. (2015). Servant leadership: Validation of a short form of the SL-28. *Leadership Quarterly* 26(2), 254–269.

Liden, R., Wayne, S., Liao, C. and Meuser, J. (2013). Serving Leadership and Serving Culture: Influence on Individual and Unit Performance. *Academy of Management Journal*. 57 (5), pp. 1434–1452

Liden, R.C., Wayne, S. Zhao, J., Hao, H. and David J. (2008). Servant leadership: development of a multidimensional measure and multilevel assessment. *Leadership Quarterly*. 19(2), pp. 161-177.

Light, R.J. and Pillemer D.B. (1984). *Summing up: The science of reviewing research*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press

Lincoln, Y.S. and Guba, E.G. (1985). *Naturalistic Inquiry*. Newbury Park, California: Sage Publications.

Liu, B., Hu, W. and Cheng, Y. (2015). From the West to the East: Validating Servant Leadership in the Chinese Public Sector. *Public Personnel Management*. 44 (1), pp. 25-45.

Liu, H. (2017). Just the Servant: An Intersectional Critique of Servant Leadership. *Journal of Business Ethics*. 156 (12), pp. 1099–1112.

Liu, X. (2008), 'SME Development in China: A Policy Perspective on SME Industrial Clustering', in Lim, H. (ed.), *SME in Asia and Globalization*, ERIA Research Project Report: China pp.37-68.

Lo, M., Ramayah, T. and Run, E. (2010). Does transformational leadership style foster commitment to change? The case of higher education in Malaysia. *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences*. 2 (2), pp. 5384–5388.

Lowe, A., Norris, A.C., Farris, A.J. and Babbage, D.R. (2018) Quantifying thematic saturation in qualitative data analysis. *Field Methods*. 30(3), pp. 191-207.

Lussier, R. and Achua, C. (2016). *Leadership Theory and Application and Skill Development*. 6th ed. USA: CENGAGE Learning.

Lussier, R. N., Corman, J. and Corman, J. (1996). A Business Success Versus Failure Prediction Model for Entrepreneurs with 0-10 Employees. *Journal of Small Business Strategy*, 7 (1), pp. 21-36.

Mackenzie, N. and Knipe, S. (2006). Research dilemmas: Paradigms, methods and methodology. *Issues in Educational Research*. 16 (2), pp. 193-205.

Madanchian, M., Hussein, N., Noordin, F. and Taherdoost, H. (2017). Leadership Effectiveness Measurement and Its Effect on Organization Outcomes. *Proceedings of Engineering*. 181 (1), pp. 1043-1048.

Marlow, S., Hart, M., Levie, J. and Shamshad, M. (2013). *Women in Enterprise: A Different Perspective*. Available:
https://pure.strath.ac.uk/ws/portalfiles/portal/17293549/Women_in_Enterprise.pdf.
Last accessed 13/4/21.

Marquis, B. and Huston, C.J (2009). *Leadership Roles and Management Functions in Nursing: Theory and Application*. 6th ed. China: Lippincott-Raven. pp. 1 - 624.

Marsh, H.W., Hau, K.T. and Kong, C.K. (2002). Multilevel causal ordering of academic self- concept and achievement: Influence of language of instruction. *American Research Journal*, 39 (3), pp. 727-763.

Martens, M. (2005). The Use of Structural Equation Modeling in Counseling Psychology Research. *The Counseling Psychologist*. 33 (3), pp. 269-298.

Mason, C. and Brown, R. (2013). Creating good public policy to support high-growth firms. *Small Business Economics*. 40 (2), pp.1-225.

Mathena, K. (2002). Nursing Manager Leadership Skills. *JONA: The Journal of Nursing Administration*. 32 (3), pp. 136-142.

Matzler, K., Schwarz, E., Deutinger, N. and Hams, R. (2008). The Relationship between Transformational Leadership, Product Innovation and Performance in SMEs. *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*. 21 (2), pp. 39-151.

Mayer, D., Bardes, M. and Piccolo, R. (2008). Do servant-leaders help satisfy follower needs? An organizational justice perspective. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*. 2 (1), pp. 180-197

Mccann, J., Graves, D. and Cox, L. (2014). Servant Leadership, Employee Satisfaction, and Organizational Performance in Rural Community Hospitals. *International Journal of Business and Management*. 9 (10), pp. 29-38.

Mccole, P., Ramsey, E. and Williams, J. (2010). Trust Considerations on Attitudes Towards Online Purchasing: The Moderating Effect of Privacy and Security Concerns. *Journal of Business Research*. 63 (9), pp. 315-328.

McKelvie, A. and Wilklund A. (2010). Advancing Firm Growth Research: A Focus on Growth Mode Instead of Growth Rate. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*. 34 (2), pp. 261-288.

McKinley, J. (2015). Critical argument and writer identity: Social constructivism as a theoretical framework for EFL academic writing. *Critical Inquiry in Language Studies*. 12 (3), pp. 184-207.

McNabb, D (2008). *Research methods in public administration and non-profit management: quantitative and qualitative approaches*. Armonk, New York: M.E. Sharpe, Inc.

McNeff, M. and Irving, J. (2017). Job Satisfaction and the Priority of Valuing People: A Case Study of Servant Leadership Practice in a Network of Family-Owned Companies. *SAGE Open*. 7 (1), pp. 1-8.

Mcquade, K.E., Harrison, C. and Tarbert, H. (2020). Systematically reviewing servant leadership. *European Business Review*. 33 (3), pp. 465-490.

Megheirkouni, M. (2018). Insights on practicing of servant leadership in the events sector. *Sport, Business and Management: An International Journal*. 8 (2), pp. 134-152.

Mertel, T. and Brill C. (2015). What every leader ought to know about becoming a servant leader. *Industrial and Commercial Training*, 47(5), pp. 228-235.

Mertens, D.M. (2005). *Research methods in education and psychology: Integrating diversity with quantitative and qualitative approaches* (2nd ed.) Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications Inc.

Mesu, J., Sanders, K. and van Riemsdijk, N. (2015). Transformational leadership and organisational commitment in manufacturing and service small to medium-sized enterprises: The moderating effects of directive and participative leadership. *Personnel Review*. 44 (6), pp. 970-990.

Mgeni, T. (2015). Impact of Entrepreneurial Leadership Style on Business Performance of SMEs in Tanzania. *Journal of Entrepreneurship & Organization Management*. 04 (10), pp. 202- 269.

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises. (2006). *THE MICRO, SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES DEVELOPMENT ACT, 2006*. Available: <https://legislative.gov.in/sites/default/files/A2006-27.pdf>. Last accessed 8/1/2021.

Miles, M. B. and Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative data analysis: An expanded sourcebook* (2nd ed.). New York: Sage Publications, Inc

Minichiello, V., Aroni, R. and Timewell, E. (1990). *In-Depth Interviewing: researching people*. Melbourne: Longman Cheshire.

Mittal, R. and Dorfman, P.W. (2012). Servant leadership across cultures. *Journal of World Business*. Elsevier, 47(4), pp. 555-570

Moreno-Luzon, M.D. and Peris, F.J. (1998). Strategic Approaches, Organizational Design and Quality Management: Integration in a fit and contingency model. *International Journal of Quality Science*. 3 (4), pp. 328-347.

Moro, A., Fink., M. and Maresch, D. (2015). Reduction in information asymmetry and credit access for small and medium-sized enterprises. *Journal of Financial Research*. 38 (1), pp. 121-143.

Moser, L., Neill, K., Sambamoorthi, U. and Bell, H. (2016). The Role of Servant Leadership and Transformational Leadership in Academic Pharmacy. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*. 80 (7), pp. 113.

Mueller, S. and Thomas, A. (2001). Culture and Entrepreneurial Potential: A Nine Country Study of Locus of Control and Innovativeness. *Journal of Business Venturing*. 16 (1), pp. 51-75.

Mukhopadhyay, A. and Pendse, S. (1983). Profit Sharing in Small Business: An Analysis of Risk and Incentive Effects. *American Journal of Small Business*. 7 (4), pp. 31-37.

Mumford, M. D. (2000). Exploring the relationship of leadership skills and knowledge to leader performance. *The Leadership Quarterly*. 11(1), pp. 65–86.

Mumford, M. D., Zaccaro, S. J., Harding, F. D., Jacobs, T. O. and Fleishman, E. A. (2000a). Leadership skills for a changing world solving complex social problems. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 11(1), pp. 11–35.

Murphy, M. (1996) *Small Business Management*. Pitman Publishing: London pp. 1-147

Nair, K. (1994). A Higher Standard of Leadership: Lessons from the Life of Gandhi. *Human Resource Development Quality*. 8 (4), pp. 347

Nanjundeswaraswamy, T. and Swamy, R. (2015). Leadership styles and quality of work life in SMEs. *International Journal of Industrial Engineering Computations*. 5 (1), pp. 65-78.

National Audit Office. (2016). *National Audit Office report: Government's spending with small and medium-sized enterprises Government's spending with small and medium-sized enterprises*. Available: <https://www.nao.org.uk/report/governments-spending-with-small-and-medium-sized-enterprises/>. Last accessed 14/1/21.

Neelankavil, J. (2007). *International Business Research*. California: M.E. Sharpe.

NESTA. (2017). *The State of Small Business: Putting UK entrepreneurs on the map*. Available: <https://www.nesta.org.uk/report/the-state-of-small-business-putting-uk-entrepreneurs-on-the-map/>. Last accessed 8/4/21.

Neuman, W. (2014) *Social Research Methods: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. Essex: Pearson.

Neumark, D., Wall, B. and Zhang, J. (2011) Do Small Businesses Create More Jobs? New Evidence for the United States from the National Establishment Time Series. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 93 (1), pp. 16–29

Newman, I. and Covrig, D. (2013). Building consistency between title, problem statement, purpose, & research questions to improve the quality of research plans and reports. *New Horizons in Adult Education and Human Resource Development*. 25 (1), pp. 70-79.

Newman, A., Schwarz, G., Cooper, B. and Sendjaya, S. (2017). How Servant Leadership Influences Organizational Citizenship Behavior: The Roles of LMX, Empowerment, and Proactive Personality. *Journal of Business Ethics*. 145 (1), pp. 2827-6.

- Ng, H. and Kee, D. (2017). The core competence of successful owner-managed SMEs. *Management Decision*. 56(1), pp. 252-272.
- Nicholls, D. (2009). Qualitative Research: Part Three – Methods. *International Journal of Therapy and Rehabilitation*. 16 (12), pp. 638-647.
- Northouse, P. (2015). *Leadership: Theory and Practice*, 7th ed. Thousand Oaks California: SAGE Publications Ltd.
- Novikova, I. (2013). Trait, Trait Theory. In: Kenneth D. Keith (ed.) *The Encyclopedia of Cross-Cultural Psychology*. USA: Wiley-Blackwell. (pp.5-45).
- Nwagbara, U. (2013). The human side of political leadership: Conversations with Myself (2010) as a reflection of servant-leadership Nelson Mandela. *Leadership*. 9 (1), pp. 141-144.
- O'Connor, K. (2010). *Gender and Women's Leadership: A Reference Handbook*. Thousand Oaks California: SAGE Publications, Inc. pp. 1 – 991
- O'Leary, Z. (2004) *The essential guide to doing research*. Thousand Oaks California: Sage Publications Inc.
- O'Sherman, R. (2019). The Case for Servant Leadership. *Nurse Leader*. 17 (2), pp. 86-87.
- OECD (2012), *Financing SMEs and Entrepreneurs 2012: An OECD Scoreboard*, OECD Publishing: Paris, pp.1-198.
- OECD. (2000). *Small and Medium-sized Enterprises: Local Strength, Global Reach*. Available: <http://www.oecd.org/cfe/leed/1918307.pdf>. Last accessed 8/4/2021.
- OECD. (2012). *Leveraging training: skills development in SMEs*. Available: <https://www.oecd.org/cfe/leed/tsmes.htm>. Last accessed 13/1/21.

- Ofcom. (2017). *The SME experience of communications services: research report*. Available: https://www.ofcom.org.uk/__data/assets/pdf_file/0030/96348/Ofcom-SME-consumer-experience-research-2016-Report.pdf. Last accessed 14/1/21.
- Olhager, J. and Rudberg, M. (2003). Manufacturing strategy and e-business: an exploratory study. *Integrated Manufacturing Systems*. 14 (4), pp. 334-345.
- Oliver, L. and Reynolds, K. (2010). Serving the Once and Future King: Using the TV Series Merlin to Teach Servant-Leadership and Leadership Ethics in Schools. *The Journal of Leadership Education*. 9 (2), pp. 122-134.
- Omar, A. and Fraser, P. (2010). *The role of small and medium enterprise retailing in Britain*. Available: <https://uhra.herts.ac.uk/bitstream/handle/2299/4997/S120.pdf?sequence=1>. Last accessed 13/4/21.
- Outcalt, C., Shannon, F., McMahon, K., Philip, T., and Christopher, N. (2001). A Leadership Approach for the New Millennium: A Case Study of UCLA's Bruin Leaders Project. *Journal of Student Affairs Research and Practice*. 38 (10), pp. 1949-6605.
- Oyelaran-Oyeyinka, B. and Lal, K. (2006). *SMEs and New Technologies: Learning E-Business and Development*. London: Palgrave McMillan.
- Ozyilmaz, A. and Cicek, S. (2015). How does servant leadership affect employee attitudes, behaviors, and psychological climates in a for-profit organizational context? *Journal of Management & Organization*. 21 (3), pp. 1-28.
- Page, D. and Wong, P. (2000). A Conceptual Framework for Measuring Servant Leadership. In: Adjibolooso, S (ed). *The human factor in Shaping the Course of History and Development*. Washington DC: American University Press. (pp. 69-110)

Palumbo, R. (2016). Challenging Servant Leadership In The Non-profit Sector: The Side Effects Of Servant Leadership. *The Journal of Non-profit Education and Leadership*. 6 (2), pp. 81-98.

Parker, J. and Begnaud, L. (2004). *Developing Creative Leadership*. USA: New Hampton: Teacher Ideas Press.

Parkin M.A. and Parkin, R. (1996). The Impact of TQM in UK SMEs *Industrial Management and Data Systems* 96 (4), pp. 6-10.

Parnas, J. and Zahavi, D. (2002). The role of phenomenology in psychiatric diagnosis and classification. In M. Maj, W. Gaebel, J. J. López-Ibor, & N. Sartorius (Eds.), *Psychiatric diagnosis and classification* New Jersey: John Wiley & Sons Inc. (pp. 137–162).

Parris, D. L. and Peachey, J. W. (2013). A systematic literature review of servant leadership theory in organizational contexts. *Journal of business ethics*. 3 (3), pp. 377-393.

Pascale, C. (2011). *Cartographies of knowledge: Exploring qualitative epistemologies*. Thousand Oaks, California: Sage. pp.4-5

Passerini, K., El Tarabishy, A. and Patten, K (2012). *Information Technology for Small Business*. New York: Springer-Verlag.

Pathak, R. (2008). *Methodology of Educational Research*. New Delhi: Atlantic Publishers and Distributions.

Pekerti, A. and Sendjaya, S. (2010). Exploring servant leadership across cultures: comparative study in Australia and Indonesia. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*. 21(5), pp. 754-780.

Perren L. and Grant, P. (2000). The Evolution of Management Accounting Routines in Small Business: A Social Construction Perspective. *Management Accounting Research*. 11(4), pp.10-11.

Peterlin, J., Pearse, N. and Dimovski, V. (2015). Strategic Decision Making for Organizational Sustainability: The Implications of Servant Leadership and Sustainable Leadership Approaches. *Economic and Business Review*. 17 (3), pp. 273-290

Peterson, S., Galvin, B. and Lange, D. (2012). CEO Servant Leadership: Exploring Executive Characteristics and Firm Performance. *Personnel Psychology*. 65 (3), pp. 565-596.

Petre, M. and Rugg, G (2010). *The Unwritten Rules of Phd Research*. 2nd ed. New York: Open University Press. pp. 1-288.

Petrovskaya, I. and Mirakyan, A. (2017). A mission of service: Social entrepreneur as a servant leader. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behaviour & Research*. 24 (3), pp. 755-767.

Pflugrath, G., Roebuck, P. and Simnett, R. (2011). Impact of assurance and assurer's professional affiliation on financial analysts' assessment of credibility of corporate social responsibility information. *Auditing: A Journal of Practice & Theory*, 30 (3), pp. 239–254.

Phillips, E.M. (1993). The Concept of Quality in the PhD. In: Cullen, D.J. *Quality in PhD Education*. Canberra: CEDAM. pp. 27-38

Piccolo, R. and Colquitt, J. (2016). Transformational Leadership and Job Behaviors: The Mediating Role of Core Job Characteristics. *The Academy of Management Journal*. 49 (2), pp. 327-340.

Pinho, J. (2008). TQM and performance in small medium enterprises: The mediating effect of customer orientation and innovation. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*. 25(3), pp. 256-275.

Pinnington, A. (2011). Leadership development: Applying the same leadership theories and development practices to different contexts? *Leadership*. 7 (3/4), pp. 335-365

Polleys, M.S. (2002). One university's response to the Anti-Leadership Vaccine: Developing servant leaders. *Journal of Leadership Studies*, 8 (3), pp. 117-129

Porter, S. (2006). *Restoring the Foundations of Epistemic Justification: A Direct Realist and Conceptualist Theory of Foundationalism*. Washington D.C.: Lexington Books.

Puccio, G. J., Mance, M. and Murdock, M. C. (2011). *Creative leadership: Skills that drive change*. Thousand Oaks California: SAGE Publications Inc.

Pugh, D. and Phillips, E. (2000). *How To Get a PhD: A Handbook for Students and Their Supervisors*. 3rd ed. New York: Open University Press. pp.1-204.

Punch, K.F. (1998). *Introduction to Social Research: Quantitative and Qualitative Approaches*. Thousand Oaks California: Sage Publications.

Punnachet, T. (2009). Catholic servant-leadership in education: going beyond the secular paradigm, *International Studies in Catholic Education*, 1(2), pp. 117-134

Rai, R. and Prakash, A. (2012). A relational perspective to knowledge creation: Role of servant leadership. *Journal of Leadership Studies*. 6 (2), pp. 61-85.

Ram, M. and Hillin, G. (1994). Achieving 'Breakout': Developing Mainstream Ethnic Minority Businesses. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*. 1 (2), pp. 15-21.

Rauch, C. F. and Behling, O. (1984). Functionalism: Basis for an alternate approach to the study of leadership. In J. G. Hunt, D. M. Hosking, C. A. Schriesheim, & R. Stewart (Eds.), *Leaders and managers: International perspectives on managerial behavior and leadership* New York: Pergamon Press. (pp. 45-62).

Reddy, V. and Kamesh, A. (2016). Integrating Servant Leadership and Ethical Leadership: Indian and European Spiritual Approaches. In: Chatterji, M. and Zsolnai, L (eds.). *Ethical Leadership*. London: Palgrave Macmillan. pp 107-124.

Reed, L. (2015). Servant Leadership, Followership, and Organizational Citizenship Behaviors in 9-1-1 Emergency Communications Centers: Implications of a National Study. *Servant Leadership: Theory and Practice*. 2 (1), pp.71-94

Reed, L. L., Vidaver-Cohen, D. and Colwell, S. R. (2011). A new scale to measure executive servant leadership: Development, analysis, and implications for research. *Journal of Business Ethics*. 101 (3), pp. 415–434.

Rego, A. and Srivastava, T. (2013). *Business Research Methodology*. New York: McGraw-Hill Education.

Reimers, J. and Parsons, G. (2004). Case Study of “Remember the Titans” (2000) to Examine Power, Servant Leadership, Transformational Leadership, Followership and Change. *The Journal of Behavioural and Applied Management*. 5 (2), pp. 152.

Reinke, S. (2004). Service before self: Towards a theory of servant-leadership. *Global Virtue Ethics Review*. 5 (3), pp. 30-57

Rest, J. R. (1986). *Moral development: Advances in research and theory*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press.

Rhodes, C. (2017). *Business statistics*. Available: <https://sigs.cim.co.uk/media/3653/sn06152-2.pdf>. Last accessed 13/4/21.

Rhodes, C. and Ward, M. (2014). *Small Businesses and the UK Economy*. Available: <https://commonslibrary.parliament.uk/research-briefings/sn06078/>. Last accessed 13/4/21.

Rhodes, C. and Ward, M. (2017). *Business statistics*. Available: <https://sigs.cim.co.uk/media/3653/sn06152-2.pdf>. Last accessed 13/4/21.

Rieke, M., Hammermeister, J., and Chase, M. (2008). Servant Leadership In Sport: A New Paradigm For Effective Coach Behaviour *Physical Education, Health and Recreation Faculty Publications*. 3 (2) pp. 233-239.

Robbins, S. (2003). *Organizational Behaviour: Concepts, Controversies, and Applications*. New Jersey: Prentice-Hall.

Robinson, G., Neubert, M. and Miller, G. (2018). Servant Leadership in Sport: A Review, Synthesis, and Applications for Sport Management Classrooms. *Human Kinetics Journals*. 12 (1), pp. 39-56.

Robinson, R. and Pearce, J. (1984). The Research Thrust in Small Firm Strategic Planning. *The Academy of Management Review*. 9 (1), pp. 128.

Robson, C. (1993). *Real World Research. A Resource for Social Scientists and Practitioner Researchers*. Oxford: Blackwell Publishers Inc.

Rodríguez- Carvajal, R., de Rivas, S., Herrero, M. and van Dierendonck, D. (2014). Leading People Positively: Cross-Cultural Validation of the Servant Leadership Survey (SLS). *The Spanish Journal of Psychology*. 17 (2), pp. 1-13.

Rodríguez-Carvajal, R., Herrero, A., van Dierendonck, D. and de Rivas, S. (2018). Servant Leadership and Goal Attainment through Meaningful Life and Vitality: A Diary Study. *Journal of Happiness Studies*. 20(2), pp. 499–521.

Ronquillo, J. (2011). Servant, transformational, and transactional leadership. In K. A. Agard (eds) *Leadership in nonprofit organizations: A reference handbook*. Thousand Oaks California: Sage Publications. pp. 345-353.

Rost, J. C. (1993). *Leadership for the Twenty-First Century*. New York: Praeger.

Rozakis, L. (New York). *Schaum's Quick Guide to Writing Great Research Papers*. (2nd ed). 2007: McGraw Hill Professional.

- Russell, R. (2001) The role of values in servant leadership. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*. 22 (2), pp. 76-84
- Russell, E. (2016). Servant leadership's cycle of benefit. *Servant Leadership: Theory & Practice*. 3 (1), pp. 52–68.
- Russell, R. (2001). The role of values in servant leadership. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*. 22 (2), pp. 76-84
- Russell, R. F. and Stone, A. G. (2002). A review of servant leadership attributes: Developing a practical model. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 23 (3), pp. 145–157.
- Ruwhiu, D. and Elkin, G. (2016). Converging pathways of contemporary leadership: In the footsteps of Māori and servant leadership. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*. 12 (3), pp. 308-323.
- Saad, M., Kumar, V. and Bradford, J. (2017). An investigation into the development of the Absorptive Capacity of manufacturing SMEs. *International Journal of Production Research*. 55 (23), pp. 6916-6931.
- SAGE Publications. (2016). *About Us*. Available: https://uk.sagepub.com/en-gb/eur/journals?_gl=1%2A1deeazr%2A_ga%2AODQ1OTQ2NjAzLjE2MTc3MjE5ODI.%2A_ga_60R758KFDG%2AMTYxODQxMDA0OS4xMi4xLjE2MTg0MTM2MDkuMA. Last accessed 14/4/21.
- Sauer, S. (2011). Taking the Reins: The Effects of New Leader Status and Leadership Style on Team Performance. *Journal of Applied Psychology*. 96 (3), pp. 574-87.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2012) *Research Methods for Business Students*. (6th ed). Essex: Pearson.
- Savel, R. and Munro, C. (2017). Servant Leadership: The Primacy of Service. *American Journal of Critical Care*. 26 (2), pp. 97-99

Scase, R. and Goffee, R. (1980), *The Real World of the Business Owner*, London: Croom Helm.

Science Direct. (2018). *Web of Science: An overview*. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/nursing-and-health-professions/web-of-science>. Last accessed 14/4/21.

Scottish Government. (2016). *Scottish Government Urban Rural Classification 2016*. Available: <https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-government-urban-rural-classification-2016/pages/5/>. Last accessed 30/4/21.

Scottish Government. (2018). *Businesses in Scotland*. Available: <https://www2.gov.scot/Topics/Statistics/Browse/Business/Corporate/KeyFacts>. Last accessed 22/11/2018.

Scottish Government (2015a) A Strong Sustainable Economy [Online] Available: <http://www.gov.scot/Publications/2015/09/7685/4> Last Accessed: 14/4/2020.

Scottish Government (2015b) *Businesses in Scotland 2015* Edinburgh: The UK Seeland, D. (2017). Stressing Servant Leadership in a Land of Big Men and Great Men. *Melanesian Journal of Theology*. 23 (1), pp. 6-21.

Sekaran, U. and Bougie, R. (2010). *Research methods for business: A skill-building approach*. (5th ed.). Haddington: John Wiley & Sons.

Sendjaya, S. (2005). Morality and leadership: Examining the ethics of transformational leadership. *Journal of Academic Ethics*. 3(1), pp. 75-63

Sendjaya, S. and Cooper, B. (2011) Servant Leadership Behaviour Scale: A hierarchical model and test of construct validity, *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 20 (3), pp. 416-436.

Sendjaya, S. and Pekerti, A. (2010) Servant leadership as antecedent of trust in organizations, *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*. 31 (7) , pp.643-663

Sendjaya, S. and Sarros, J. C. (2002). Servant leadership: Its origin, development, and application in organizations. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 9 (2), pp. 57-64.

Sendjaya, S., Sarros, J. and Santora, J. (2008). Defining and Measuring Servant Leadership Behaviour in Organizations. *Journal of Management Studies*. 45 (2), pp. 402-424.

Serrano, C. (2014). Charismatic and Servant Leadership as Seen in King Saul and Young David: An Inner Texture Analysis of 1 Samuel 17: 1–58. *Journal of Biblical Perspectives in Leadership*. 6 (1), pp. 27-40.

Shanghai, L., Tong, J., Hu, W. and Cheng, Y. (2014). From the West to the East Validating Servant Leadership in the Chinese Public Sector. *Public Personnel Management*. 44 (1), pp. 25-40.

Sheehan, M. (2013). Human resource management and performance: evidence from small and medium-sized firms. *International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship*. 32 (5), pp. 545-570.

Shields, P. and Rangarajan, N. (2013). *A Playbook for Research Methods: Integrating Conceptual Frameworks and Project Management*. Oklahoma: New Forums Press.

Shim, D., Park, H. and Eom, T. (2016) Public servant leadership: Myth or powerful reality? *International Review of Public Administration*, 21 (1), pp. 3-20.

Sihombing, S., Astuti, E., Al Musadieq, M., Hamied, D., and Rahardjo, K. (2018). The effect of servant leadership on rewards, organizational culture and its

implication for employee's performance, *International Journal of Law and Management*, 60 (2), pp.505-516.

Silverman, D. (2000) *Doing qualitative research: A practical handbook*. London, Thousand Oaks, New Delhi: Sage Publications Inc.

Simmons, A. and Branch, L. (2015). Have You Paid Your Rent? Servant Leadership in Correctional Education. *Journal of Prison Education and Reentry*. 2 (1), pp. 70-73.

Simons, D. and Levin, S. (1998). Failure to detect change to people during a real-world interaction. *Psychonomic Bulletin & Review*. 5 (4), pp. 644-649.

Simpson, M. and Docherty, A. (2004). E-commerce adoption support and advice for UK SMEs. *Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development*. 11 (3), pp. 315-328.

Sims, B. (1997). *Servanthood: Leadership for the Third Millennium*. Cambridge, MA: Cowley.

Sinclair, A. (1992) The Tyranny of a Team Ideology. *Organization Studies*. 13 (4), pp. 611–626.

Siropolis, N.C. (1997). *Small business management*. (6th ed). Boston: Houghton Mifflin Co. pp. 1-52.

Slavin, R. (1986). Best-Evidence Synthesis: An Alternative to Meta-Analytic and Traditional Reviews. *Educational Researcher*. 15 (9), pp. 5-1.

Slavin, R. E. (1986). Cooperative learning: Engineering social psychology in the classroom. In R. S. Feldman (Ed.), *The social psychology of education: Current research and theory* (p. 153–171). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Small Business Service. (2005). *Annual Report and Resource Accounts 2005-06*. Available:

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/231561/1507.pdf. Last accessed 8/4/2021.

Smith, B. Ray. V. Montagno, R. V. and Montagno Kuzmenko, T. (2004). Transformational and Servant Leadership: Content and Contextual Comparisons. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*. 10 (4), pp. 80-91.

Sober, E. (2013). *Core Questions in Philosophy: A Text with Readings* (6th ed.). Boston: Pearson Education.

Somekh, B. and Lewin, C. (2005) *Research methods in the social sciences*. California Thousand Oaks: Sage.

Song, C., Park, K. and Kang, S. (2015). Servant leadership and team performance: The mediating role of knowledge-sharing climate. *Social Behaviour and Personality: An international journal*, 43 (10), pp. 1749-1760

Sousa, M. and Van Dierendonck, D. (2014). Servant Leadership and Engagement in a Merge Process Under High Uncertainty. *Journal of Organizational Change Management*. 27 (6) pp.877-899.

Sousa, M. and van Dierendonck, D. (2017). Servant Leadership and the Effect of the Interaction Between Humility, Action, and Hierarchical Power on Follower Engagement. *Journal of Business Ethics*. 141 (1), pp 13–25.

Spears, L. (1996). Reflections on Robert K. Greenleaf and servant-leadership. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*. 17(7): pp. 33-35

Spears, L. (2010). The Journal of Virtues & Leadership. *Character and Servant Leadership: Ten Characteristics of Effective, Caring Leaders*. 1 (1), pp. 25-30

Spears, L. (1995), Servant-leadership and the Greenleaf legacy, in Spears, L., *Reflections on Leadership: How Robert K. Greenleaf's Theory of Servant-leadership Influenced Today's Top Management Thinkers*, New York: John Wiley, pp. 1-14.

Spears, L. (1996). Reflections on Robert K. Greenleaf and servant-leadership. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*. 17 (7), pp. 33-35

Spears, L. C. (1998). Introduction: Tracing the growing impact of servant-leadership. In L. C. Spears (Ed.), *Insights on Leadership: Service, Stewardship, Spirit, and Servant-Leadership* New York: Wiley pp. 1-12.

Spector, B. A. (2016). Carlyle, Freud, and the great man theory more fully considered. *Leadership*, 12(2), 250–260.

Stentz, J., Clark, C. and Matkin, G. (2012). Applying mixed methods to leadership research: A review of current practices. *The Leadership Quarterly*. 23 (6), pp. 1173-1183.

Stewart, J.A. (2009). Evaluation of an action learning programme for leadership development of SME leaders in the UK. *Action Learning, Research and Practice* 6 (2), pp. 131-148.

Stogdill, R. M. (1974). *Handbook of Leadership*. New York: Free Press.

Stone, A. Russell, R. and Patterson, K. (2004). Transformational versus servant leadership: a difference in leader focus. *Leadership and Organisation Development Journal*. 25 (4), pp. 349-361

Stoten, D.W. (2013). Servant leadership in English sixth form colleges: what do teachers tell us? *International Journal of Educational Management*. 24 (4), pp. 377-386

Strauss, A. and Corbin, J. (1998). *Basics of qualitative research: Techniques and procedures for developing grounded theory* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks California: Sage Publications, Inc.

Sturm, B. (2008). Principles of Servant-Leadership in Community Health Nursing Management Issues and Behaviours Discovered in Ethnographic Research. *Home Health Care Management & Practice*. 21 (2), pp. 82-89

- Sugrue, C. (2009). Performativity and Professionalism: Irish Primary Principals' Experience of Building Leadership Capacity. *European Educational Research Journal*. 8(3), pp. 372–386.
- Sundararajan, M., Sundararajan, B. and Henderson, S. (2012). Role of Meditative Foundation in Entrepreneurial Leadership and New Venture Success. *Spirituality, Leadership and Management Inc.* 6 (1), pp. 59-70.
- Surie, G. and Ashley, A. (2008). Integrating Pragmatism and Ethics in Entrepreneurial Leadership for Sustainable Value Creation. *Journal of Business Ethics*. 81(1), pp. 235-246.
- Sutton, J. and Austin, Z. (2015). Qualitative Research: Data Collection, Analysis, and Management. *Canadian Journal of Hospital Pharmacy*. 68 (3), pp. 226–231.
- Taherdoost, H. (2016). Sampling Methods in Research Methodology; How to Choose a Sampling Technique for Research. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. 5 (2), pp. 18-27.
- Tang, G., Kwan, H.K. and Zhang, D. (2016). Work–Family Effects of Servant Leadership: The Roles of Emotional Exhaustion and Personal Learning. *Journal of Business Ethics*. 137 (2), pp 285–297.
- Taylor, T., Martin, B., Hutchinson, S. and Jinks, M. (2007). Examination of leadership practices of principals identified as servant leaders. *International Journal of Leadership in Education Theory and Practice*. 10(4), pp. 401-419.
- Tesch, J., Baptista, A., Frick, L. and Holley, K. (2015). The doctorate as an original contribution to knowledge: Considering relationships between originality, creativity, and innovation. *Frontline Learning Research*. 3 (3), pp. 51-63.
- Thacker, J. W. and Blanchard, P. N. (2004). *Effective Training: Systems, Strategies, and Practices* (5th ed.). New York: Pearson Education International

The Federal Council. (N.D.). *SME Portal for small and medium sized enterprises*. Available: <https://www.kmu.admin.ch/kmu/en/home.html>. Last accessed 8/4/21.

Thomas G. and James, T. (2006). Reinventing grounded theory: some questions about theory, ground and discovery. *British Educational Research Journal*. 32 (6), pp. 767-795.

Thomas, D. (2006). A General Inductive Approach for Analyzing Qualitative Evaluation Data. *Research Methods and Evaluation*. 27 (2), pp. 237-246.

Thomas, D. and Hodges, I. (2010). *Designing and Managing Your Research Project: Core Skills for Social and Health Research*. London: Sage Publications Inc.

Thompson, A. (2014). *Research Methodology in Marketing*. Hertfordshire: KOROS PRESS LIMITED.

Todorov, K. and Smallbone, D. (2014) *Handbook of Strategic Management in Small and Medium Enterprises Theory and Practice*. Hershey: IGI Global.

Tourish, D. and Pinnington, A. (2002). Transformational Leadership, Corporate Cultism and the Spirituality Paradigm: An Unholy Trinity in the Workplace? *Human Relations*. 55 (2), pp. 147-172.

Tranfield, D., Denyer, D. and Smart, P. (2003). Towards a Methodology for Developing Evidence-Informed Management Knowledge by Means of Systematic Review. *British Journal of Management*. 14 (1), pp. 207-222.

Trevino, L. K. and Brown, M. E. (2004). Managing to be Ethical: Debunking Five Business Ethics Myths. *Academy of Management Executive*, 18(2), pp. 69-81.

U.K. Parliament. (1998). *SMALL AND MEDIUM SIZED ENTERPRISES*. Available: <https://publications.parliament.uk/pa/cm199798/cmselect/cmtrdind/774/77406.htm>. Last accessed 13/4/21.

U.S. Small Business Administration. (2016). *2016 Small Business Profiles for the States and Territories*. Available: <https://www.sba.gov/advocacy/small-business-profiles-states-and-territories-2016>. Last accessed 8/1/2021.

Uchenwamgbe, B. (2013). Effects of Leadership Style on Organizational Performance in Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) in Nigeria. *European Journal of Business Management*. 5 (23), pp 23-30.

Uhl-Bien, M., Riggio, R., Lowe, K.B. and Carsten, M. (2014). Followership Theory: A Review and Research Agenda. *The leadership quarterly*. 25 (1), pp. 83-104.

Uman, L. (2011). Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses. *Journal of the Canadian Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry*. 20 (1), pp. 57-59.

University of Stirling (2016). *Learning in Smaller Companies*. Stirling: Educational Policy and Development. pp.3-50.

US International Trade Commission. (2010). *Small and Medium- Sized Enterprises: Characteristics and Performance*. Available: <https://www.usitc.gov/publications/332/pub4125.pdf>. Last accessed 8/1/21.

University of the West of Scotland. (2016). *Guidelines for Ethical Practice*. Available: <https://www.uws.ac.uk/media/5544/guidelines-for-ethical-practice-in-research-and-scholarship-refreshed-september-2019.pdf>. Last accessed 14/4/21.

van Breukelen, W., Schyns, B. and Le Blanc, P. (2006) Leader-Member Exchange theory and research: accomplishments and future challenges. *Leadership* 2(3): pp. 295-316.

van Dierendonck, D. (2010). Servant Leadership: A Review and Synthesis. *Journal of Management*. 37 (4), pp. 1228-1261.

van Dierendonck, D. (2017). Leading people positively: cross-cultural validation of the Servant Leadership Survey (SLS). *Spanish Journal of Psychology*. 7 (2), pp. 17-63.

van Dierendonck D and Nuijten I (2011) The Servant Leadership Survey: Development and Validation of a Multidimensional Measure. *Journal of Business Psychology*. 26(3): pp. 249-267

van Dierendonck D, Sousa M, Gunnarsdóttir S, Bobbio A, Hakanen J, Pircher V, A., Cihan Duyan E and Rodriguez-Carvajal, R. (2017). The Cross-Cultural Invariance of the Servant Leadership Survey: A Comparative Study across Eight Countries. *Administrative Sciences*. 7(2): pp. 1 -11

van Dierendonck, D. and Patterson, K. (2014). Compassionate Love as a Cornerstone of Servant Leadership: An Integration of Previous Theorizing and Research. *Journal of Business Ethics*. 28 (1), pp. 119–131.

Van Winkle, B. Allen, S., DeVore, S. and Winston, B. (2014). The Relationship Between the Servant Leadership Behaviours of Immediate Supervisors and Followers' Perceptions of Being Empowered in the Context of Small Business. *The Journal of Leadership Education*. 13 (3), pp. 70-82.

Van Zyl, H. and Mathur-Helm, B. (2007). Exploring a conceptual model, based on the combined effects of entrepreneurial leadership, market orientation and relationship marketing orientation on South Africa's small tourism business performance. *South African Journal of Business Management*. 38(2), pp. 17-24

VanMeter, R., Chonko, L., Grisaffe, D. and Goad, E. (2016). In search of clarity on servant leadership: domain specification and reconceptualization. *AMS Review*. 6 (1), pp. 59-78.

Vecchio, R. P. (2003). Entrepreneurship and leadership: common trends and common threads. *Human Resource Management Review*, 13(2), pp. 303–327.

Veiga, M.C. and McCahery, J. (2019). The Financing of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises: An Analysis of the Financing Gap in Brazil. *European Business Organization Law Review*. 2014 (7), pp. 633–664.

Veiss, S. (2016). Charismatic, Transformational, and Servant Leadership in the United States, Mexico, and Croatia. *International Journal of Business and Social Research*. 6 (2), pp. 25-34.

Verdorfer, A., Duyan, E. and Rodriguez-Carvaja, R. (2017). The Cross-Cultural Invariance of the Servant Leadership Survey: A Comparative Study across Eight Countries. *Administrative Sciences*. 7 (2). pp. 1 -11.

Vincent, B. (2014). *Spiritual Leadership*. Online: Lulu.com. pp. 1 - 240.

Vine, W.E. (1985). *Vine's expository Dictionary of Biblical words*. Nashville, T.N: Thomas Nelson.

Walley, K. (2000). TQM in Non-Manufacturing SMEs: Evidence from the UK Farming Sector. *International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship*. 18 (4), pp.1-48.

Walumbawa, F., Lawler, J., Avolio, B., Wang, P. and Shi, K. (2005). Transformational Leadership and Work-Related Attitudes: The Moderating Effects of Collective and Self-Efficacy Across Cultures. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*. 11 (3), pp. 2-16.

Walumbwa, F. O., Avolio, B. J., Gardner, W. L., Wernsing, T.S. and Peterson, S. (2008), Authentic leadership: Development and validation of a theory-based measure. *Journal of Management*. 34 (1), pp. 89-126.

Wang, Y. and Poutzoris, P. (2010). Leadership Styles, Management Systems and Growth: Empirical Evidence from UK Owner-Managed SMEs. *Journal of Enterprising Culture*. 18(3), pp. 331-354.

Washington, R. R., Sutton, C. D. and Feild, H. S. (2006). Individual differences in servant leadership: The roles of values and personality. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 27(8), 700–716.

White, J. D. (1999). *The narrative foundations of public administration research*. Washington, DC: Georgetown University Press.

Wienclaw, R.A. (2013). *E-Commerce*. Online: Research Starters: Business

Wiley. (2018). *Librarians*. Available: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/library-info/products/journals>. Last accessed 14/4/21.

William, B. and Evans, D. (1989). Small Business Economics. *Small Business Economics* 1(1), pp. 7-20.

Wilson, R. (1999). Servant Leadership. *International Journal of Care Coordination*. 3(2), pp. 100-107

Wilson, H., Daniel, E. and Davies, I. (2008). The diffusion of e-commerce in UK SMEs. *Journal of Marketing Management*. 24(5-6), pp. 489–516.

Winston, B. (2004). Servant leadership at Heritage Bible College: a single-case study. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*. 25(7), pp. 600-617

Winston, B. and Fields, D. (2015). Seeking and measuring the essential behaviours of servant leadership. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 36(4), pp. 413-434

Winston, B. and Ryan, B. (2008). Servant Leadership as a Humane Orientation: Using the GLOBE Study Construct of Humane Orientation to Show that Servant Leadership is More Global than Western. *International Journal of Leadership Studies*. 3(2), pp. 212-222

- Wiśniowski, A., Sakshaug, J. Ruiz, D.A.P. and Blom, A. (2020). Integrating Probability and Nonprobability Samples for Survey Inference. *Journal of Survey Statistics and Methodology*. 8 (1), pp. -20260- 216918-27.
- Wong, A., Liu, Y., Wang, X. and Tjosvold, D. (2016). Servant leadership for team conflict management, co-ordination, and customer relationships. *Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resources*. 56 (2), pp. 238-259.
- Wright, P. (1996). *Managerial leadership*. London: Routledge.
- Wright, P. and Taylor, D. (1994). *Improving Leadership Performance: Interpersonal Skills for Effective Leadership*. New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Xu, L., Trae, S. and Haber-Curran, P. (2015). Measurement Invariance of the "Servant Leadership Questionnaire" across K-12 Principal Gender. *School Leadership & Management*. 35 (2), pp. 202-214
- Yammarino, F. (2013) Leadership: Past, present and future. *Journal of Leadership and Organisational Studies*. 20 (2) pp. 149-155.
- Yan, A. and Xiao, Y. (2016). Servant leadership and employee voice behavior: a cross-level investigation in China. *SpringerPlus*. 5 (1), pp. 1-15
- Yang, J., Liu, H. and Gu, J. (2017). A multi-level study of servant leadership on creativity: The roles of self-efficacy and power distance. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*. 38 (5), pp. 610-629.
- Yasir, M. and Mohammed, N. (2016). Ethics and Morality: Comparing Ethical Leadership with Servant, Authentic and Transformational Leadership Styles. *International Review of Management and Marketing*. 6(S4), pp.310-316.
- Yigit, B. and Bozkurt, S. (2017). A content analysis of servant leadership studies. *International Journal of Organizational Leadership*. 6(2), pp. 190-196

Yin R.K. (1994). Discovering the Future of the Case Study. Method in Evaluation Research. *Evaluation Practice*. 15 (3), pp. 283-290.

Yukl, G (2010). *Leadership in Organizations*. 7th ed. New York: Pearsons.

Yukl, G. (2006). *Leadership in Organizations* (6th ed.). Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Pearson Education.

Yukl, G. (2013). *Leadership in Organisations*, 8th ed., Pearson: Essex.

Zaccaro, S., Kemp, C. and Bader, P. (2004). Leader traits and attributes. In J, Antonakis, A, Cianciolo, & R Sternberg (Eds.), *The Nature of Leadership*. Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publications.

Zahra S., Gedajlovic E., Neubaum, D. and Shulman, J. (2004). A typology of social entrepreneurs: Motives, search processes and ethical challenges. *Journal of Business Venturing*. 23(1), pp. 519–532.

Zaridis, A.D. and Mousiolis, D.T. (2014). Entrepreneurship and SME's Organizational Structure. Elements of a Successful Business. *Procedia - Social and Behavioural Sciences*. 148 (10), pp. 463-467.

Zhao, C., Liu, Y. and Gao, Z. (2016). An identification perspective of servant leadership's effects. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*. 31 (5). pp.898-913

Participant Information Sheet

Research project title:

Servant leadership in SMEs: A study of Scotland

Research investigator:

Katie Mcquade

Address & contact details of research investigator:

Personal details
withheld.

I would like to invite you to take part in this research study. Please take time to read the following information carefully. Ask further questions if anything you read is not clear or if you would like more information to be provided. Please take time to decide whether or not to participate.

About the project:

The purpose of this project is to examine the skills required for leadership within Small to Medium Enterprises within Scotland. The research is aiming particular to focus on the skills necessary for servant leadership. Servant leadership is considered an ethical form of leadership, which is concerned with putting the needs of the follower first. The servant leader aims to serve the follower, providing support and guidance wherever possible. The main objective of this project is to determine the skills necessary for servant leadership within SMEs in Scotland.

What Participation will entail:

Participants will take part in a semi-structured, audio-recorded interview that will last around 45-60 minutes, at a location of the participant's choice. If participants find it more convenient, interviews can also be conducted over video conferencing. If participants are not comfortable with audio recordings, please inform the investigator and field notes can be taken instead. Interviews will be recorded for the purposes of transcription. The research investigator will only access all data gathered. Furthermore, after transcription the recordings will be destroyed. All participants will be kept anonymous. The data will not be shared with any organization.

.

What are your rights as a participant?

Taking part in the study is voluntary. You may choose not to take part or subsequently cease participation at any time.

If you have any further questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me

APPENDIX TWO: INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Informed Consent Form

I, the undersigned, confirm that (please tick box as appropriate):

1.	I have read and understood the information about the project, as provided in the Information Sheet.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.	I have been given the opportunity to ask questions about the project and my participation.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.	I voluntarily agree to participate in the project.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.	I understand I can withdraw at any time without giving reasons and that I will not be penalised for withdrawing nor will I be questioned on why I have withdrawn.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5.	The procedures regarding confidentiality and data protection have been clearly explained to me.	<input type="checkbox"/>
6.	I understand and approve of the use of a recording device(s) within the interview process.	<input type="checkbox"/>
7.	The use of the data in research, publications, sharing and archiving has been explained to me.	<input type="checkbox"/>
8.	I understand that only the researcher will have access to this data.	<input type="checkbox"/>
9.	I, along with the Researcher, agree to sign and date this informed consent form.	<input type="checkbox"/>

Participant:

Name of Participant

Signature

Date

Researcher:

Name of Researcher

Signature

Date

APPENDIX THREE: LETTER TO PARTICIPANTS

Dear (insert participants name),

I am a PhD researcher at the University of the West of Scotland currently conducting my PhD thesis. This letter is an invitation to consider participating in leadership research I would like to provide you with more information about this project and what your involvement would entail if you decided to take part.

My research is entitled:

Servant leadership in SMEs: A study of Scotland

In order to conduct this research, I would be looking to hold a semi-structured interview with you which would last around 45 minutes to an hour,

By participating in the interview, you will be contributing to valuable research that will allow for the creation of a framework outlining the servant leadership skills necessary within small to medium enterprises. It will also allow for research to be developed the impact of servant leadership. After the research is completed a copy of the final project will be made available to you, so you can view the final results and findings of the research.

You will be able to remain anonymous throughout the process, thus ensuring the protection of their privacy. Whilst field notes and audio recordings will be used throughout the interview process, you can be assured that only the researcher will hear or view their personal data.

Yours Sincerely,

Katie Mcquade

MBA, PgDip, BAHons

Please find attached a consent form, information sheet and interview protocol.

APPENDIX FOUR: EMAIL TO PARTICIPANTS

To whom it may concern

I am a PhD researcher at the University of the West of Scotland and I am undertaking my thesis, which is entitled:

"Servant Leadership in SMES: A study of Scotland."

I would like to interview a leader and an employee within your organisation to participate in a short series of interviews I am conducting into leadership within Small to Medium Sized Enterprises in Scotland.

By participating in an interview, you will be contributing to valuable leadership research. This research will allow for an understanding of the servant leadership skills necessary within small to medium enterprises. It will also allow for research to be developed concerning impact of servant leadership on organisations. After the research is completed a copy of the final project will be made available to you. This will enable you to view the valuable results and findings of the research which you have participated in.

In order to conduct the primary research, I will be looking to hold semi-structured interviews with you and, additionally, an employee within your organisation. I would like to interview you at your own convenience and, interviews will not take any longer than 45 to 60 minutes. Please find attached Participant Information Sheet for more information.

If you would be interested in participating or wish to ask for any further information, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Thank you for your time and consideration.

Yours Sincerely,

Katie McQuade

Questions for Leaders

The Opening Segment: Creating Space for a Narrative Grounded in Participant Experience

- 1) Introduction to the researcher and the research to be undertaken. Additionally, ensure that the participant is comfortable with the research and all aspects of consent
 - 2) Allow participant to discuss themselves and their organisation
 - 3) Explain the concept of servant leadership and explain the concept of skills
 - 4) Invite the participant to ask any questions they may have regarding the research
-

Middle Section: Questions of Greater Specificity

Part One - Servant Leadership:

- 1) Enquire about participants opinion on their approach to leadership
- 2) Do you believe that you serve those in your organisation? If yes, what skills does this require?
- 3) Do you try to serve within the community? If yes, what skills do you believe this requires?
- 4) Do you try to promote employee empowerment and development? What skills do you believe this takes?
- 5) What experiences do you think have shaped your approach to leadership?
- 6) How do you think your approach to leadership has contributed towards the success of your organisation?

Part Two: Skills

- 1) What skills do you think are necessary in order to fulfil your roles and responsibilities?

- 2) How do you think your experiences have enabled you to develop those skills?
 - 3) Explain the concept of technical conceptual and interpersonal skills
 - 4) What technical skills would you say you possess?
 - 5) What conceptual skills would you say you possess?
 - 6) What interpersonal skills would you say you possess?
-

Concluding segment: Revisiting the Opening Narrative for Important Theoretical Connections and Moving Towards Closure

- 1) Address any issues/ areas of further development you feel were identified within the interview
 - 2) Ask participant if there was anything additional, they would like to add
 - 3) Thank them for their time – reiterate consent
-

Questions for Employees

The Opening Segment: Creating Space for a Narrative Grounded in Participant Experience

- 5) Introduction to the researcher and the research to be undertaken. Additionally, ensure that the participant is comfortable with the research and all aspects of consent
 - 6) Allow participant to discuss themselves and their organisation
 - 7) Explain the concept of servant leadership and explain the concept of skills
 - 8) Invite the participant to ask any questions they may have regarding the research
-

Middle Section: Questions of Greater Specificity

Part One - Servant Leadership:

- 7) Enquire about participants opinion on their leaders' approach to leadership
- 8) Do you believe that your leader serves those in your organisation? If yes, what skills does this require?
- 9) Do you believe that your leader tries to serve within the community? If yes, what skills do you believe this requires?
- 10) Do you believe that your leader promotes employee empowerment and development? What skills do you believe this takes?
- 11) What experiences do you think have shaped your leaders' approach to leadership?
- 12) How do you think this approach to leadership has contributed towards the success of your organisation?

Part Two – Skills

- 7) What skills do you think are necessary in order for your leader to order to fulfil their roles and responsibilities?
 - 8) How do you think their experiences have enabled them to develop those skills?
 - 9) Explain the concept of technical conceptual and interpersonal skills
 - 10)What technical skills would you say your leader possesses?
 - 11)What conceptual skills would you say your leader possesses?
 - 12)What interpersonal skills would you say your leader possesses?
-

Concluding segment: Revisiting the Opening Narrative for Important Theoretical Connections and Moving Towards Closure

- 4) Address any issues/ areas of further development you feel were identified within the interview
- 5) Ask participant if there was anything additional, they would like to add
- 6) Thank them for their time – reiterate consent

APPENDIX 7: SEARCH STRING PROCESS

Servant leadership in title

Exact phrase: servant leadership

- Springer
Initial search: 103
Inclusion/Exclusion: 83
- Emerald Insight
Initial search: 78
Inclusion/Exclusion: 48
- Taylor and Francis
Initial search: 66
Inclusion/Exclusion criteria: 47
- SAGE Publications
Initial search: 99
Inclusion/Exclusion criteria: 67
- Wiley Online
Initial search: 46
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 37
- Web of Science
Initial search: 307
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 186

Serv*** AND lead***** in title

Skills anywhere

- Wiley Online
Initial search: – 28
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 20

- Emerald-
Initial search: 209
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 27

- SAGE Publications
Initial search:194
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 21

- Taylor and Francis
Initial search: 274
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 25

- Web of Science
Initial search:77
Inclusion/exclusion: 7

- SpringerLink
Initial search: 1
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 0

Servant AND lead***** in title

Servant leadership anywhere

- Wiley
Initial search: 40
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 40

- SAGE online
Initial search: 101
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 68

- Springerlink
Initial search: 2
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 1

- Emerald Insight
Initial search: 79
Inclusion/Exclusion criteria: 68

- Taylor And Francis Online:
Initial search: 68
Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria: 46

- Serve and lead***** in title
Servant leadership anywhere

- Web of science
Initial search: 10
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 8

- Taylor and Francis Online
Initial search: 68
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 44

- SAGE publications

Initial search: 100
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 65

- Wiley
Initial search: 48
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 32
- Springer
Initial search: 0
- Taylor and Francis online:
Initial search: 68
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 45

Serv*** AND lead***** in title

Behav**** OR traits OR characteristics OR personality anywhere

- Taylor and Francis Online
Initial search: 397
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 40
- Wileyonline
Initial search: 221
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 24
- Emerald Insight
Initial search: 273
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 52
- Web of Science
Initial search: 391
Inclusion/exclusion criteria: 101

- Springerlink
Initial search: 1
Inclusion/exclusion: 0
- SAGE
Initial search: 266
Inclusion/exclusion: 33

APPENDIX 8: PARTICIPANT INFORMATION

Leader	Employee	Geographical Location
Leader A	Employee A	Large Urban Area
Leader B	Employee B	Other Urban Area
Leader C	Employee C	Accessible Small Town
Leader D	Employee D	Large Urban Area
Leader E	Employee E	Large Urban Area
Leader F	Employee F	Remote Small Town
Leader G	Employee G	Accessible Rural Town
Leader H	Employee H	Accessible Small Town
Leader I	Employee I	Remote Rural Town
Leader J	Employee J	Remote Rural Town
Leader K	Employee K	Other Urban Area
Leader L	Employee L	Accessible Rural Town
Leader M	Employee M	Large Urban Area
Leader N	Employee N	Large Urban Area
Leader O	Employee O	Other Urban Area

Ethics approval application form (UEC1.1)

Pre-screening questions:

(Please read the UWS and your School Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship before answering these questions, which will help you decide whether or not you need to make a full ethics approval application for your work).

Does your work involve human participants? YES

Does your work involve the use of personal data? YES

Does your work involve the use of animals? NO

(For this purpose animals are defined as captive or temporarily captive living vertebrates or cephalopods. If such work is already licensed under the terms of the Animals Scientific procedures act (ASPA) then no further ethics approval is required)

Does your work involve risk to the investigator that is not adequately mitigated by proper application of the University's health and safety policies and procedures? NO

If you have answered **YES** to **any** of the above questions you should complete the remainder of this form and submit it to your school ethics committee for approval **PRIOR** to commencing any work on your project.

If you have answered **NO** to **all** of the above questions your research/scholarship would be Class 1 as defined in the UWS Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship and so you do not need the approval of a School Ethics Committee for your work.

1. Name of Principal Investigator: Katie Mcquade

2. School: Business and Enterprise

2b. If you answered "other" above please provide details below:

3. Position of Principal Investigator: Postgraduate student

4. Name and contact details of collaborators:

Personal details
withheld.

5. Name of Supervisor/Director of Studies: Christian Harrison
(for student applications only)

5a. Position of Supervisor/Director of Studies: Lecturer in management, strategy and leadership
(for student applications only)

5b. School of Supervisor/Director of Studies: Business and Enterprise
(for student applications only)

6. Title of the study: Servant Leadership: The Skills of Those who Serve

7. Primary purpose of the study: Postgraduate dissertation
If you answered “other” to this question please provide details below:

8. Has the proposed study been considered by any other ethics committee? NO
If the study has been considered by another ethics committee please provide details below:

9. Please give a full summary of the purpose, justification, design and methodology of the planned study:
(word limit 1000 words. A full study protocol should be attached to your application)

10. How has the scientific quality of the proposed research project been assessed?

- | | |
|--|-------------------------------------|
| Independent external review | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Review within a company | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Review within a multi-centre research group | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Review within the principal investigator’s institution | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Review within the research team | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Review by supervisor/director of studies | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> |
| Other | <input type="checkbox"/> |

If you answered “other” above please provide details below:

11. Please explain/justify your intended sample size:

12. Please explain how you will analyse, present/disseminate the data you intend to collect:

13. Does the proposed research involve the use of individual/group interviews or questionnaires?

YES

13a. Will proposed interviews or questionnaires discuss topics that might be sensitive, embarrassing or upsetting for participants or is it possible that criminal or other disclosures requiring action could occur during the study?

NO

If you have answered **YES** to the question above please provide details below and how you propose to deal with such issues:

14. Is the study likely to cause any discomfort or distress, either physical or psychological (see UWS Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Research and Scholarship)?

No

If you have answered **Yes** to the question above please provide details below and how you propose to deal with this:

15. Does the proposed research involve any physically invasive procedures? NO

If physically invasive procedures are to be used what hazards are associated with them?

16. Please identify any other ethical considerations with the proposed study.

N/A

17. Does the proposed research involve deception regarding aims, objectives or the identity of the investigator? NO

If you have answered **YES** to the above question please provide an explanation/justification of this deception:

18. Will research participants be debriefed after their participation? NO

If you have answered **YES** to the above question please provide details of when this debriefing will take place, who will do it and how it will be done:

19. What is the expected duration of participation in the study for each participant?

One hour

20. Please provide details of how you will recruit participants to your study:

Participants have been identified in the Scottish SMEs directory and through pre-existing contacts. Participants will be contacted via email in order to recruit them into partaking in this study.

21. What measures will you put in place to ensure the confidentiality of personal data gathered during your study?

Participants and their organisations will have their anonymity protected throughout their participation in this research. They will additionally be provided with a consent form which will verify and ensure them of their privacy.

22. Who will have access to the data collected during the study and how will you keep it confidential?

23. Will informed consent be obtained from study participants? YES

If you have answered **YES** to the above question please provide details of how you will obtain this consent and the information you will provide to potential participants to allow them to make an informed choice about whether or not to participate in your research.

Participants will be provided with a consent form detailing

If you have answered **NO** to the above question please justify your decision not to obtain consent from your participants.

24. How long will potential participants have to decide whether or not to take part in the study?

25. Will participants be informed that they can withdraw from the study at any time?

Choose an item.

26. Will participants be from any of the following groups?

- | | | |
|--|-------------------------------------|--------------------------|
| Children under 16 | <input type="checkbox"/> | |
| Adults with learning disabilities | | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Adults who are unconscious or severely ill | <input type="checkbox"/> | |
| Adults with a terminal illness | <input type="checkbox"/> | |
| Adults in emergency situations | | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Adults with mental illness
(particularly if detained under the mental health act) | <input type="checkbox"/> | |
| Adults with dementia | <input type="checkbox"/> | |
| Adults in Scotland who are unable to consent for themselves | | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Those who could be considered to have a particularly
dependent relationship with the investigator | <input type="checkbox"/> | |
| Other | <input type="checkbox"/> | |
| None of the above | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | |

If you answered “**other**” above please provide details:

If you intend to include participants from any of the above groups please outline how you will mitigate the risks involved:

27. Are there any special pressures which would make it difficult for potential participants to refuse to take part in your study?

(e.g., relationship to the investigator?)

28. Will study participants be paid to take part? NO

If you have answered YES to the above question please provide details of the payments involved:

29. Where will the proposed research take place?

Participants work places

30. How will the costs of the study be met?

Principal investigators own finances

31. Please indicate which supporting documents you are submitting with this application:

- | | | |
|---|-------------------------------------|--------------------------|
| Participant information sheet (PIS) | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | |
| Consent form | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | |
| Copy of the protocol | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | |
| Letters to participants | <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | |
| Letters to parent/guardians/gatekeepers etc | <input type="checkbox"/> | |
| Letter or ethical committee approval or other approvals | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| Risk assessments | <input type="checkbox"/> | |
| Other relevant materials (please specify below) | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

The information supplied above is, to the best of my knowledge and belief, accurate. I have read the university ethics guidelines and clearly understand my obligations and the rights of study participants, particularly in relation to obtaining valid consent.

Signature of the principal investigator(s):

Date: [Click here to enter a date.](#)

Signature of the supervisor/director of studies:

(if applicable)

Date: [Click here to enter a date.](#)